

School for Advanced Studies in Social Sciences
Paris, France

Master Degree Research in Social Sciences

Mention Southern and Eastern Asia
Fieldwork, Texts and Social Sciences

Academic Year 2018-2019

Economic Strategies of an Orang Asli Village in Endau-Rompin National Park, Malaysia

By Aude Vidal
Under the direction of Pr. Bernard Sellato

September 2019

Members of the Jury: Pr. Bernard Sellato and Dr. Elsa Lafaye de Micheaux

Terima kasih

I would like to thank the people of Kampung Peta who welcome me to their village, especially Sima Sangka and her family, whose help was very precious to me, as well as Rado Sangka and Ny Aina Raharinarivonirina who transcribed my most difficult interviews, and my classmates Luna Michel and Aina on whom I was able to rely for translations from Malay.

Thanks to my friends from Malaysia, especially Shamila Ariffin, Theivanai Amarthalingam and Shervin Cheong who for more than five years have been trying to make me understand the mysteries of Malaysian politics. Thanks also to Auntie Ong Mui Ling and her husband for the stories of *bomoh* and cobras. Thanks to Pascale-Marie Milan and Franck Michel for their answers to my questions about anthropology of tourism.

I would also like to thank *para pengajar* in Malaysian and Indonesian at Inalco who taught me the little Malay I know, as well as Paul Wormser and Mathieu Guérin who, after having taught me some rudiments of history, remained available during this master year to answer my questions.

I am very grateful to Colin Nicholas of the Center for Orang Asli Concerns who made it possible for me to be welcome in Kampung Peta and gave me access to precious references and texts, to Dr Lye Tuck-Po of Univiversiti Sains Malaysia who kindly supported my request for a permit from the Malaysian authorities and offered very useful hints, and to Pr Dr Shanthi Thambiah of University of Malaya for her friendly availability to my questions in a free-wheeling conversation.

Finally, I would like to thank the teachers of the Southern and Eastern Asia Master who offered me a field grant, as well as Irène Bellier and Emmanuelle Ricaud Oneto, Amandine Dabat and the students of the Asia seminar, Benoît de l'Estoile and the students of the Oikonomia seminar, Francis Zimmermann, Clotilde Luquiau who gave me her advice during the writing of this thesis, Elsa Lafaye de Micheaux for more than her teaching and Bernard Sellato for his supervision throughout this year.

I hope that I have benefited to the best of my ability from all these lessons, but I remain the only one to blame for the weaknesses of my work.

Summary

Terima kasih.....	2
Introduction.....	5
Chapter 1. Orang Asli in Malaysia.....	7
Chapter 2. Kampung Peta.....	15
Chapter 3. Rituals and Society.....	23
Chapter 4. Subsistence Activities.....	41
Chapter 5. Primary Sector Commercial Activities.....	53
Chapter 6. Self-Employment (Except Primary Sector) and Wage Employment.....	69
Chapter 7. Tourism Economy.....	81
Chapter 8. Several Effects of Market Economy.....	101
Conclusion.....	115
Appendices.....	117
Glossary.....	118
Interviews.....	120
Households Sources of Income.....	121
Maps, Diagrams and Photos.....	122
List of Photographs, Tables, Maps and Diagrams.....	129
Bibliography.....	131
Table of Contents.....	141

Introduction

In Kampung Peta, a Jakun village of northern Johor, almost everyone dreams of tourism, whether it is imaginable or not to access the jobs it offers. Villagers judge by this measure every other opportunity within their reach. I asked myself what were the motivations of their choices, the constraints on them and the activities that they must accept for lack of better ones, their aspirations if they were allowed to dream. What do the inhabitants of the village live on and would like to live on?

An initial survey, carried out with the help of my informant and hostess, of each of the houses and the activities carried out there by the members of the hostel allowed me to have an idea of the proportion of each activity in the village: collection of forest products, agriculture, tourism employment and other jobs. I was able to verify the accuracy of these informations in the interviews I conducted subsequently in about 15 households. We worked with my informant to meet people of all economic conditions and working in all sectors. I conducted these semi-directed interviews alone, more rarely with her, keeping in mind that her presence as much as my residence at her place could bring me a privileged contact with the villagers as well as enroll me in a fabric of complicated, even conflicting relationships (Beaud and Weber 1998).

As these incomes were unstable (Wollenberg and Ani 1998), my respondents referred to a baseline income, a sort of year-long average that they seemed to have in mind before my questions, or the income of the last few months. I accepted this imprecision, supplemented with a second part on expenditure and followed up with a final part devoted to choices, assessments, constraints and dreams. "And if you had a choice..." (*Kalau ada pilihan...*) was my most common introduction.

The following pages are based on this ethnographic survey. After a presentation of the overall situation of the Orang Asli in Malaysia, the village of Kampung Peta is described in its natural environment and social organization. I describe then their sources of income in four chapters by separating subsistence activities and commercial activities from the primary sector (collection of forest products and agriculture), self-employment and wage earning without tourism and then within tourism, to better measure the particularities of this sector and its links with

environmental protection. A final chapter is devoted to some of the effects of the development of the market economy, in particular the increased income inequalities between women and men and between households, as well as the decline in the "moral order" in which the Jakun economy has long been situated.

Chapter 1. Orang Asli in Malaysia

1.1. Orang Asli in Malaysia, a Complex of Peoples

The Federation of Malaysia is composed of eleven states in the peninsula and two others in Borneo, as well as three federal territories. In 2017, of the 28.74 million Malaysians, 23.2% are Chinese and 7.0% are Indian (Department of Statistics 2018b). The majority is 68.8% Bumiputra. This status confers a "special position of the Malays and natives of any of the States of Sabah and Sarawak¹," according to Article 153 of the Constitution (1957 Constitution, revised in 2007), which grants "preferential treatment to the Malays" (Lafaye de Micheaux 2012). This positive discrimination is sometimes extended, according to the institutions, to the Orang Asli, which represent approximately 178,000 people, or 0.76% of the peninsula's population (2010 figure, Endicott 2016: 2).

Indigenous peoples in Western Malaysia are traditionally divided into three main branches: Semang (or Negritos), Senoi and Proto-Malay (or Indigenous Malay). This classification, which is common today in academic literature as well as in administration and the general public, is based primarily on linguistic criteria: speakers of Austronesian languages on the one hand (or indigenous Malay: Jakun, Temuan, etc.) and on the other hand speakers of Austro-Asian languages: Semang and Senoi peoples.

The tripartite division of Orang Asli groups into Negritos (Spanish for "little blacks"), Senoi and Aboriginal Malays developed from early 20th century European racial concepts, with the Negritos (short, dark-skinned, curly-haired people) being seen as the most primitive race, the Senoi (taller, lighter-skinned, wavy-haired people) being more advanced and the Aboriginal Malays (tall, light-skinned, straight-haired people) being seen as almost the equals of the Muslim Malays. (Endicott 2016 : 5)

The first Malaysian states were led by *raja* then sultans, originating from the west of Borneo and the east of Sumatra (Andaya 2008, Milner 2008 and 2016) but the first settlements of the

1 "It shall be the responsibility of the Yang di-Pertuan Agong to safeguard the special position of the Malays and natives of any of the States of Sabah and Sarawak."

peninsula are the ancestors of the Orang Asli (between -50,000 for populations close to the Semangs and -2,500 for those close to the indigenous Malays). People of the forest or sea, on the margins of these states, they were more or less dependent partners. The word Sakai, commonly used in colonial times to name the indigenous peoples of the peninsula but now perceived as very disparaging, even insulting, may have meant "dependent", "slave" (Manickam 2015: 49-52).

The Orang Asli groups kept to themselves until about the first millenium A.D. when traders from India, China and the Mon civilizations sought forest products such as resins, incense woods, rhinoceros horns, feathers, and even gold. Orang Asli living in the interior became suppliers of these items, bartering them for salt, cloth and iron tools. (Nicholas 2000 : 11)

They supplied forest products traded by coastal merchants (Andaya 2008), served in the military service of the sultans (Harper 1997: 3) or made "symbiotic" arrangements (Endicott 1984: 30) with peasant populations.²

Typically, a group of Semang would camp near a Malay village et the time of the rice harvest and would help with reaping and storing the grain in return for food, tobacco, cloth, etc. (Endicott 1984 : 30)

The Orang Asli would recognize the authority of states but remained "outside the orbit of kingdoms" (Endicott and Dentan 2004:26) and resisted assimilation. Over the centuries, the conversion of the Malays to Islam, the lower value of forest products on the world market and the increased pressure on the forest (agricultural pioneer fronts, forestry and plantation agriculture) degraded the social position of the peninsula's indigenous people, pushing them inland, in mountainous areas, and making their living conditions more precarious.

2 Here I use the notion of "peasant" in contrast to "tribal", as proposed by G. Benjamin, which characterizes peasant populations by their allegiance to the State and the payment of taxes in exchange for the prestige that a common cultural identity brings with the leaders. "Peasants' lives were controlled by agencies of the state, which they provisioned (often under force) in exchange for a little reflected cultural and religious glory but no counter-control, while continuing to support themselves through their own family-based subsistence activities." Benjamin 2015 : 2, note 6.

1.2. Political and Economic Situation of the Orang Asli

Today the Orang Asli present the most worrying human development indicators of the country with the indigenous people of the states of Sarawak and Sabah: "The minority Orang Asli still are far behind other Malaysians in major measures of health status, including life expectancy, childhood nutrition, and other indicators of well-being" (Baer 2010 : 4). In 2009, 50.0% of Orang Asli were considered poor, compared to 22.8% for East Malaysians and 3.8% for the general population (UPR 2010:185) and 19% were very poor (hardcore poverty) compared to 0.7% for the general population (Nicolas *et al.* 2010: 45). 30% have secondary education, compared with 72% of Malaysians (Ministry of Education 2013: 4-21, in UNDP 2013: 149). Their life expectancy is 52 years for women, 54 years for men, compared with 68 years for other women in the country and 72 years for men (Nicholas 2000: 28). The poorer performance of women is explained by more acute or specific health problems for women: malnutrition and death in childbirth, among others (Baer 2006: 109-110).

	Poverty	Hardcore Poverty	Secondary Education	Women Life Expectancy	Men Life Expectancy
Orang Asli	50,0 %	19 %	30 %	52 years	54 years
General Population	3,8 %	0,7 %	72 %	68 years	72 years

Table 1. Comparison of the main human development indicators between Orang Asli and the general Malaysian population.
Sources : EPU 2010, Ministry of Education 2013, Nicholas 2000.

The existence of the Orang Asli challenges the narrative of the Malaysian political majority. According to Mahathir Mohamad, prime minister of Malaysia from 1981 to 2003 and since 2018:

The Orang Melayu or Malays have always been the definitive people of the Malay Peninsula. (...) There was no known aborigine government or aborigine state. Above all, at no time did they outnumber the Malays. (Mahathir 1970, *in* Benjamin 2015 : 4, note 12)

Tunku Abdul Rahman, prime minister from 1957 to 1970, uses the same argument: "There could be no doubt that the Malays were the indigenous people of this country because the original

inhabitants did not have any form of civilization compared with the Malays" (Abdul 1989, in Benjamin 2015: 4, note 12). If the Malays have the right to govern the country they claim to own, the Orang Asli have an embarrassing prerogative over them, resolved by their differentiated treatment.

The Department of Aborigines, established in 1950 during the colonial era, and the Aboriginal Peoples Act of 1954 laid the groundwork for this treatment. Like McClelland, a resident of Pahang in 1922 who compares "wild beasts and Sakai" (Guérin 2017b: 58), Theodore Hubback, founding figure of environmentalism in the peninsula, speaks in favour of the right to the Orang Asli forest on the grounds that it is "a most important sanctuary for all sorts of wildlife, including Sakai" (Guérin 2017b: 58). Colonial authorities gave themselves a mission to protect and administer indigenous peoples. The British resident of Selangor stated in 1895 that "they must be provisionally treated as children and protected accordingly, until they are capable of taking care of themselves" (Selangor 1895, in Harper 1997: 8). The communist insurrection in 1948 and the ensuing guerrilla warfare until 1960 justified in the eyes of the British a rigorous administration of the indigenous peoples who were forcibly settled and grouped in camps and villages (Endicott and Dentan 2004: 28). Because the communists tried to rally them to their cause or forced them to provide logistical support, the colonial authorities sought to remove the Orang Asli from the guerrilla-controlled areas. T. N. Harper describes this era, because it gives rise to relocation and strong control over non-Member populations, such as "the making of modern Malaya" (Harper 1997: 17).

The Aboriginal Peoples Act of 1954 set out to "provide for the protection, well-being and advancement of the aboriginal peoples of Peninsular Malaysia" (Aboriginal Peoples Act 2006: prologue). The administration then promised to gazette and protect the traditional territories of the peoples in question (Aboriginal Peoples Act 2006: 6-1). On 22 May 1954, for example, three years before independence, the Assistant Protector of Aborigines of Mersing (Johor), a local representative of this administration, concerned about the Chinese forestry industry, recommended the classification as an Aboriginal reserve of three miles of land around the Endau river (Assistant Protector of the Aborigines 1954, in Nicholas 2013: CN167).

This general good will is shared by the United Malays National Organisation (UMNO), the party to which the British ceded the country's government in 1957. In 1948, his secretary general expressed concern that "the present system of earmarking certain areas as Sakai Reserves

without survey and publication in the Gazette as intended by law did not give the 'Sakai' population sufficient security" (UMNO 1948, in Nicholas 2013: CN191).

This project is not much further advanced when, the country being independent, the Department of Aborigines is replaced by a new dedicated department, the Jabatan Hal Ehwal Orang Asli (JHEOA, since 2011 Jabatan Kemajuan Orang Asli, JAKOA). This new administration, whose director prided himself on "taki[ng] care of [the Orang Asli] from the womb to the grave" (Jimin bin Idris, in Endicott and Dentan 2004:35), "has over the years developed a paternalistic relationship to the community" (Rusaslina 2010:95).

The Aboriginal Peoples Act allows the department to expel foreign persons from villages, remove village leaders (*batin*) from their duties, censor publications introduced into administered villages, or prohibit the sale or donation of alcoholic beverages. The JHEOA devotes a significant part of its efforts to the accession of the Orang Asli to "development."

Since 1961 Malaysian officials have expressed a desire to "integrate" Orang Asli into the Malaysian "mainstream." This has come to mean bringing them into the market economy, asserting political control over them, and assimilating them into the Malay ethnic category. (Endicott et Dentan 2004 : 24)

This economic assimilation and its relation with religious conversion have been well documented. States' very slow gazetting of traditional lands on the Aboriginal reserves and areas register leaves many communities vulnerable to alienation of their lands by non-indigenous people despite the provisions of the Aboriginal Peoples Act. In 2010, according to the Malaysian Human Rights Commission (Suhakam), the JHEOA estimated that 14% of the area of indigenous lands actually registered and 59% of the area of indigenous lands currently registered (Suhakam 2013: 62).

As, according to Kirk Endicott and other authors, "the biggest problem facing the Orang Asli today is their lack of land rights" (Endicott 2016: 24), their current claims focus primarily on land and have been supported by roadblocks since 2011 (Sheema *et al.* 2013: 648) as well as by lawsuits brought in states since 1996: "The move to the courts is a fairly recent one for the Orang Asli" (Rusaslina 2010: 89). Considered as "tenants-at-will" (Rusaslina 2010) of their lands, "historically marginalized and repeatedly ignored in their demands for rights, the Orang Asli

described their move to the courts as a last-resort attempt to have their voices heard" (Rusaslina 2010: 90). These trials are tried at the state level and then at the federal level and their outcome depends on the good will of the parties, including judges, since the indigenous peoples in Western Malaysia are relegated in "an historical and legal limbo, especially with regard to land-rights" (Benjamin 2015: 9). Unlike eastern Malaysia, where native customary rights established in colonial times are recognized by the Malaysian state, at least in principle if not in practice, rights to the land of the Orang Asli are not recognized by any legislation – which does not prevent them from benefiting from a more favourable jurisprudence overall than the concessions made to them by the States.

1.3. Jakun in the Orang Asli Complex of Peoples

The usual classification of the Orang Asli into three groups is based, as we have seen, on linguistic and "racial" criteria. Geoffrey Benjamin prefers the criteria of lifestyle and social organization to differentiate three groups: Semang egalitarian hunters-gatherers, Senoi slash-and-burn cultivators and collectors of forest products, also egalitarian. In contrast to them, people who follow a "malayic pattern" are culturally closer to the Malay, Islam aside. They practice the collection of forest products but, more involved in trade with the Malays, they have certain characteristics in common with them: their societies are hierarchical, more densely populated than those of the Senoi, with a preference for marriages in the family circle (Benjamin 2002: 10-11). These Malayic-type societies are mostly Austronesian languages but some are Austro-Asian languages, such as the Semelai, and are found in the south, less mountainous, of the peninsula (Gianno and Bayr 2009: 157-158). Within Malayic-type societies, the Jakun are a large group of about 30,000 people (2010 figures, Endicott 2016) who speak an Austronesian language close to Malay. They live in northern Johor and southern Pahang.

The Endau basin, in the north-east of Johor State, is populated by Jakun villages. Explorers who followed one another on the river in the second part of the 19th century named the non-Malay inhabitants of the river in various ways. Logan in 1847 named them Binua or Orang Binua: "This people occupy all the interior of Johore (...). The most definite description of their territory however is, that they occupy the upper branches of the last or more southern systems of river in the Malay Peninsula, that is the rivers of Johore (...) and Indáu" (Logan 1847: 246). For Lake and Kelsall, "the inhabitants of Endau are 'Jakuns', or 'Orang Hulu', as they prefer to be called" (Lake and Kelsall 1894:13). Hervey (1881) names them "Jakuns", as do P. É. L. Favre (1865) as

well as Skeat and Bladen (1906). In the 1960s, Maeda Tachimoto Narifumi called them "Orang Hulu" in his study of the Endau basin:

The term Jakun has a pejorative connotation, like the term Sakai. The people I studied recognize Jakun as designating a certain other group. But, since we do not have a definite term to designate those numerous, small, non-Muslim aboriginal populations in southern Malaya, the term Jakun is applied as a general name for them, because it circulates widely among ethnologists. The people along the Endau River call themselves Orang Hulu, which means literally the people of the upper streams. (Maeda 2001 : 10)

The word "jakun" is offensive in Malay, it applies to a foolish or innocent person. It is no longer in all dictionaries even though everyone understands the expression "jangan jakun" (don't be silly). According to G. Benjamin,

"Jakun" is a term that seems to be shifting in its political correctness. I avoided the word for many years, using "Orang Hulu" instead (...). But I have been told that Jakuns themselves (all of them?) are happy to be called "Jakuns", and I have accordingly reverted to this older established usage. (Benjamin 2002 : 60, note 9)

In Kampung Peta, the word "Jakun" is accepted when it comes to the people, even if its other meaning is considered insulting. It is preferred to "Orang Hulu", which seemed to me to be falling into disuse, but it is eclipsed by the expression "Orang Asli" and the adjective "Asli", to which the people of the village more readily identify themselves and which accounts for a community of destiny with the other tribal peoples of the peninsula. I have often heard the term "bahasa Asli" used to refer to Jakun words, even though language is what divides the Orang Asli the most. The term Orang Asal, which concerned only the natives of Sarawak and Sabah, is also increasingly used on the peninsula. Jaringan Orang Asal Semalaysia (JOAS) brings together indigenous people from both parts of Malaysia under one umbrella and one term.

While many Orang Asli communities live in natural environments that have been severely disrupted, those in Kampung Peta enjoy habitat in the heart of a protected forest. We must now understand what this natural environment is and how the village is equipped.

Chapter 2. Kampung Peta

2.1. Situation and History

Maeda Tachimoto Narifumi mapped the Jakun establishments on the Endau River in the Mersing District, Johor state, in the southern part of the peninsula in the 1960s (see Map 2). Kampung Peta is then the seventh and last village above the river (see map 3). The villages had been settled since "five to ten years"³ (Maeda 2001: 17) and were in the process of being settled. Some have not moved since then (see map 4): Kampung Labong, Denai, Kampung Mentelong, Kampung Tanjung Tuan are still in the same place. Kampung Tanah Abang, a settlement that had not been registered by Maeda, seems to have welcomed the inhabitants of Kampung Jorak, a missing hamlet. Kampung Punan moved slightly away from the Endau.

Kampung Peta moved to the other side of the river, on the right bank where it is currently located. On this bank, where the ground is quite flat, were the cultivated land. The villagers thus brought their houses closer to their gardens (*kebun*). This settlement of Kampung Peta, documented by Maeda, was quite recent in the 1960s and the inhabitants of the village spontaneously trace the history of the village to the regrouping of the scattered habitats of Ulu Endau in Ewah, twenty minutes by boat upstream, during the Emergency.

During their counter-insurgency war against the Malayan Communist Party (MCA), the British authorities gathered the Orang Asli living in the forest throughout the peninsula in dedicated villages, afraid they might collaborate with the MCA (Harper 2001). When Aboriginal people did not join the MCA, it forced them, as it did with the Jakun, to labour or threatened their lives if they did not provide logistical support (Harper 1997: 21). Still today, the villagers remember the vice in which they or their ancestors were caught during the guerrilla war, between colonial authorities and MCA (informal interview with Syamsul and Saifuddin).

Between their gathering in Ewah and the settlement in Kampung Peta at the end of the Emergency, the Jakun still had other places of residence.

During the Emergency (ca. 1954), the Jakuns were first resettled by the British at Ewah (Iwah), a short distance upriver from the present park headquarters. When the insurgency intensified, the Jakun were again forcibly resettled further downriver at

3 "The hamlets I studied had the same locations for five up to ten years."

Tanjung Pelandok (and later, after Merdeka in 1957, at Dusun Tinggi), both close to the present Kampung Tanah Abang. And when the Emergency was declared over, the Jakun of the Endau River opted to return to their traditional territories or to settle in more suitable locations. These were at Mentolong, Jorak/Tanah Abang, Punan and Peta. The people of these settlements nevertheless remain interrelated through kinship ties. (Nicholas 2013 : R6-R7)

It is possible to go back further in time to find trace of the Jakun of the Endau around the river Semberong or Semerung, a tributary of the river Endau which has the particularity of having two branches, one which flows into the Endau (then into the China Sea) and the other in the Strait of Malacca.

Most of the Jakun living in these three settlements [Pengkalan Tereh, Kampung Peta and Kampung Punan] were formerly from Sungai Semerung near Kluang in Johor. Present day Pengkalan Tereh is located near Sungai Semerung. In the late nineteenth century, the Jakun living at Sungai Semerung had to leave because the then Sultan of Johor prohibited the hunting of rhinoceros which was a major source of income for the Jakun. Some of them continued with such hunting even after the prohibition was ordered. Angered, the Sultan sent Kapitan Mat (...) to punish those involved; some were even imprisoned. As a result of this prohibition, the Jakun of Semerung left and moved to Pahang. While in Pahang, they lived at Kengalung, and during the Emergency period, they moved to Sungai Rompin. From Rompin, they moved to Sekin, and from there to Labi-Labi and later to Sungai Kencim. During the critical period of the Emergency, all the Jakun communities living in Johor and Pahang were gathered at and were grouped by the British who built an airstrip there with the help of the Jakun. The group of Ewah broke up and formed several different settlements. (...) Another group eventually settled at Peta. (Thambiah 1999 : 269-270)

The conflict between the Jakun and the sultan of Johor over the poaching of rhinoceros horns, if it is the one reported by Favre (Favre 1865: 44-46), dates from 1847.

2.2. Description of the village

2.2.1. Access

Kampung Peta is the most upstream village of the Endau River. It takes its source at Gunung Besar (1036m) and flows into the South China Sea at Endau, in the district of Mersing. At one day by motor boat from the mouth, as described by Maeda, Kampung Peta is now more commonly reached by road. On Route 50 between the Kluang and Mersing district capitals, a few kilometers east of the small town of Kahang, a dirt track leads to several oil palm plantations. After one hour of trail in the middle of the plantations, a paved road leads to Kampung Peta and Endau-Rompin National Park (see map 5). To the right of the fork, the village. To the left is the National Park and a paved road that stops only at Kuala Jasin, six kilometers away. There are the last of the park's built infrastructures.

Kampung Peta is located 50 kilometers from Kahang, almost an hour and a half drive, in a loop of the Endau, on a low plateau that is regularly flooded during the rainy season. Kampung Orang Asli Peta is an indigenous village under the responsibility of Jabatan Kemajuan Orang Asli (JAKOA). Its land was listed in 1989 as an Aboriginal reserve, comprising 221 hectares, not counting about 40 hectares, which are now planted with rubber trees and located within the park (Nicholas 1999) (see maps 7 and 8).

2.2.2. Natural Environment

The village is on the right bank of the Endau River, between the Peta Mountains (552m) and Janing Mountains (655m), about 20m above sea level⁴ (see map 6). A rainforest of *Diptrocarpaceae* (Maeda 2001: 13) covers these relatively low mountains compared to those of the Main Range, further north in the peninsula. The banks of the river are sometimes covered with lower vegetation but they are not swampy, as is the case further downstream where Maeda noted the presence of alluvial forests. The forest around the village is protected by three statuses: indigenous reserve, subject to village governance, national park (Taman Negara, managed by the national parks of the state of Johor) and the forest reserve (*rizab hutan*, managed by the forest administration, Jabatan Perhutanan Semenanjung Malaysia). Following a clear cut of 140 hectares in 1997 (Nicolas 1999: 9), the forest within the Aboriginal reserve was regenerated into a secondary forest (*belukar*). The park and forest reserve forest is preserved, but according to the

4 <http://elevation.maplogs.com/>, website consulted on 8 July 2019.

Global Forest Change project⁵, the last major cuts in Endau-Rompin National Park took place three kilometres north of Bukit Peta, in another watershed in Pahang State (see map 9) in 2017 and 2018, leaving villagers doubtful about the ability of the authorities to prevent deforestation. Large-scale poaching by groups of armed men was also reported in the park and reserve (interviews with Kamaruddin, Saiful and Syazwan).

The climate in Endau-Rompin is tropical and Kampung Peta receives 2800mm of annual rainfall for an average temperature of 26.5°C over the year and a high humidity rate. During the rainy season, from November to January, temperatures drop by one or two degrees and precipitation is twice as intense (see figures 1 and 2). In this season, more often called *musim banjir* (flood season) than *musim hujan* (rainy season), the way out of the village is more frequently cut.

The land claimed by the inhabitants of Kampung Peta in the name of customary land rights lies between the two ridge lines, along the river, between Kuala Lemakoh (Nicholas 1999: 2, Kuala Lemakoh in Maeda 2001) downstream and Kuala Kinchin upstream – the latter border being more vague as there is no other village upstream of Kampung Peta. The plateau where the village itself is located is relatively flat. A few much lower lands along the river are not cultivated and there are bushes and shrubs. Almost all the lands which are located south of road following the massif of Bukit Janing are very steep and are not cultivated, except around the houses.

2.2.3. Houses and Settlements

The first twenty houses of the village are located along the road before the village entrance. After the village entrance sign are about fifty houses along a road that makes a loop. Some houses in the village are made of bricks, with an English toilet in the house. Their construction was subsidized by the Jabatan Kemajuan Islam (interview with Rabiah). The others are equipped with squatting toilets in a hut outside, as well as a shower room under a shelter attached to the house (see an example figure 3). Most have a mixed one-storey structure: floor and lower walls in concrete, top wall made of planks, zinc roof, between three and five separate rooms, sometimes an extension of wood on stilts, on a total surface of 50 m² or more. Bricks, beams, boards and other materials are often purchased in Kahang (interviews with Iman and Asma). There are still traditional houses, all wood on stilts, using wood bark for walls rather than boards. They are still being built, with wood cut and processed on site (interview with Kamaruddin), and

5 Webpage <http://earthenginepartners.appspot.com/science-2013-global-forest> from HANSEN *et al.* 2013.

the *rumah adat* itself (a house built at the end of 2018 for a collective use) sacrificed to the tradition only the use of nails. The oldest wooden houses in the village are abandoned.

Most of the village is in a loop whose southern and eastern areas are planted with rubber and less populated than the northern and western areas, where are located the communal facilities, *balai budaya* (a covered place with concrete floor where the villagers can have activities together) and *rumah adat*. Most of the cultivated land lies outside the village, between the Endau River and the road along the Janing Massif, as well as in the southern and eastern parts of the village. The land beyond the reserve belongs to the park on the south side above the river, and to a forest reserve downstream on the left bank. Villagers are not allowed to clear the forest in order to open up farmland.

Some villagers have two houses, one in the village and the other outside, closer to the farmland, but this situation does not concern more than four households. Maeda noted in the 1960s:

When asked where he had lived, an Orang Hulu might give the names of as many as 12 localities or hamlets. This seems to be the result of individual mobility and frequent shifting of hamlet sites, a practice that is very easy on account of the simplicity of the house structure and the poverty of utensils and personal possessions. As well, houses are frequently shifted so that work in the forest is more conveniently at hand. The hamlets I studied had the same locations for five up to ten years. (Maeda 2001 : 17)

The policy of settling semi-nomads, the disappearance of itinerant cultures and the change in the structure of houses and possessions contributed to the establishment of permanent villages.

2.3. Equipment

2.3.1. Water and Electricity

Access to running water is provided by a distribution system managed by the village, the responsibility of which lies in the hands of a man of about fifty years, younger brother of the village chief (*batin*) Rampuyan Kantan. Water is captured on Janing Mountain and distributed through a system of plastic pipes. It is not drinkable but of good quality and only once during my

stay the heavy rain made it slightly opaque. Wastewater is released into the environment, with the exception of those of the toilets that are treated individually in septic tanks. This equipment of the village houses was realized in 2016 with the support of the company Petronas, the national oil company (informal interview with Syamsul).

Most of the houses in the village are connected to the electricity grid by the national company Tenaga Nasional. Some of the houses were not in 2019. Some are connected to neighbours' homes and informally share invoices. Others are too far from the nearest homes to be able to cover the cost of the equipment, whether it is taken care of by the household or by the company, which would charge 500 RM per pole (informal interview with Balqis, whose house is not connected to the network). Of the 20 or so homes I was allowed in or visited, three did not have access to electricity. The kitchen is made with gas and the light in the evening is provided by candles or lamps that are loaded during the day in the homes of family members. Public lighting is provided by solar lamps in good condition. Power outages during my stay were rare and short (less than two hours), with the exception of a 24-hour power outage. The infrastructures of the national park and the school are equipped with a generator for their own needs.

The waste is not collected in Kampung Peta and the villagers throw it around their houses (especially the organic waste to hens or dogs) and then burn it with the dead leaves.

2.3.2. Public Services

Photo 1. *Surau*. Photo 2. *Pusat Rawatan Kesihatan*. Photos A. Vidal, March-April 2019.

Photo 3. SK, *Sekolah Kebangsaan* Kampung Peta. Photo A. Vidal, March-April 2019.

The state services in Kampung Peta are a police station, a prayer hall (*surau*, see photo 1), a health center (*pusat rawatan kesihatan*, see photo 2) opened one evening a month by the Ministry of Health, a nursery school (*tadika*), a primary school SK (*sekolah kebangsaan*, see photo 3). The next school cycle (*sekolah menengah*) is provided outside the village and adolescents between 12 and 17 years are schooled a few kilometers from Mersing in the Sekolah Menengah Kebangsaan Nitar in full board (*asrama penuh*). School children return to the village every other weekend, at the expense of their parents who organize the carpool. Adults are also concerned by the educational offer since at the SK courses for adults (*kelas dewasa*) are offered three times a week: Malay on Mondays, English on Tuesdays and mathematics on Wednesdays. These classes take place in the afternoon, when the children have left school, and are attended almost exclusively by women.

2.3.3. Means of Communication and Transportation

I did not see any wireline phones during my stay. In 1999, Colin Nicholas reported a network in poor condition, listing Kampung Peta's public services as "public telephone (albeit it has not been in working condition for some time)" (Nicholas 1999: 2). Some inhabitants of the village are equipped with mobile phones and connected to the Internet via 3G, which it is possible to catch in one place in the village, between the river and the *rumah adat*. People who own smart phones are mostly men between the ages of 20 and 40. Older people, for some, have more basic telephones that do not allow them to access the Internet. It is possible to receive the GSM network for calls or text messages but only in the centre of the village.

There is no public transport that would connect Kampung Peta to the first *pekan*, the town of Kahang. It is possible to make the journey by scooter, faster than the car but rather painful and

this mode of transport is reserved for journeys to oil palm plantations by the people who are employed there. To go to Kahang – and further to Kluang or Mersing where it is possible to take a bus to Kuala Lumpur or Singapore – the villagers use private cars.

There are 24 cars for about 70 houses in the village and many people do not have a driver's license. While employees of institutions (national park, police, etc.) and tourist transport companies travel exclusively in four-wheel drive vehicles, better equipped for the track, the majority of villagers own two-wheel drive cars. These cars are less comfortable than the 4x4 and are more difficult to use during the rainy season, which condemns many inhabitants to stay in the village. All the villagers travel by scooter in the surroundings, less willingly on foot and never by car. Cars are sometimes owned in *kongsi* (mutual structure), members of the same family sharing a vehicle. "If there is no kongsi, there is no car,"⁶ says Syazrina (informal interview) about the vehicle she shares with her children. Even if the association is not formal, it is still possible to *tumpang*, to be taken here or there by sharing the costs (a round trip to Kahang is estimated at RM 50, a round trip to Kluang or Mersing at RM 100). Access to transport is much more expensive in Kampung Peta than elsewhere: from Kluang it is possible to buy RM 25 a ticket to Kuala Lumpur (300km) or RM 8 a ticket to Mersing (100km).

6 "Jika tak ada kongsi, tak ada kereta."

Chapter 3. Rituals and Society

Jakun way of life and social organization were documented by travelers and then scientists who have roamed the north of the sultanate of Johor, sometimes the south of Pahang where also live Jakun: J. R. Logan (1847), P. É. L. Favre (1865), D. F. A Hervey (1879 and 1881), H. W. Lake and H. J. Kelsall (1894), W. W. Skeat and C. O. Blagden (1906) and I. H. N. Evans (1923). The next study has been conducted by Maeda N. around 1965 throughout the Endau basin. The last texts, by Colin Nicholas and Shanthi Thambiah, date from 1999. They allow us to understand how the great stages of an individual's life (birth, marriage and death) as well as the social life, centered on village and the person of the *batin*, or customary chief, are organized.

3.1. Rites of Passage

3.1.1. Being Born and Being Named

The myth of childbirth in the Jakun family depicts spouses in solidarity in the course of pregnancy and deliverance.

The child was first conceived and carried by the man in his calf, and after nine months, and incision had to be made on the calf to bring the baby out. The women felt sorry for the man and took it upon herself to relieve the man from his great pain. The capability to give birth was mystically transferred to the woman. Then, the men felt sorry for the women for they had to cut into the womb to take the baby out, and many women died in the process.

One day, a man who was worried for his wife's safety went wandering into the forest thinking of the pain his wife would endure if he had to bring the baby out of her womb by cutting open her womb. On his way back, he saw a monkey give birth, and also watched how another monkey helped out in the birthing. When the time came for his wife to give birth, his family brought a machete to cut her up. He stopped them and taught his wife to push the baby out. He was the first man to be a *bidan* (mid-wife) for the Jakun. Until today the Jakun believe that men will conceive the

child and hold it in them for 9 days before it is mystically transferred to their wives. They will feel weak, sick and have cravings for the first 9 days before their wives go through the same feelings for the next 9 months. (Thambiah 1999 : 273)

According to Logan, it is the mother of the woman in childbirth who serves as a *bidan* but her husband can possibly replace her. There is no specialized midwife but we can note the intervention of the *pawang* (village magician), according to Maeda.

The wife's mother generally act as midwife, but when absent the husband himself supplies her place. (...) In the third month of pregnancy the Poyáng visits the mother, performs some ceremonies and binds a charm round her waist in order that all may go well with her and the child. On the birth of the first child a feast is generally given by the Binúas. (...) Names are sometimes given at birth, but these are changed at the age of puberty. (Logan 1847 : 90-91)

In his 1865 work, Favre describes another ritual of birth of the Jakun, but according to him the women in childbirth receive no help from their entourage.

No assistance is ordinarily given to lying-in women; their physicians or Pawangs are not permitted to appear in such circumstances, and midwives are not known amongst them. It is reported that, in several tribes, the children as soon as born, are carried to the nearest rivulet, are washed, then brought back to the house where a fire is kindled, incense of kamunian wood thrown upon it and the children then passed over it several times. (...) A few days after the birth of the child, the father gives him a name, which is ordinarily the name of some tree, fruit or colour. (Favre 1865, 68-69)

There have been specialized *bidan* in the village (interview with Ahmad and Zarina) and Maeda clarifies how they were paid (Maeda 2001: 55) but since the authorities started taking medical care of childbirth (Gianno 2006: 101) there doesn't seem to be any. The medical centres where births take place are very far from the villages, which no longer allows the family to accompany

the woman in childbirth.

The birth names, whether given by the father or by the couple of parents, are almost always replaced by names of use (*nama timangan*) that reflect a particular characteristic of the person in a way that is often a bit mocking. The term *timangan*, which refers to the act of rocking or jumping on one's knees, suggests that the name is given during childhood and not adolescence. After the birth of their first child, the Jakun are called more commonly with a teknonym: they then take the name of "mother or father of their elder" ("Pak" or "Mak", and if the elder dies, they change the teknonym to the name of the next child) and later the name of "grandmother or grandfather of their eldest grandchild" ("Nenek"). Officially, the villagers bear their name of birth and that of their father, preceded by *binti* or *bin* as Malays do, more rarely AP or AL (*anak perempuan, anak laki-laki*).

3.1.2. Marriage and Matrimonial Strategies

Logan describes a Jakun wedding. It is a ceremony between two families, without the presence of a ritual specialist.

According to the Binúas the union is arranged by the parents, and the ceremony consists simply in the parties eating from the same plate. After partaking of a repast the relatives of the bridegroom depart, leaving him to pass the night in the bride's house. Next day he carries her home. A small present is sent to the bride's parents previous to the marriage. (...) Most of the Binúas have one wife, but some have two and there does not appear to be any rule on the subject. (Logan 1847 : 270)

The present offered by the fiancé to his future in-laws is described more precisely by Favre, while Skeat and Bladen (1906: 519) indicate how he is rendered in the event of divorce. This gift is valuable.

The dowry given by the man to his intended is delivered, and must consist at least of a silver or copper ring; if the man is not poor, a pair of bracelets. Some other ornaments, and several articles, as of furniture for the house of the new family, are added. Sometimes the woman presents also some gifts to her intended. (Favre 1865 : 65-66)

More than a century after Logan, Maeda describes a ceremony that tends more towards the Malay model and involves the village institutions as well as the neighbours.

Primary prestation in marriage is the *mas kawin*, which is decided by the *batin*. Contingent prestation depends upon the negotiation at the wedding ceremony. This ceremony consists of four parties. The first is a series of rituals, such as bathing, a procession, a reception, the *bersanding*, eating saffron rice, chewing betel and tobacco, and sitting on a pillow. The second part is the feast of the invited guests. During the ceremony there are recreations such as playing cards and other games. The fourth part is a meeting called *berhadat*. The day after the feast, the relatives of both parties gather together and receive salutations from the newlyweds. Usually the wedding ceremony is held at the bride's house. (Maeda 2001 : 72)

The newlyweds then stay ideally one year with the wife's parents, says Maeda. Thambiah also notes a temporary *uxorilocality* (Thambiah 1999: 271). The departure to a self-contained house (*neolocality*) depends on the material possibilities of the couple. The village in which they settle is their choice and depends on personal tastes as well as on economic opportunities.

Photo 4. Wedding of Adam and Farah, 25 March 2019. Photo A. Vidal.

The wedding in March 2019 of Adam and a young Temiar woman, Farah, resulted in a comparison of the rites of the two groups. "In my culture we just meet our parents, have some

discussions and get married. We did it there [in the north of Perak], now it's their culture, it's a bigger thing, it looks more like Malay" (interview with Farah, who is a teacher of English). Like the Malay wedding that influenced it, the Jakun wedding is organized around the reception of guests to whom is presented the married couple. The whole family does not dress up but some women took the opportunity to dress elegantly and some girls and women to put on makeup in collective sessions. Adam's mother and aunt (the latter perhaps replacing Farah's mother, who came with three friends of her age but without family) put on nice dresses, they animate a ceremony during which the groom makes the bride smoke and vice versa, then makes him chew a nut of areca and vice versa, eat some rice and vice versa, eat a piece of chicken and vice versa (all products mentioned by Maeda with the exception of chicken). Once this ritual is performed in front of a large audience, the couple is surrounded by family and friends and subject to photography sessions (see photo 4 previous page).

Guests take advantage of the renting of a sound system to sing Indonesian karaoke songs, while others gamble with cards or chat in the house. The reception (*kenduri* in Malay) is prepared the previous day during a *gotong-royong* (helping each other between neighbours) that resembles the preparations for the Malay wedding in the 1990s described by Thompson: "A group of women cooked curries and other dishes to feed the dozens of relatives and neighbors in attendance for the preparations, which felt itself like a small *kenduri*" (Thompson 2012: 108). On that day, the carers are a little less numerous than the guests will be the next day, the industrious atmosphere is very friendly and the food plentiful. The food expenses of Adam's parents for the entire marriage are approximately RM 1,000, plus transportation and equipment rental.

If the Malay tradition has, as we have seen, "a preference for consanguineal (cousin) marriage" (Benjamin 2002: 11), the village nevertheless constitutes too close a family. Since young people have few opportunities to get out of high school, how does one find a spouse in Kampung Peta? In an informal interview, Asma and Iman explained to me that the most common way to meet other young people of flirting or marrying age was through the online social network Facebook, which allows friends to be identified and a conversation to take place. Zubaidah, a woman almost 30 years old, met her husband on the Wechat messaging application. This pattern tends to replace the intermediary of relatives who present acquaintances or family in remote villages. Some couples come from close family, such as Syazrina and Zulkarnain who were first cousins, the family of the latter having established itself Kampung Peta when he was a child.

Others find a spouse further: Kamaruddin's wife, Hainil, comes from Tasik Cini, another large Jakun settlement area, southeast of Pahang (Crabtree-Parker *et al.* 2016). Kamaruddin is about 40 years old and his partner is ten years younger. With the growing success of Orang Asli and indigenous community organizations (Persatuan Orang Asli Semenanjung Malaysia, Jaringan Orang Asal Semalaysia) that bring together for cultural or political purposes people from across the peninsula, unions between partners from distant Orang Asli groups take place, such as Adam and Farah.

In Kampung Peta there are a number of mixed couples, in many of whom I know the wife is indigenous. Is this due to the uxorilocality or to a pattern of social hierarchies in which men from the least considered groups cannot claim to marry women from other groups? Normah, the sister of several of my respondents, is married to a Malaysian Indian and Zubaidah to a Malay of Javanese descent. Asma almost married a Malay but her father discouraged her, the conversion to Islam that this union implies being a major obstacle for the Jakun of Kampung Peta (informal interview with Asma). Kamal, a man of about 40 years, has left the village and the state, he is married in Perak with a Malay and he is the only man I know who is married to a non-Orang Asli person. Older unions, with Chinese workers, left mixed grandchildren, like Omar.

"Divorce and remarriage are simple processes and common practice" (Maeda 2001: 65). Fifty years after Maeda, I didn't meet many recomposed couples. Have the couples stabilized to the same extent as the villages? Of the 15 or so couples I interviewed, there is only one whom I know is recomposed: Kamaruddin is widowed and remarried. His first son lives with his elder sister Hatiqah.

3.1.3. Funeral Rituals

The dead are buried without ceremony, according to Logan, but in a tomb whose structure is particular.

On the day succeeding the death the body is wrapped in cloth and deposited in a grave dig near the hut, together with some of the clothing of the deceased, and his parang if he possesses one. No ceremony is observed. Above the grave a frame work of wood resembling a box without top or bottom is placed. This is filled with earth, a

piece of carved wood is stuck at each end, and frequently the whole is protected by a roof. (Logan 1847 : 271)

Photo 5. Tomb of Zulkarnain and rite by his widow Syazrina.
Photo A. Vidal, March-April 2019

Evans states that "the dead are buried lying face upwards, with their heads pointing to the west" (Evans 1923: 266). The tomb of Zulkarnain, an ancient *batin*, fits these descriptions (see photo 5 above). It is protected by a zinc roof and consists of a tiled concrete base with a rectangular wooden structure representing a house. At the head is a carved hornbill and at the foot is an anthropomorphic figure slightly scary of about 40cm who was described to me as the king of spirits or the overseas grave (see detail below in photo 5).

Miniature means of transportation (carved or purchased: plastic aircraft, carved wooden boat, etc.) are found near the head to help the dead person travel her way. The tomb of Zulkarnain is a bit peculiar since it is that of an ancient *batin* (it identifies not its dates of birth and death but of exercise) but the rites are the same for all. His grave was visited during my stay: his family went to visit him following a dream of Anwar who dreamed that his dead father, Zulkarnain, wanted to eat *kuih pisang*, a banana cake. This kind of dream is perceived as a request expressed by the dead and quickly granted. Death can appear in dreams to close family or to distant people. At the end of the day, at about 6:30 p.m., an hour considered auspicious, part of the deceased's family, his widow and two children, went to lay on the grave slices of cake as well as coffee served in a glass. Syazrina, the widow of Zulkarnain, burned fragrant wood and spent the offerings in smoke

while singing, in a very simple ceremony that lasted a little over ten minutes.

The Jakun bury their dead in scattered places and hold ceremonies up to a hundred days after the death (informal interview with Asma, Iman and Syazrina). The first ceremony takes place three days later and is called *peniga*, (from the word *tiga*: three) the second or *penujuh* takes place seven days later and the others respectively fourteen, forty and one hundred days later. Evans noted only three moments: "Feasts are held on the third, seventh, and hundredth days" (Evans 1923: 266). On the first day of mourning, no one works in the village, no one cuts trees or listens to music. The body is washed in water, rice powder (*beras*) and lime (*limau*). The shaman recites incantations in the presence of family and friends.

The body is buried with supplies to allow it to make the way that takes it away. If there is not enough food, the dead remains and demands, a frightening perspective for the Jakun even if the ghost is friendly.

3.1.4. Other Rituals

The Jakun are animists. Logan, who describes a people close to them (and whom he calls Bermun) as atheists, sees in their worship monotheistic traits.

[The Jakun] have a simple, and, to a certain extent, rational theology. They believe in the existence of one God, PIRMAN⁷, who made the world and every thing that is visible, and at whose will all things continue to have their being. Pirmán dwells above the sky, and is invisible. Intermediate between Pirmán and the human race are the Jín, – the most powerful of whom is the Jín Bumi or Earth Spirit, who is Pirmán minister. He dwells on the earth, feeding on the lives of men and all other things living. It is the Jín Bumi who sends all kinds of sickness and causes death; but his power is entirely derived from Pirmán. Each species of tree has a Jin. The rivers have a spiritual life, but it is that of the Jín Bumi, who haunts them with his power. The mountains are also animated by him. (...) There is no religious worship, but to avert death recourse is had in sickness to a Poyáng⁸, no other person being supposed to have the right of imploring mercy from Pirmán. (Logan 1847 : 275)

The *Pawang* has a special role. He "possesses a familiar which he may have either obtained by inheritance or which may have come to him in a dream" (Evans 1923:264). In the 1960s it is always the *batin* who stands as *pawang* although it is conceivable that the two functions are taken care of by different people with a preeminence in one area or the other: "The *pawang* is a mediator between this world and the supernatural one; in this world the *batin* is supreme" (Maeda 2001: 79).

Purification of the Orang Hulu hamlet (*bela kampong*⁹) (...) is held by the *batin* once a year to protect the hamlet from devils and keep the people in health and prosperity. The day, which is called *hari batin besar* (a *batin's* big day), must be celebrated with feasts provided by the *batin*. (...) All the members of the hamlet must return on this feast day from wherever they are working, so the *batin* and his *anak buah* can see the unity of the hamlet. Most of the expenses for the feast will be met by the *batin*, who also decided the proper date for it. (Maeda 2001 : 79-80)

7 From firman (loan from Arabic) : decree or divine command in Malay. Jin is also an Arabic word adopted by Malay, which means genius, good or bad spirit created by Allah. Both appointments are derived from Islam.

8 "The shaman is called *poyang* by many of the Sakai-Jakun tribesmen, especially by those whose mother-tongue is Malay. *Poyang* is probably a variant of *pawang*, the ordinary Malay term for the shaman" (Evans 1923 : 216).

9 From the verb *pelas*, *memelas*: purify the village and the territory. One can also envisage a semantic congruence with the verb *membela*, defend. It is a ritual commonly found in other peoples of the archipelago (Bernard Sellato, personal communication).

The *hari batin besar* has some similarities with the Bela Tanah described by Colin Nicholas more than thirty years later but the date seems to no longer depend on the *batin* and the ritual is conducted by a *pawang* (Atan Jala or Harun) who does not seem to be the *batin*.

The ritual of *Bela Tanah* or "appeasing the spirits of the land" (...) is done once a year, usually coinciding with the lunar new year (which incidentally usually coincides with the rice harvest when the Jakun still practiced swiddening). It is based on the belief that the land (especially that in the vicinity of the Jasin and the Marong) is inhabited by *orang bunyian* (people we cannot see) and that the Jakun need to respect their presence, and to express gratitude to them for what has been taken from the forest they watch over. For this reason, a goat is sacrificed and as a mark of respect to the spirits, and certain taboos are strictly followed during the 3-day ritual. The ritual is conducted at two places each year: Kampung Peta itself and Kuala Jasin. Kampung Peta, because it is the place where the Jakun presently reside; and Kuala Jasin because it is this where their *kampung asal* (original village) is. Kuala Jasin is also regarded as the abode of the ancestors, where all food has its origins. Nevertheless, Kuala Jasin is also considered a "*tempat keras*" ("hard" place). A place is given such status when one or more unnatural deaths occur there. The *bela tanah* ritual begins with one or both of the *pawang tanah* (land shamans), Atan Jala or Harun, calling upon the land spirits to accept their thanksgiving. A *kenduri* (feast) is held and for the next three days strict taboos (*pantang*) would be enforced: no cutting of wood, no working on the land, no making of any noise, no cutting of anything that has blood, and such. The *bela tanah* ritual is done to ensure the safety of all, not just the Jakun. (Nicholas 1999 : 4)

In the 1990s the park authorities pressured the Jakun to trivialize the Bela Tanah to reduce the impact on tourism activity. More prosaically than when the *pawang* alone could summon the spirits, these are today summoned to earn money in gambling. Iman prays to a divine being whom she asks for help to get her lottery number out (informal interview). This being is present everywhere, but she does not tell me any more than how she comes into contact with him: "We put something in the tree and we pray, we put something on the grave and we pray." Syamsul, a man of about 30 years who works in tourism, prays for his protection, the protection of those

around him and his environment: "Please protect my family, our life is more better, our community, protect our jungle." When he is still in the forest at the time when the cicadas signal the end of the day by their stridulation, he asks permission from Dato Moyang¹⁰. "I ask please protect my guests, my tourists, we just want to go camping, if bad things please keep away from us." The spirits likely to intercede for the Jakun are in the forest and especially on the river bank where two *keramat*¹¹ (sacred places) are listed: in Kuala Jasin where the Bela Tanah is held and in Pantai Burung, another important *keramat*, former burial place on the banks of the Endau and from where today the activities of tubing leave. "I pray from *semangat* Nenek Moyang, we call it *keramat*, like Pantai Burung, they send message to the god we believe is there." Places matter, but spirits can also be invoked elsewhere: "Have also in *kampung*, we pray in our hearts." Other rites, collective ones, concern the predation of natural resources: "Before we harvest the fish aruana, the shaman will go up river and have a special place in the landscape to pray there, for the community here, when we harvest the aruana fish¹² to ask the permission from the spirit of river" (interview with Syamsul).

The villagers told me more about "shaman" than about *pawang* or *bomoh*, so I was able to confuse the two functions. Or maybe there is no more *pawang* in Kampung Peta. The difference between the two is not of quality but of power, explains Maeda (2001: 79). The villagers use the *bomoh* to solve health problems. These are not psychological problems, which are treated by institutions outside the village (interview with Rabiah), nor acute physiological problems. It seems that the *bomoh* is being consulted for chronic conditions and that its most common prescription is the pork-free diet (prescribed to my knowledge to Syazrina, Hatiqah, a 60-year-old woman and her younger sister, and Qalesya, a woman of almost 40 years). There is at least one *bomoh* in the village but never one since it is an apprenticeship that requires a long transmission (interview with Ahmad and Zarina).

The Jakun of Kampung Peta still have practices of animism, perhaps less structured than before. They are less widely converted to Islam than elsewhere in the peninsula, which could be due to the strength of their collective structures (Colin Nicholas, personal communication). It should be noted that a Muslim cult is held in the village where the school's Malay teachers call to prayer (*azan*), five times a day from the *surau*. The people of Kampung Peta respect the *adat*, a set of norms that organizes rituals and regulates social life, even if it is challenged by the economic and

10 Dato Moyang may be the spirit of the ancestors, "semangat Nenek Moyang."

11 *Keramat* (malais, de l'arabe *karamat*) is a place charged with magical powers.

12 The aruana, a freshwater fish of the family *Osteoglossidae*, is sold as ornamental fish at very high prices.

social changes that are the subject of this study. The *adat* is taught within a family and then, possibly, in formal training in the village.

3.2. Social Organisation and Family

3.2.1. The *Batin* and the Village Committee

Societies based on the Malay model are on the whole more hierarchical than other Orang Asli societies, in particular Semang (Schebesta 1973, Endicott and Endicott 2012, Lye 2018), in which the *batin* can exercise no coercion. The Jakun accept the authority of a *batin*, whose prerogatives were before contemporary times more extensive.

Each *Bátin* has absolute authority with his own jurisdiction. (...) Offenses against property or person are, from the mildness of the people, of very rare occurrence. Crimes of all kinds may be expiated by the payment of fines, which are invariably imposed, not in coins, of which very few reach their hands, but in coarse Chinese plates or saucers (*pingan*) (*sic*). (...) One half of the fine goes to the *Bátin* and the other half to the injured person. If the offender fail (*sic*) to deliver the *pingan* he becomes a slave of the latter. Complaints are enquired into the *Bátin*, who assembles a number of the elders and consults with them. (...) No regular tax is paid to the *Bátin*. But presents are frequently made to them. (Logan 1847 : 274)

Logan and others report a complex hierarchy in which the *batin* is a title inserted in the Malay administrative or military hierarchy (*penghulu*, *panglima*).

Among the Jakun of the south we have, under the tribal Chief or *Batin*, a series of subordinate chiefs called respectively "Jinang," "Jukrah," "Penghulu," "Penglina" – a state of things which points to a comparatively great advance on the part of the race in the art of self-government. (Skeat et Bladen 1906 : 494)

Maeda in the 1960s notes no Jakun authority beyond the *batin* of each village – even though the villages in the Endau basin feel they belong to the same society and have between them exchanges and conflicts (Maeda 2001: 84).

The headman of a hamlet, the *batin*, has control only within his hamlet. His role as a leader is to settle disputes among the people of the hamlet, to set dates for important occasions there, and to officiate at these affairs. Also, he's expected to act as the hamlet's agent or representative to the outside world. (Maeda 2001 : 76)

The *batin* are chosen by the community but confirmed by the administration (Aboriginal Peoples Act 2006: 16-1), which may also remove them from office. In the Jakun people, they are all men. It is Rampuyan Kantan, a man over 60 years old, who performs the function of *batin* during my stay but his position has become precarious: he is deprived of the allowance he receives for this function because of his partisan involvement in the 2018 elections to the Pakatan Harapan coalition (informal talks with Rampuyan Kantan and Asma) but he is invited with all the country's *batin* to the Orang Asli Convention of 23 April 2019 in the federal capital. The *batin* guarantees the *adat* and its respect.

The Orang Hulu *hadat*, customary laws, is "historically transmitted sayings" which categorize normative behavior to which the people are expected to conform. Those who deviate from the *hadat* are expected to be punished in one way or another. (...) Now, ultimate sanctions of the law are unfavorable social opinion, *malu* (shame), and supernatural retribution. (Maeda 2001 : 77)

Knowledge and adhesion to the *adat* vary according to the degree of interference and islamisation (Nobuta 2009) of village societies. In Kampung Peta the *adat* is alive and well and is transmitted in formal teachings that are offered to all inhabitants. The *batin* is the one who is required to control it better.

The *batin* leads the JKKK (Jawatankuasa Kemajuan dan Keselamatan Kampung or village committee for development and security) which in Kampung Peta is composed of fourteen people: Rampuyan Kantan, his son, his younger brother and his own son, their younger brother, their two nieces and the husband of one and others whose identity I do not know. The village is a large family but it is a smaller family that is active in the JKKK. Asma justifies this bias by the lack of interest of other inhabitants in the governance of the village and their lack of enthusiasm to incur transport and other costs which, although associated with the missions of the JKKK and its delegates, remain at the expenses of the persons. When I ask her why then these expenses are not reimbursed, she ceases to be the knowledgeable and diligent informant that she has been for

the rest of my stay and tells me that this is none of my business. Anthropologist Colin Nicholas, who has been accompanying this village for at least twenty years to assert its rights to the land or to carry out initiatives that would reduce poverty, nevertheless considers that the governance of the village allows it to make wiser choices than others for the preservation of its material and cultural integrity (interview with Colin Nicholas). At a meeting in September 2018 that I was given the opportunity to attend to (see photo 6 below), the people present were not only the JKKK members since there were more than fourteen people.

Photo 6. Meeting between Colin Nicholas (COAC) and Kampung Peta inhabitants at *balai budaya*. Photo A. Vidal, September 2018.

3.2.2. Gotong-royong

Although more "informal and loosely knit" (Thambiah 1999 : 269) than in a Malay village, Kampung Peta's social life has many things in common with it, including the JKKK and the *gotong-royong*. During my stay, two *gotong-royong* activities took place in the primary school. The first was devoted to landscaping: weeding, sweeping of dead leaves and planting of trees. In the second, the ceiling of the canteen was repainted. Participants of both genders were parents or grandparents of students, but not only. They worked for more than two hours before being offered a light meal. The *rumah adat*, built at the end of 2018, was also the subject of a *gotong-royong* construction site. Thompson describes another Malay *gotong-royong* construction site for the rehabilitation of a suspension bridge:

The dozen or more men involved in the project worked in pairs spread out along the span of the bridge, removing cracked and broken planks along with rusty nails, and replacing them with new planks. (...) The bridge repair project reflected the sort of gotong-royong activity of rural kampung that is valorized in Malaysian popular culture. (Thompson 2012 : 125)

According to Thompson, the *gotong-royong* is not so much a rural use as one marked by the socio-economic class, since he notes its persistence in poor and tight-knit urban environments on the occasion of a *kenduri*. Self-help is evident in communities where there are reciprocal obligations to interconnectedness and service delivery, and where they cannot afford the services of poorer than themselves. This is especially the case in Kampung Peta, which has often been presented to me as an extended family, where all homes have blood ties to each other.

3.2.3. Land

In pre-colonial uses in the Malaysian peninsula, the usufruct of the land belonged to whoever worked on it, as described here by Paul H. Kratoska.

Indigenous Malay law, then, provided that a person retained proprietary rights over land so long as the land continued to be affected by his labour, and when land no longer bore signs of the previous possessor's labour his claim to the land lapsed. The governing principle was that a person was entitled to the product of his labour. (Kratoska 1985, *in* Nonini 1992 : 34)

The colonial authorities (and their influence before 1874 on the states they had not yet submitted) changed this relationship to the land in which the land "in most areas in Malaya was not a commodity, that is, a thing or object to be bought or sold as such, or to be 'owned' in an absolute sense" (Nonini 1992: 33). It is less a temporary possession than a usufruct, a right of use. This is the relationship the Jakun had with the land in the 1960s. Their practice of sampling is very extensive and involves cultivating plots which are then left fallow, the time to let grow a secondary forest (*belukar*) which once cleared will again enrich the soil. "By tradition, the Orang Hulu say, the land belongs to the *batin*, and there are no sales of land along the Endau" (Maeda 2001 : 55). The rotation of the plots is organized by the *batin* which distributes them to each *kelamin*, who can clear them, cultivate them and harvest the product of their labour until the next

rotation.

Clearing is accomplished by felling trees and then burning off the cover vegetation. This activity is supervised by the *batin*, who uses his knowledge of tradition, his experience, and the inspiration provided by his familiar spirits to decide upon the site to be cleared and the date of the clearing operations. Before the plot of land (*homa*) is cleared, the *batin* apportions it among the village households (each consisting of at least a husband and a wife, a *kelamin*). Each household is responsible for its own plot, usually half an acre or so. (Maeda 2001 : 37)

Today in the Orang Asli communities "there are two types of property: individual lots (people are given 6 acres or so, where the houses are sitting), that's personal property that can be passed on to next generation. And there is the forest, that's communal property" (interview with Colin Nicholas) in which one can own individual trees without owning the land at the same time. Trees can therefore be sold: "The durían tree is not unfrequently the subject of sale" (Logan 1847: 260). The agricultural land is now owned in Kampung Peta in its entirety and individually. They are transmitted by a "bilateral inheritance system" (Thambiah 1999: 287), to both daughters and sons, and can be sold or purchased provided they remain in the community (Aboriginal Peoples Act 2007: 7-2). I have only heard of one case of land surrender, the sale by Ismail, a poor man of about 50 years of age, with a very large family, of his land to his sister. Renting is more frequent and the farmer who cultivates the land pays the owner half of the income he earns (informal interview with Balqis).

3.2.4. The *Kelamin* Family Group

In Malay, language with which Jakun language has largely hybridized, *keluarga* means family and *kelamin* couple or pair. In Malaysia and Indonesia, the word *keluarga* is used to refer to the nuclear family, but the Jakun prefer to use *keluarga* for the extended family and reserve *kelamin* for the nuclear family¹³. The inhabitants of the village constitute one and the same *keluarga*, even if some branches are quite remote. *Kelamin* is the unit in which the Jakun live and share resources. It is an economic and, ideally, residential unit.

A *kelamin*, a family or household, is the minimum, basic unit among the Orang Hulu.

13 In Borneo, *lamin* could also mean "residential unit". It is the apartment in a long house and the family group that occupies it (Bernard Sellato, personal communication).

Generally speaking, a single family occupies a house and consists of a conjugal couple and unmarried children. The wife and husband are equal, and neither seems to exercise authority over the other in any formal manner. (...) Although the conjugal couple is an important unit of social activity, the mechanism uniting the spouses does not work strongly. (...) Moreover, individual property is clearly separate. And divorce and remarriage are simple processes and are common practices. (Maeda 2001 : 65)

A *kelamin* is formed from the moment of marriage. A girl and a boy then settle down together, at the parents of one or the other, and as soon as possible in a new house. In Kampung Peta there are 72 houses (my survey) for 90 *kelamin* according to the *batin*. Four *kelamin* have two houses at their disposal, one in the village and the other, an improved "field hut" closer to the land they operate. It is more common to observe that there are several *kelamin* in one house. This is the case for half a dozen houses and it is due to lasting material difficulties for the young couple to set up a permanent home ("a lack of resources for individual families and a lack of space in the localities," Thambiah 1999: 271) rather than a first temporary residence among parents as observed elsewhere in the peninsula (Carsten 1996). Some houses are inhabited by single people (*sendiri*): Sam, a man of about 50 years, is not married but lives by himself. Rabiah, a single woman of about 40 years, also lives alone. Her parents died and her brothers and sisters live in the village but she is converted to Islam and, because of this status, received one of the most comfortable houses in Kampung Peta. Some seniors also live alone. Most of the houses in the village are inhabited by couples with unmarried children and sometimes an elderly grandparent. These elderly people, even when they live with one of their children, are in fact a *kelamin*, an economic unit alone, but often they are no longer economically independent. So in my study of the income and expenses of a *kelamin* I sometimes came to include one or two grandparents without resources. I prefer to talk then about a home in the sense of residents of the same house.

In the next chapters I study the resources of these *kelamin* or households: subsistence activities, independent commercial activities of the primary sector, then wage-earning and independent activities in services and especially tourism.

Chapter 4. Subsistence Activities

The transition of the Orang Asli from a subsistence economy to a market economy is well documented, with texts that cover several decades and concern several groups: Jakun in the 1960s (Maeda 2001), Batek in the 1970s (Endicott and Cottendi 2012), Semai in the 1980s (Gomes 2004) and Temuan in the 1990s (Nobuta 2009). These studies reflect very different situations and a greater or lesser dependence on commercial activities. Involved in the trade of forest products for a long time, in 2019 the Jakun participate strongly in the market economy. However, their subsistence activities can help them to be resilient in case of economic difficulties: do these activities in Kampung Peta allow them to stand losses of income and to safeguard a certain independence from their economic partners? After having compiled a picture of the wild and cultivated resources that the villagers have at their disposal to ensure their daily lives, we will try to understand the decline of their subsistence activities.

4.1. Food Self-production

Self-production has become marginal in Malaysia: even if the Orang Asli are, of all the ethnic groups in the country, the one who uses it the most, it is estimated at less than 5%, when the income from their commercial activities represents more than 70% (UNDP 2013: 313, based on 2009 data). In Kampung Peta this share is not so negligible and it contributes to the positive appreciation of the villagers in their place of life as expressed by Syazwani, a woman of about 50 years of age whose husband is a full-time wage earner.

We like being in the village: we don't pay for the water, we don't pay for the house, there is the garden, there is family and friends. We like to eat *ubi*, *pucuk paku*, there is no need to pay. (...) Here we are fine¹⁴. (interview with Syazwani)

Ubi are root and tuber vegetables. *Pucuk-pucuk* are leaves, usually wild. *Pucuk paku* is the most popular wild leaf (*Diplazium esculentum*, a kind of fern). Asma also compares the city lifestyle (whether Kahang or Kuala Lumpur) with her life in the village by emphasizing the importance in the city of money and commercial relations.

14 "Kita suka di kampung, air tak bayar, rumah tak bayar, ada kebun, ada keluarga, ada kawan. Kita nak makan ubi, pucuk paku, tak bayar. (...) Sini senang hati."

If you stay in Kahang, you cannot collect babi, sayur [vegetables], apa laginya? (...)
In KL, pay. One goes to toilet, must pay. Tissue? Pay. Money is everything. Because that is important have the forest. (interview with Asma)

4.1.1. Fishing, Hunting, Gathering

In the 1960s, "the game and fish gained are an important source of animal protein" (Maeda 2001: 36). Maeda Narifumi lists various techniques of fishing for fish and shrimp: to the line, with bait made of manioc, to the trap in rattan traps (*lukah*), to the lance with or without the use of poison based on *nuba* root, *Fabaceae Derris*. The techniques are different upstream of the Endau, as in Kampung Peta, and downstream, where the use of the net (*jala*) purchased outside is more common. "At the downstream hamlets, where the catches are not as abundant, fish screens (*jalin*), fish-cage traps, and piscisidal plants are more often used" (Maeda 2001: 36).

The techniques I have observed are angling (*pancing*), traps, made out of handcraft or recycling plastic packaging, and nets. Most homes are equipped with fishing rods and, like it was 50 years ago, it is an activity that women and men engage in and that seemed to me to be the village's favourite subsistence activity (that of Zubaidah, whose husband just lost his job, as of Umairah and Zulkifli, a couple with two decent incomes). The authorized fishing area is located downstream of the park.

The villagers also eat game: wild boars (*babi hutan*), wild gallinacean (*ayam hutan*), deer. All I have ever seen is wild boar. Deer are more often caught in the rainy season, which is conducive to very few activities, except hunting. The *ayam hutan* was mentioned before me only by a villager converted to Islam and to whom the consumption of wild boar is prohibited. The turtles are consumed as well as the frogs but I have been able to see, however, that it was possible to release them for lack of appetite. Monkeys were still consumed in the 1990s but were no longer at the end of that decade (interview with Asma) for conservation issues that we will mention later.

Blowpipe (*sumpitan*) was used, as in other Orang Asli groups, with arrows poisoned with *ipoh* wood (*Antiaris toxicaria*) concentrate to kill civets and tree-roaming animals such as squirrels and birds (Endicott and Endicott 2012: 107). It is no longer so today but these animals can be

slaughtered with a slingshot (*lastik*). Omar, a man from the village who is about 30 years old, hunts with *lastik* (he has a purchased one), as does Machang, a man of about 50 years old interviewed by Colin Nicholas twenty years ago: "Before, when we found a *beringin* tree¹⁵, we used to kill the birds with a slingshot¹⁶" (Nicholas 1999: 13).

Wild boars are hunted with a spear, which is not thrown but planted in the animal's body. Hunting is a male activity but during the intrusion of a wild boar I saw women stand ready to kill the animal. The legislation allows Orang Asli to hunt for personal consumption one species of wild boar, three species of deer, three species of monkeys and macaques, two porcupines and two birds (Wildlife Conservation Act 2010: 192). Maeda mentions only the wild pig, a small deer (*kancil*, *Tragulus sp.*), monkeys, pythons, turtles. The catching or hunting techniques he has documented are traps, snares, blowpipe, spear (Maeda 2001: 35).

The *pucuk-pucuk* are available at will, especially by the river. It is mainly women who pick them. Hatiqah, a woman in her fifties who often gathers edible wild plants, names *pucuk paku*, the favourite *pucuk*, as well as *pucuk kedember*, *pucuk kepondong*, *pucuk simpu*, *pucuk cekoh*, *pucuk kokol*, *jering* (*pucuk* and pea), *pucuk putat* which are young leaves of trees or bushes. Thambiah also notes that "the collecting of food for household consumption – vegetables, roots, ferns and mushrooms – is an activity predominantly done by female" (Thambiah 1999: 280).

4.1.2. Subsistence Agriculture

Around the houses are raised for their flesh exclusively chickens (*ayam kampung*) and ducks, on free range. Like dogs and cats, they are partly fed with food scraps and no food is bought nor prepared for them. Cats are allowed inside houses, unlike dogs that stay outside. Neither of them benefit from gestures of human affection.

The villagers grow some roots and tubers, *ubi* (manioc, taro, sweet potato), of which they also consume the leaves: *pucuk keledak* are young sweet potato leaves. It is less common to eat young rubber leaves or the heart of a palm (*bayas*). The fruit trees of the village are durian, rambutan, mangosteen, trees whose harvests are short and intense. With the exception of the areca whose nut is eaten with a betel leaf and is more of a recreation than a food intake, plants that bear fruits continuously (banana, coconut tree, papaya, pineapple) are much less present in the village than

15 *Ficus benjamina* whose fruits are prized by birds.

16 "Masa dulu, bila kita jumpa pokok beringin, kita suka lastik itu burung."

in most Malaysian villages.

In the 1960s, hill rice, cassava, maize, millet, bananas and sugar cane (Maeda 2001: 37) were cultivated in the Endau basin. Although it is common in South-East Asia to start a swidden agriculture cycle with rice, the Jakun often start farming a plot by cultivating corn and cassava directly, two American-origin cultogens, and then planting fruit trees (Maeda 2001: 39). The opening of a new plot by slash-and-burn is regulated by custom (*adat*).

Clearing is accomplished by felling trees and then burning off the cover vegetation. (...) A ceremony is held after the rainy season to placate the spirit of the earth (*jin bumi*) at the site about to be cleared and the work then begins. The undergrowth and heavy wood will first be cleared (*nobas* and *nobang*, respectively). Afterwards the cover vegetation is set afire (*hangoi*). These clearing activities are carried out between June and September, depending on the rainfall. (Maeda 2001 : 37)

The harvest is the object of a ritual conducted jointly by the village magician (*pawang*) and the *batin*, who are then one. During the first days of harvest, "several taboos (*pantang*) are imposed to the members of the hamlet" (Maeda 2001: 38) and the first crop rice is shared at a party. The *padi bukit* plantation was abandoned in Kampung Peta in 1994 following a loss of transmission of the rite (Nicholas 1999: 2). On the other hand, since the 1960s, before the creation of the park (1993) and the concession of an Orang Asli reserve (1989), the villagers no longer have the right to practice this semi-nomadic agriculture by opening swidden plots outside the 220 hectares they already cultivate (interview with Kamaruddin). The crops (mainly rubber planting) are now permanent on the reserve lands and the slash-and-burn concern parcels left fallow, rarely from the forest since it never has time to develop. In 2019, Syamsul started cultivating a plot of *padi bukit* again, without much success since few plants had grown. Two of his aunts, Syazrina and Hatiqah, were during my stay clearing another piece of land for the same purpose: they cut out the remaining vegetation mechanically (photo 7 below).

Photo 7. Syazrina opening up a plot. Photo A. Vidal, March-April 2019.

4.2. Decline in Subsistence Activities

The first texts about the Jakun present rural communities engaged in food farming alongside the collection of commercial products.

Some few years back, the Jakuns on the Ěndau, that is to say, the Ěndau, Sěmbrong, and their tributaries, were in comparative comfortable circumstances, procuring the produce of the jungle for traders, and receiving the ordinary returns in kind, or planting tapioca, klědek, sugar-cane, and plantain. (Hervey 1881 : 120-121)

Aside from sugarcane, these crops are the most common in the village and correspond to the crops that the inhabitants plant most easily – or would plant, in the case of bananas (plantains), if the animals did not endanger their crops.

4.2.1. Animal Intrusions and Crop Damages

D F. A. Hervey does not mention the culture of *padi bukit*. Less present than that of manioc, it is nevertheless attested in Kampung Peta by Maeda in the 1960s before disappearing in the 1990s. Other food crops are also much less present in Kampung Peta than in villages with similar

economic activities. In a Temuan village (another Orang Asli group of the Malayic type) where the culture of the rubber tree dominates, in Ulu Beranang Jeramkedah in the state of Negeri Sembilan, the fruits are widely available and many vegetables are grown around the house (my observations).

Kampung Peta, unlike other villages, is located between a forest reserve and a national park. Wildlife makes there numerous intrusions. This is a common trait in rural wooded areas (Guérin 2017a) but it is accentuated with the reduction of the habitat of the species in question, destroyed by deforestation and the establishment of oil palm plantations (Luquiau 2013, The Star 2019). Elephants eat fruit and break young rubber trees. The villagers tried unsuccessfully to pull them away, firing firecrackers at night, shouting or operating noisy devices: "We make noise, they run away"¹⁷ (interview with Nasrul). Wild boars dig up roots and tubers. Iman, who grows sweet potatoes around her garden in the middle of the village and at the house of whom I saw a monkey stealing cookies, describes this situation.

We have problems with wild boars and monkeys and also elephants. They disturb us. (...) There are bananas here but it's difficult because elephants also like to eat them. And for pineapples, it's the monkeys. (...) If you want to eat bananas here, you have to buy them from Kahang¹⁸. (interview with Iman)

Qalesya is a woman in her late thirties who has an older husband, both of whom have no regular income. They live in an extension of the village, less dense and closer to the rubber plots, and she also complains of wild boars digging up her *ubi* and elephants attacking her banana trees. Fatimah, a 50-year-old woman who lives far out of the village, along the road, also complains about elephants: "Sini susah tanam apa yang binatang tak boleh makan. (...) Kalau tak ada gajah, kita boleh tanam ubi, pisang." Ahmad, a 60-year-old who (among many other activities) shows blowpipe and animal traps for tourists, does not mention these intrusions. He pretends to live on the vegetables he cultivates but he lives with his children in the heart of the village, in a set of houses organized around a central and relatively closed courtyard. This configuration may keep the animal away from his vegetable garden. Syazrina, the mother of Iman, considers that elephants trespass two or three times a year and that today "every month they come in our gardens"¹⁹. These intrusions have already been documented by Maeda.

17 "Kita buat bunyi, dia lari."

18 "Kita ada masalah dengan babi hutan dan monkeys, and then gajah. Mereka sudah mengganggu. (...) Ada pisang di sini tapi is difficult because sometimes the gajah also like pisang. Nanas di sini banyak sangat itu monkeys. (...) Here if you want to makan pisang, you need to buy from Kahang."

19 "Tiap-tiap bulan datang kebun."

Before harvest time, subsidiary swidden huts are built on the clearings to protect the crops from numerous pests, such as wild elephants, pigs or deer. In one hamlet fences were built around the entire field to protect it from pigs and elephants. Although other hamlets do not provide fences, usually some men sleep in the swidden huts to keep watch. (Maeda 2001 : 38)

In the 1960s, these intrusions were so devastating that they were able to deter from planting rubber: "Small holdings of rubber were introduced by the government years ago, but they did not seem to have caught hold due to the ravages of elephants" (Maeda 2001: 40). Cash crops are not safe from animal predation, and the cost is important for a two-year rubber tree being destroyed, as it is a long-term investment for the person who planted it. Food crops, which can be consumed by wild boars and monkeys, seem even more vulnerable.

4.2.2 Preferences for Commercial Activities

Is this the only reason why the villagers of Kampung Peta do not cultivate to meet their subsistence needs? For a long time the Jakun have been arbitrating between subsistence activities and commercial activities, with apparently a preference for them when available. Hervey already noted agricultural work being abandoned (perhaps for a period that will make not harm) to prioritize a commercial activity.

At this place, Kampong Kěnalau, I found a clearing, but no cultivation; on asking the reason, I was told they were too busy getting rattans for the Malays, which they do at a fixed price in rice and other articles, such as clothing, crockery, parangs, salt, and tobacco. (Hervey 1881 : 103)

Maeda in the 1960s documented a further decline in subsistence practices (subsistence agriculture and food gathering).

There are many instances of the Orang Hulu no longer practicing the traditional cycle of agricultural work. In these cases there is a large reliance upon the sale of collected forest products, such as rattan, to obtain money for necessities. The people as a whole have become rather indifferent to subsistence by swiddening and searching

ressources in the forest. Instead, they prefer to earn money to buy necessities.
(Maeda 2001 : 43)

This is a finding shared by authors who work on other groups, such as Alberto Gomes who in his work on the Semai in the 1980s emphasizes the use of the expression *cari duit* (looking for money) to identify activities that bring money and participate in a market economy.

In recent years, the subsistence activities of swidden cultivation, hunting and fishing, which the Semai are renowned for, have been relegated to secondary economic status. At the time of my study, these subsistence pursuits were not as economically important to Semai livelihood as commodity and cash earning productive activities, such as fruit collecting, forest product trading, rubber tapping and wage employment that people keenly undertook to earn money. (Gomes 2004 : 51)

This decline is part of a large movement, which affects all the Orang Asli groups and whose dynamics are due to the attraction of the market economy and the disappearance of the material basis of subsistence, with the destruction of the forest. It is a push and pull movement, with forces that repel and others that attract. Colin Nicholas *et al.* show how degradation of their environment, by restricting Semai's access to land and forest resources, hampers livelihoods and engages in paid employment (Nicholas *et al.* 2003). Shanthi Thambiah insists on the attractiveness of the market economy and the way in which the Jakun voluntarily commit to it: "For most families wage employment is the only means for acquiring processed food and new prestige symbols such as motorcycles, modern houses, electrical appliances, etc." (Thambiah 1999 : 282). In the 1960s, the needs, some of which were then new, concerned clothing and equipment goods: sarongs, shoes, bras, kitchen equipment, tools (machetes, hoes, sickles), radio sets, electric or oil lamps are purchased outside the village (Maeda 2001: 56-60). "There is the consideration that purchased goods are often of better quality than those which can be extracted or fabricated from forest resources" (Maeda 2001 : 43). Today in Kampung Peta other needs require the acquisition of consumer goods (means of transport, energy, building materials, means of telecommunication) which are very expensive with regard to the average income and for which it is necessary to obtain more money. A scooter, such as those used for transport in and around the village, costs around RM 9,000 depending on the duration of the credit while the monthly income of village farmers rarely reaches RM 1,000 (Malaysian minimum wage being RM 1,100 in 2019).

Among other reasons for the decline in subsistence activities is economic rationality. The comparison between the work invested and the result obtained is an important motivation to engage in one activity or another.

Collection and growing subsistence materials requires considerable time and patience, whereas the cash products of the forest are rather easy to found and not yet as exhausted as the subsistence products are. (Maeda 2001 : 43)

Maeda also notes: "It is true that an Orang Hulu can make money and buy food quicker and more easily than he can obtain it from the forest and prepare it" (Maeda 2001: 37). It is a rational choice that the Jakun operate in their arbitrations, preferring from time to time commercial activities to those of subsistence to limit their working time and the tasks which they consider most painful. This criterion of least effort is also present, we shall see, to arbitrate between different commercial activities.

A last motivation to prefer the search for money (*cari duit*) to that of subsistence products is well documented by the literature on the Orang Asli in the last decades but it no longer seemed relevant to me in Kampung Peta where the question no longer really arises, or at least not in those terms. That's the difference in status between the food, which has to be shared, and the money or the goods that are (or can be) marketed, which everybody keeps to themselves. Engaging in the search for commercial products also means not subjecting the result of his work to the obligation of sharing with others, even if it would be reciprocal.

Ressources extracted from the forest for subsistence purposes are expected to be shared with relatives and neighbors. Products extracted for commerce, however, are clearly valued in terms of money and are not subject to sharing. (Maeda 2001 : 43)

The sharing of subsistence is a common trait among different Orang Asli groups. For the Bateks, a group of hunter-gatherers from the northern part of the peninsula, food is shared as opposed to other goods and money.

Sharing food was an obligation for the Batek, not something the giver had much discretion over. The sharing obligation was enforced by strong social pressure. (...)

In theory nonconsumable goods a person made or obtained in trade, including cash, were considered personal possessions that did not have to be shared. (Endicott 2012 : 73-74)

Ahmad explains that game (in this case boar) is shared with "whoever asks" (*sesiapa yang minta*) at a rate of one kilogram per household and that if you want more, you have to pay (*bayar*). The term *bayar* situates the exchange in a commercial context, where the relations are closed (*putus*) by the monetary compensation. Maeda recounts the repugnance of a *batin* to have the anthropologist pay for the gas tank he just received from him: "If I paid the money on the spot, he argued, the relation between us would be put to an end (*putus*)" (Maeda 2001: 30). On the contrary, reciprocal relationships assume that one demand (*minta*) and the other gives (*bagi*).

Wild game, caught by luck, and the harvest, reaped by one's own efforts (*kerja*), are expected as a matter of course to be distributed to others. These receivers can, out of necessity or merely if they want (*ingin*), demand (*minta*) without shame or consideration of recompense of some portion of the goods. Contrariwise, the exchange of goods which have been evaluated in terms of money is a sort of "on-the-spot" give-and-take, with the relationship between the participants in the exchange beginning and ending with the exchange itself. (...) Instead of making a demand (*minta*), however, it is said that the taker will "pay" (*bayar*). (Maeda 2001 : 29)

This situation described by Maeda and Ahmad is quite different from what I have seen. According to my observations, the wild boar is divided only in the immediate family, this for various reasons: due to the natural growth of the population, Kampung Peta has become much bigger, from 19 *kelamin* in the 1960s to more than 80 today, and the neighbors are too many to share a single beast with them. Freezers are not rare and make it possible to preserve meat, or to share the wild boar with oneself in the future. And finally it is possible to sell the wild boar to Malaysian Chinese merchants. What money can buy, and then what can be sold, gets out of the reciprocal trading system that Maeda calls, according to Bronisław Malinowski, "a constant give and take" or ongoing exchange of donations. The goods which were divided then become merchandise. Colin Nicholas *et al.* showed a similar evolution in the circulation of *petai* pods (*Parkia speciosa*), among others, within the Semai communities (Nicholas *et al.* 2003) and Alberto Gomes documented the same change 15 years earlier: "I had come across hunters selling their game to others instead of sharing it with their fellow villagers, a practice that would have

been unthinkable for Semai in the past" (Gomes 2004: 52).

When the Jakun in the 19th century enter into commercial relations with the Malays to obtain food or equipment in exchange for forest products, and nowadays when they adopt other activities (independent or salaried), they make economic choices which are also life choices concerning their contact with and participation in the majority society of the peninsula. They then choose by balancing many criteria (time spent, difficulty) including contact with the outside world.

It seems, then, that the Orang Hulu have done "commercial" collecting activities as well as subsistence ones either to maintain their way of life or to prevent oppression from outside. Through time, of course, more and more emphasis has come to be placed on commercial activities. (Maeda 2001 : 28)

This motivation to protect a way of life appears very clearly in the current initiative to cultivate the padi bukit again. The first one to do so, Syamsul, is very attached to the village, Jakun culture and the forest. Despite studies in accounting that would have allowed him to leave the village, he insisted on returning and participating in the community life. For him, growing rice does not correspond to any economic logic but makes sense within a cultural and identity framework that he wishes to preserve or revive.

We have begun to see how what are made these choices between subsistence activities and commercial activities, what are the reasons behind them, the constraints faced by the villagers and the preferences they express. Rattan harvesting, rubber planting and tourism are the three main activities available to villagers to help them earn a living, but there are others. Having identified and described these activities, we must try to understand the choices made between them in the light of the criteria that we have begun to list.

Chapter 5. Primary Sector Commercial Activities

After we tried to understand the decline in subsistence activities (harvesting and subsistence agriculture) in Kampung Peta, we must now consider the commercial activities that are carried out in the village, initially those of the primary sector. The most important of these are the gathering of rattan and the planting of rubber, the first being a long-standing activity and the other having recently been introduced, as we shall see. After examining the conditions of exercise and the income that can be earned from them, we will wonder what are the reasons why the inhabitants engage in one rather than the other, what are the choices they make between the two and on what criteria? What other productions are they considering and what are the advantages to them?

5.1. Collecting and Trading Rattan

Rattan (*rotan*) is the generic name for 106 climbing palm species present in Malaysia, of which about 20 are used commercially (FAO 1997). Rattan is much mentioned in the accounts of the early ethnographers, because of the omnipresence of its prickly stems in the landscape: "The rattan thorns were a constant annoyance" (Hervey 1879:103).

The country from Kuala Indau up to Kuala Sembrong is perfectly flat and covered with dense uninhabited jungle, of which perhaps the most striking feature is the abundance of rotans of various species, the most conspicuous along the river banks being "Rotan S'ntawa." (Lake et Kelsall 1894 : 2)

5.1.1. A Long-Standing Commercial Activity

The trade in non-timber forest products harvested by inland populations has been documented since the first millennium in the peninsula (Andaya 2002: 30). The commercial collect of these products by the Jakun of the Endau basin was documented by Logan in 1847.

The Malays ascend in their canoes laden with a tempting variety of [articles] and the

Binuá, unable to resist the desire of calling some of them his own, needs little persuasion to become a debtor of the Malay trader (...). The Binuá now finds himself (...) under an obligation to collect rattans, káyu gháru, chándán, camphor, dammar, wax, or taban for his creditor. (Logan 1847 : 261)

The products which the Jakun trade are camphor²⁰, *kayu gaharu*, a resin produced by the diseased wood of some trees among which *Aquilaria sp.*, *taban*, a natural latex, and *dammar*, a resin from the *Dipterocarpaceae Shorea sp.* Maeda draws a similar list from her observations more than a century later (2001: 43). Rattan was a major trade between Jakun and Malay traders in the 19th century. Hervey crosses several times the path of "Jakun [...] engaged by Malays in procuring rattan" (Hervey 1881:98) while others are, as we have seen, "too busy getting rattans for the Malays" (Hervey 1881:103). Lake and Kelsall met "a penghulu [Malay leader] of the Kahang district who had gone downstream in search of rattan with his Jakun²¹" (Lake and Kelsall 1894: 6).

Rattan was not collected as a constant or regular employment in the 1840s (Logan 1847). In the 1890s the hamlets along the Endau seemed chiefly engaged in collecting forest produce for the Malays (Hervey 1881; Lake and Kelsall 1894), although we do not have any documents about Orang Hulu attitudes toward such work at that time. In the 1960s rattan collecting is a regular part of their work. Most of them take "cutting rattan" (*potong rotan* or *kerja rotan*) as their own work for a livelihood. (Maeda 2001 : 31)

5.1.2. Economic, Environmental, and Social Issues

In the 1960s the collection of rattan eclipsed that of other non-timber forest products, or even other activities, including subsistence activities. The collection itself is according to Maeda a rather masculine activity which men run in the morning, returning home at noon. "Women never go out to cut rattan" (Maeda 2001: 44) but they clean it in the river. The Chinese *tawkey* or merchant comes then by boat. The merchant is no longer Malay but the practice remains the same: he buys rattan and sells food or equipment. His sales are higher than his purchases and he

20 Logan (1847: 263) documents rites related to the collection of camphor, including a ritual language (*bássá kápor*) and food prohibitions, to put all the chances on his side in this collection, which is very unpredictable. See also Lake and Kelsall 1894: 8-9.

21 "The Penghulu of the Kahang district was some distance down stream with a party of his Jakuns collecting rotans."

leaves the Jakun indebted and forced to collect rattan for his next visit. This is a situation already described by Logan, who notes the high selling prices and low purchase prices of the Malay merchant, noting a profit margin of 50% at each transaction (Logan 1847: 287-288). Maeda points out that the *tawkey* enjoys a monopsony situation: he is the only merchant who agrees to come from Padang Endau to buy the rattan upstream, which leaves little choice to the sellers (Maeda 2001: 48).

This increase in activity seems to have been accompanied by a certain exhaustion of the resource. In the 1960s, "little rattan is seen along the river banks and the Orang Hulu have to penetrate inland to get them" (Maeda 2001: 44). Not all the collection sites are so far away that the Jakun cannot go there for the day, but some expeditions take them far away from their place of residence.

When the site for cutting rattan is far from the hamlet, several families go together and spend as long as a month there. Sometimes each family builds its own cottage, and sometimes the whole group builds a longhouse and lives there together on the collection site. (...) After about a month's work in the interior, such a group usually returns to the hamlet and rests during the following month. They explain that the work is too hard to be continued without an interval. (Maeda 2001 : 45)

Shanthi Thambiah documented a somehow different situation in 1999. The rattan is then only one of the remunerated activities of the Jakun and this activity is in full evolution. According to her, the demand for *layar tanah*, *batu*, *lebun*, *kandul*, *semabu*, two sorts of *segar* (*badak* and *emas*), *kerai*, *duduk*, *sentawa*, *tetil* et *dahan* "is not as great as before" (Thambiah 1999 : 276) and only *manau* and *jelayan* are subject to significant commercial demand. They are in fact thick enough to be used in the manufacture of furniture. The other species, with a finer stem, are used in basketry. While Maeda described a sexual sharing of tasks, for Thambiah this sharing is a recent trend due to the changing demand but it is not traditional: "The rattan is pulled and cut into long strips, (...) by both males and females. Carrying the rattan into the settlement from the forest was also done by both sexes" (Thambiah 1999 : 276). The situation is changing because of the demand for *manau* rattan: thicker and heavier, harder to carry, it would justify that women be excluded from collecting activities.

Photo 8. Rattan *manau*. Photo A. Vidal, March-April 2019.

5.1.3. Trading Rattan Today

If the demand for *manau* remains high, I have noted however that it is rare and that the villagers did not collect much for the sale of their harvest in April 2019 (six or seven fagots (*ikat*), that is about forty stems of about two meters, see photo 8). Among the people who collect the rattan, I have identified three couples who work together (Fatimah and Nasrul, a 50-year-old couple, Ahmad and Zarina, a 60-year-old couple, Qalesya, a woman almost 40 years old and her husband 15 years older than her), two women whose husband has another occupation and a woman who lives alone. Rather than being gendered, it seems that the collection of rattan is a second-class occupation, which supplements the income of a household in case of economic difficulty or in a context where men are offered better jobs than women.

Photo 9. The *tawkey rotan* has the merchandise he buys loaded. Photo A. Vidal, March-April 2019.

In Kampung Peta, there are seven *kelamin*, or just under 10% of households, who collect rattan and sell it to an intermediary. They represent twelve people according to Fatimah. Every two months or so, the *tawkey rotan* (rattan trader) comes at the request of someone from the village, when the inhabitants have amassed a sufficient harvest. The *tawkey* now comes by road, and it is also by road that the villagers went to the place of their collection. During my stay, the rattan was collected about 20 minutes by scooter from the village, which entails significant fuel costs but the villagers nevertheless continue to reside at home during the month or the weeks of gathering. These places of gathering change every year. Syamsul, who himself works in tourism and does not look for rattan, explains this rotation.

They go to the jungle in one area this year, next year too and other and when rotan is back we come back, we don't take the whole place. If not the rotan is finished, is gone. It recovers around two or four years. (interview with Syamsul)

If the collection of rattan is authorized for the Orang Asli in the forest reserve (National Forestry Act 2006: 40), sale is prohibited but appears to be tolerated. Nor does the *tawkey* has the right to buy it. In other states on the East coast where he operates (Pahang, Kelantan), it is completely legal, he tells me by showing me papers. But in the Johor his activity is illegal. Even though the whole village knows about it and he passes an official car of the national park, he fears that I will take pictures of his truck's license plate. On the road leading to the village, his truck stops at each place where buyers have placed at the side of the road *ikat* of a hundred rods (*lai*) of about four meters in length, folded in half. Each *ikat* weighs several tens of kilograms. Everyone can lift them but this represents a big effort (photo 9 previous page).

Photo 10. Zarina cleans rattan. Photo A. Vidal, March-April 2019.

The group of ten villagers who sold their crop in April 2019 while I was there picked up 17,000 stems, almost exclusively from fine stem rattans. These are negotiated between RM 35 and 50 a cent, against RM 2 to 4 a piece for the *manau*. Qalesya and her husband earned about RM 800 on that day, which is their only income for the next two months. Fatimah and her husband earned little by their standards: "Yesterday we did not earn much, 1,000 or more only, for almost one month of work. One home, two people collecting²²" (interview with Fatimah and Nasrul). The Malaysian minimum wage is in 2019 of RM 1,100 monthly per person. Syazrina compares the current prices to the prevailing prices a few decades ago: the price for one hundred ikat, RM 6, enabled to buy 30 kg of rice, whereas today RM 50 enables to buy only 20 kg. Since the harvest places are far from the river and the *tawkey* no longer comes by boat, the rattan is sold unwashed, unlike that of two other villagers, Ahmad and his spouse Zarina. They go to the forest together to collect the rattan. Zarina is also recognized by others for her ability to find rattans of the most highly rated varieties. She alone takes care of cleaning it, leaving it for a day or two to soak and then cleaning each rod with a metal brush (see photo 10 previous page). They work in one-week cycles: five days of collection, one day of cleaning and one day of rest. Ahmad and Zarina, for whom it is not the only activity but who dedicates a lot of time to it, told me that they earn about RM 2,000 for each passage of the *tawkey*. Despite their age, they collect more rattan and at a more regular pace than *kelamin* who have other sources of income but also than some *kelamin* who have only rattan to live on.

The gathering of rattan is considered the most difficult activity for earning a living. "Colecting

22 "Kemarin jumlah tak banyak, baru 1,000 lebih sahaja, itupun dekat satu bulan kerja. Satu rumah, dua orang cari."

rattan is hard,²³" says Zubaidah, a young woman recently involved in this activity. "For us Asli looking for rattan is hard,²⁴" says Qalesya that day. She and her husband, hearing the news of the upcoming passage of the *tawkey*, cut rattan during an intense week. Nasrul describes more precisely the hardship: the need to walk in rugged terrain that hurts the legs, as well as the load over long distances and the thorns (*duri*) of the plants. Syamsul remembers a difficult activity. "It's tough, I followed my parents before only one week, it's hard, going up hill, carrying *rotan* is very heavy" (interview with Syamsul). My respondents, in their appreciation of gathering rattan, never mention the pleasure of being in the forest, in a cooler environment. Remuneration is also not attractive, or insufficient to compensate the hardship.

Kamaruddin sometimes cuts the rattan but did not do so during my stay. He explains me he looks for rattan when he has time, not necessarily when he needs money. Zubaidah, whose husband was a part-time employee in an oil palm plantation, began cutting rattan when he lost his job. "There is no choice. When you cannot do [anything else], go to the forest and collect rattan²⁵" (interview with Zubaidah). They have about fifty rubber trees which are not enough to ensure a proper income, she says she prefers planting rubber and regrets not having more land. Qalesya and her husband claim to own some trees but this point is not clear, as others in the village accuse her husband of being too lazy to cultivate the land he inherited (and which he sold in part to his sister). They are the poorest household I met.

Fatimah and Nasrul own land which is planted with rubber, but more than half of the trees are growing and are not producing enough. Nasrul explains their situation: "[When you] cannot do an other work, look for rattan²⁶" and express a strong preference for agricultural work on his land: "We don't go too far, it is more pleasant.²⁷" Gathering rattan also makes longer working days and they both enjoy working only in the morning: "If we collect rattan, [we leave] for the day, if we collect rubber, we come home at 12²⁸" (interview with Fatimah and Nasrul).

Ahmad and Zarina also have land but their trees are not yet in production. These last two couples are known in the village to be good rattan gatherers but despite this they invest in other activities. This choice, as well as the slightly feminised work on rattan, makes me assume that it is a complementary or last resort activity. It is not demeaning to have to cut the rattan, it is the physical difficulty that makes it less attractive. When the villagers express preferences, it is

23 "Cari rotan susah."

24 "Kita Asli susah pencarian."

25 "Tak ada pilihan. Kalau tak boleh, masuk hutan cari rotan."

26 "Tak boleh kerja lain, cari rotan."

27 "Tak jalan jauh jauh, lebih senang."

28 "Kalau kita cari rotan, satu hari, kalau menoreh getah, [jam] 12 balik."

always for another activity than rattan, especially for the rubber agriculture, which is the main activity of the village.

5.2. Rubber Agriculture

Hevea brasiliensis, whose cultivation occupies an important part of the Jakun of Kampung Peta, is a plant native to the Amazon basin, introduced to Southeast Asia by Henry A. Wickham in the 1870s. The discovery of the elastic properties of latex in 1839, the invention of vulcanization in 1844, then the explosion of industrial needs (with the invention of tires in particular) gave rise to an economic boom in rubber at the end of the nineteenth century.

5.2.1. Introduction of Rubber Tree Cultivation in Malaysia

The first exploitation of trees took place, starting in the 1840s, in the Amazonian forest: the trees were bled by *seringeiros* workers who travelled for miles to slash the trees and collect their latex a few hours later (Dove 2002: 350 and 358, note 9). The same mobile gathering model is adopted in Congo to collect latex from the *Landolphia owariensis* liana. This is also the model for the exploitation of the indigenous latex of the peninsula, which is attested to in the Endau Basin by Logan in 1847 for *taban*, a variety of latex from the *Palaquium gutta* or *Palaquium oxleyanum* tree.

At the period of my visit nearly every man in the country was searching for taban (to which the name of gittáh perchá, a gum yielded by a different tree, is erroneously applied by Europeans). This tree is one of the most common in the forest of Johore. (...) The Binua after felling the tree make an incision quite round it from which the mik flows. This is repeated at distances of 6 to 18 inches along the whole trunk. (...) I asked both Malays and Binuas in different parts of the country whether they could not procure it without destroying the tree in the same way as they collect mínía dammer. But the answer always was that the tábán would not run like dammer and many other gittás such as the caoutchouc. (Logan 1847 : 262)

The gathering and trade of native latex intensified in the second half of the century.

A major element in this region's ancient trade in forest products was plant

"exudates", including gums, hard and soft resins, and latexes. Driven by the new demands of the industrializing societies during the latter half of the nineteenth century, there were minor booms in the trade for these indigenous South-East Asian latexes. (Dove 2002 : 350)

The introduction of the *Hevea brasiliensis* into Southeast Asia resulted in a change in the ecology of the tree as it was then cultivated. At the time of my stay the only latex sold in Kampung Peta came from rubber cultivation. In the texts available to us on the Jakun of the Endau basin, this production did not appear until the ethnography of Maeda in the 1960s. The latter notes that "small holdings of rubber were introduced by the government years ago" (Maeda 2001: 40), which may suggest that this was the first time that the Jakun cultivated rubber. This introduction in the early years of independence is fairly consistent with the history of rubber in the British Malaya, where the authorities' efforts to develop this production on independent smallholdings only date back to the 1950s (Cho 1982: 204) after decades of competition between smallholdings and estates. "The transfer of *Hevea* to South-East Asia was so successful that whereas South-East Asia produced just 1% of the world's rubber in 1906, it produced 75% just 15 years later" (Dove 2002: 350). During the first decades of the twentieth century, rubber was grown on the large estates under Western landownership and colonial authorities implemented regulations such as the Stevenson Plan to restrict the access of small local producers (cultivating less than 10 ha and mostly Malaysian) to the world market.

The Stevenson Scheme, attempted to maintain high prices for rubber on the international market by restricting the amount of rubber that could be sold by producers, in particular smallholders. (...) [It] was in effect from 1922 to 1928. (Dove 1996 : 39)

An "international agreement for the regulation of latex" followed in 1934, "[designed] in theory to stabilize world rubber prices by limiting production through taxation, sales quotas, prohibition of planting, and even in some cases the felling of planted trees" (Dove 1996: 39) but which in practice allowed unfair marketing conditions to be imposed on small producers to the benefit of estates. In spite of this, small producers engage in rubber cultivation in a substantial way. In 1921, they were already cultivating 167.000 ha for 33% of the area planted to rubber in four states (Ghee 1974: 108) and their market share has been increasing ever since. In 2016 in Malaysia, they are cultivating one million hectares against 77.000 hectares that are cultivated in

plantations (Lembaga Getah Malaysia 2018: 7).

Rubber cultivation is carried out differently on estates and in smallholdings.

The plantation sector (especially in the British colonies; Cramer 1956:286) spaced their trees widely and clean-weeded their estates in the hope that this would maximise production and minimise the threat from pests and disease, especially root disease [*Rigidoporus microporus* and *Phellinus noxius*]. In contrast, the smallholders planted their rubber two or three times as densely (Bauer 1948: 56; Cramer 1956: 305) and they permitted natural secondary growth to spring up among the rubber trees during periods of non-tapping; and even during tapping they only lightly cut back this growth. (Dove 2002 : 352)

The dense planting on deliberately limited plots detailed by Michael Dove in Borneo, alongside food crops on which farmers retreat as soon as latex prices fall, differs from the cultivation method of Malay farmers on the peninsula described by Mathieu Guérin, where rubber trees are planted in agroforestry, amidst food crops (personal communication). The two methods have in common less dependence on the market and less vulnerability of the peasant economy in the event of disease.

5.2.2. Rubber Agriculture in Kampung Peta

After the trial around 1960 mentioned by Maeda, rubber cultivation was again introduced in Kampung Peta in 1990 (interview with Syamsul) and new plantations are regularly made. Fatimah and Nasrul, for example, have 600 growing trees, Hatiqah has 100 which should yield in three years. This is also the case for Ahmad and Zarina. Balqis, a 30-year-old woman who harvests latex from land that is not hers, was during my stay clearing a plot with her husband to plant rubber trees (see photo 11 on the next page). "Dulu Orang Asli potong rotan hari-hari, dia naik gunung, sekarang potong getah," says Saifuddin, whose main activity is latex: "Pendapatan carian harian kita kerja hari-hari, itu memang getah" (interview with Saifuddin). Out of just over 80 *kelamin*, 38 depend entirely or partly on rubber cultivation. Among the people I interviewed is the same proportion of rubber farmers.

Photo 11. Balqis (pictured) and her husband clearing a plot of land.
Photo A. Vidal, March-April 2019.

Gomes describes the work of the rubber tree in a Semai village in which rubber cultivation represents less than 1% of the income but is nevertheless present.

The villagers told me that rubber tapping was an easy but tedious task. Its alleged monotony would partly explain its unpopularity among the people who clearly seem to prefer variety in their production. In a typical day of rubber tapping, the tapper would leave home at about 6:30 or 7:00 in the morning for his or her trees. For each tree, an incision would be made on the bark to draw out the latex. The latex would be collected in a cup placed beneath the incisions. I have observed that it would take a rubber tapper about thirty minutes to tap 10 trees. The trees would be left for approximately one hour to bleed out latex to fill the cup during which time the tapper might engage with some other activity, usually petai collecting. The tapper would then return to the trees to collect the latex in buckets that would be carried to the location of the rubber roller or presses. (Gomes 2004 : 63)

The villagers have between 50 trees (Zubaidah) and 400 trees (Fatimah, Iman, Saifuddin). Fatimah and Nasrul planted 600 more. Their monthly income varies between RM 200 (Zubaidah for 50 trees) and 600 (Kamaruddin and Hatiqah for 300 trees each), or between RM 1 and 4 per tree, which may be due to the assiduity with which the latex is harvested. The earlier this activity is conducted in the morning, the better the harvest (Nobuta 2009: 155). Prices during my stay

were RM 2.50 per kilo for pressed and dried latex (*kering*) (according to Iman) and for wet latex (*basah*) "the price of rubber felled. Now RM 2.20 per kg. Sometimes 2.20, sometimes 2.80"²⁹ (interview with Saifuddin).

All the rubber farmers I interviewed complain about low prices ("Getah sangat murah", Iman) or have a very meagre income due to the fact that their plantations are not yet producing. It takes between six and ten years for a rubber tree to produce latex, which is a long latency period for households that live from day to day. During my stay, latex was not harvested because of seasonal leaf fall (*musim luruh*). "Here we haven't sold anything for three months now [April 9, 2019], there are no leaves, we cannot collect rubber"³⁰ (Saifuddin). But his work continues: "We still work at weeding, work here and there but we don't earn money."³¹ "If there are no leaves, we cannot collect rubber, we have to find another work. If we do not, we collect rattan,"³² says Fatimah, who explains her shift to rattan. The return on investment over a long period of time, unstable market prices, the seasonal loss of income, and the meagre income due to the small areas of land available to the villagers, all this makes rubber agriculture as it is practised in Kampung Peta a rather unsatisfactory activity. Fatimah and Nasrul also note that their young trees are vulnerable to animal intrusion, something that in the 1960s had cut down rubber plantations. At night they sleep in a hut (*pondok*) in their plantation (*kebun*) but they lost ten trees³³ (interview with Fatimah and Nasrul) a few days before our interview. I have seen broken saplings in other parts of the village during my stay, and these are the most serious damage that elephants do according to the villagers.

We have seen that rubber growing is a more attractive source of income than rattan collection, because it is less strenuous and more sedentary. This is what Saifuddin says, but it is a very relative preference.

People work in rattan, not because they like it, but because they have an interest in it, it's to make a living. When there is no money, you have to look for it, you have to work. They don't like rubber either, because there are mosquitoes, but you have to earn money, you have to work for food. Nobody likes that³⁴. (interview with

29 "Harga getah jatuh, turun. Sekarang RM 2.20 sekilo. Kadang 2.20, kadang 2,80."

30 "Kita sekarang sini sudah tiga bulan tak jual, tak ada daun, tak boleh menoreh."

31 "Kerjapun bersihkan, buat itu, buat ini, tapi tak dapat duit."

32 "Tak ada daun, tak boleh menoreh, baru kerja lain. Tak boleh kerja lain, cari rotan."

33 "Sepuluh pokok getah gajah habiskan."

34 "Orang kerja rotan, bukan kerana dia tak suka tapi kerana kita minat, itu kerja cari duit. Sudah tak ada duit,

Rampuyan)

In Kampung Peta, in contrast to the Malaysian smallholder techniques of the beginning of the last century, the trees are spaced at a density that seems to me to be close to the average found in Malaysia "between 445 and 535 trees per hectare" (Mohd Napi *et al.* 1987: 142). Farmers continuously clear the vegetation between the trees and, as we have seen, food crops are too insufficient to ensure food security for the inhabitants, thus increasing their dependence on rubber cultivation.

When asked about the possibility of improving their living conditions, some villagers express a desire for more land, such as Zubaidah, who has an insufficient plot of land. Others compare it with more remunerative activities such as tourism. I have not heard any comments that question the farming methods and very few about the possibility of adopting other crops that are more attractively priced or better adapted to the constraints of farming in Kampung Peta. However, other agricultural choices are possible. For example, Saifuddin recalls the culture that prevailed before the choice of rubber tree: "Before we planted many durian trees. As we could not sell them, we planted rubber tree."³⁵

5.3. Other Cash Crops

5.3.1. Cultivation and Trade in Durian and Other Seasonal Fruits

Alberto G. Gomes worked on the transition in the early 1980s in a village from a subsistence economy (where people look for the necessities of life in kind: *cari makan*) to a market economy (where people look for money: *cari duit*). The village in question derives 90% of its income from durian (and to a lesser extent *petai*) cultivation. Durian, *Durio zibethinus*, is a large fruit (usually up to 5 kg) with a striking smell and taste, much appreciated by the Malaysians and relatively expensive, from RM 25/kg to the final consumer, sometimes more for varieties and regions that are particularly appreciated.

Like other Orang Asli in Malaysia, the Jakun have marked the landscape with their presence

mesti cari, mesti kerja. Getahpun tak suka sebab banyak nyamuk tapi cari duit, kita kerja, cari makan. Tak ada seseorang yang suka."

35 "Dulu kita tanam durian banyak. Bila tak boleh jual, kita tanam getah."

through the planting of fruit trees, especially durians. The map prepared by the villagers of Kampung Peta to demonstrate their ancient presence in the reserve and beyond takes care to note the presence of durians along the river, in front of and upstream from the park (see Map 8). Pak Liman, an informant of Colin Nicholas in 1999, wants them to be understood as evidence of the historical settlement of the Jakun.

Who said the durians were planted by elephants? If elephants planted the durians, why is it that on the road to Kahang, where there are always lots of elephants, there is no durian anywhere?³⁶ (Nicholas 1999 : 2)

As in the rest of Peninsular Malaysia, the durian season takes place in Kampung Peta in July and August but January also brings some fruit. The villagers have more seasonal fruit trees than plants that produce continuously and this sudden abundance gives them the opportunity to sell the surplus during July and August: the villagers cannot eat everything, neither can the animals and the quantities are large enough for the traders to make the effort to come such a long way.

The six households studied by Gomes own between 10 and 50 trees and derive almost all of their annual income from them over a period of two months, an income that varies from year to year due to more or less successful harvests. The farmers of Kampung Peta are more involved in rubber farming but still own some durians. Saifuddin has five trees and estimates the ratio at RM500 per tree per season, at RM 5/kg, i.e. the price at which traders come to the village to buy them. He notes in early April that the season is promising as there are many flowers on the trees. "Now we could sell but there are not trees anymore,³⁷" he says. Shanthi Thambiah notes in 1999 different situations between the three Jakun villages he investigated. In two *kampung* the villagers consume all the fruit they produce and only in Kampung Peta are surplus durians available. They are sold to Chinese merchants who travel to the village (Thambiah 1999: 278). Many respondents did not spontaneously tell me about their income from fruit trees, and I have little data on this, but I have met people in situations as varied as between Kampung Peta and other villages. Syazwan, a man of about 30 years old who works in tourism, owns a jackfruit tree (*nangka*), a mangosteen tree (*manggis*), a durian tree and sells these last two fruits for RM 300/year. He consumes a large part of his harvest and earns only an anecdotal income from it. Hatiqah also has a rambutan tree in addition to jackfruit, mangosteen and durian but she does not

36 "Siapa kata pokok durian itu gajah yang tanam? Kalau gajah yang tanam, kenapa di jalan pergi ke Kahang, ada banyak gajah selalu lalu, tapi mana ada pokok durian?"

37 "Sekarang boleh jual tapi pokok sudah habis."

produce enough to sell, she has many small children and seems to consume it all. Fatimah and Nasrul have three durian trees in production and three that are still too young. Durian is one of their sources of income, which should bring them RM 1,500 each summer. When investing in a new plantation, they choose rubber but do not forget to plant a few durians.

5.3.2. Oil Palm and Agricultural Prospects

Only one *kelamin* in the village grows oil palm, along with rubber. This plant could have been more present in the village since there was talk of growing it in 1997.

A Chinese businessman from Kluang by the name of Ah Tee had proposed to the Jakun of Kampung Peta that oil palm be grown on their 350 acres (141.6 hectares) on a joint-venture basis with him. He offered RM 3000 up front per family plus 37% of the proceeds from the yield. The Jakun agreed to this arrangement. (...) In exchange for the timber in the said area, which was valued at RM 3 million, the cooperative would give each family a house, some land for an orchard and plant oil palm for them, the total cost of which was estimated at RM 2 million. However, as it turned out, when the logs were removed, the cooperative was not to be heard from again. Neither were the houses, orchards or oil palm smallholdings delivered. All they received thus far was RM700 worth of shares in the cooperative for each eligible applicant. (Nicholas 1999 : 9)

This plot was never used after it was felled and twenty years later a secondary forest (*belukar*) grew back. The land is quite steep but the project to plant it with oil palm appeared realistic and other trees such as durian are fit to this landscape. There has never been any spontaneous mention of oil palm in my dealings with the inhabitants, except in connection with large plantations that employ a few men from the village. In 2014, 15% of the areas planted with oil palm belonged to small independent producers and 23% to small producers engaged in FELDA-type schemes (Rosniza *et al.* 2018: 70).

The villagers are looking for other options. A few years ago, Asma planted 160 robusta coffee trees and 60 vanilla trees, which she is still waiting for them to bring fruit. The reasons for her choice are the high prices of these two plants on the Malaysian market (where robusta, a variety that makes a very black liquor, sells well) as well as the lack of taste for them from animals,

which are not likely to destroy them. It seems that the tree she has chosen to carry the vanilla pods and give them shade, a kind of *Fabacea*, is harmful to the development of the orchid and that her project is threatened.

The villagers are engaged in an Indigenous Community Conservation Area (ICCA) project with the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). The second small grant they have received in this framework is devoted to the search for more interesting cash crops than those in which they have been engaged in recent decades. Lee Shin-Shin, who runs this small grant programme in Putrajaya, consults with local people and tries to find advice and training for them. She recalls the main perspectives that have been considered.

Those plants that they want, lemongrass, chili, my concern is where is the market? We don't want to do it in a rush. Once they planted cocoa and chopped it all down because no one was buying. Same thing for the chili, if they produce 100 and sell only 10 they would just let it rot. (...) If we sell fresh chili, it might be have certain limitations. They thought about lemongrass because it lasts longer but it has very low price. Coffee, I talked with someone, they would make it but they need bigger amounts. (interview with Lee Shin-Shin, 24 April 2019)

The villagers have not yet found crops adapted to their agricultural constraints: farm size, labour, relative distance from the market, animal intrusions. The income they earn from rattan collection and rubber tree cultivation, compared to that from salaried jobs or service jobs, remains very meagre: it takes one *kelamin* to try to reach RM1.000 per month with rattan or rubber tree, though it is hardly the income of one person employed full time. We therefore continue the comparison with activities in other sectors and salaried jobs in all sectors.

Chapter 6. Self-employment (Except Primary Sector) and Wage Employment

Apart from rattan and rubber tree, which offer the most accessible income in Kampung Peta, other activities allow the villagers to earn a living, either through self-employment or salaried work. Retail trade and handicrafts are the main forms of self-employment. The majority of wage employment is in the public sector and other opportunities for the villagers exist outside the village. Income from tourism, regardless of the form of employment, will only be discussed in the next chapter.

6.1. Retail Trade and Handicraft

6.1.1. Retail Trade

In the Endau Basin in the 1960s, two households were engaged in retail trade and both were mixed couples whose wives were Orang Asli and husbands Chinese. "Unlike these Chinese, Orang Hulu men would not dare to make a profit just for the 'transmission' of goods" (Maeda 2001: 50). No Jakun couple then traded in the area and these "village shopkeepers are in competition both with the Chinese merchants in the town and also with a Malay peddler who visits the villages on occasion" (Maeda 2001: 50). Maeda recounts the conflict that has developed between the people of the village and one of these grocers,

regarded as a cheat and (...) the object of animosity because he takes money from the people in the community in the same way as retailers in town, although his profit is actually very minimal. The owner is an old Chinese who has lived in the forest like an ordinary Orang Hulu for more than twenty years. (Maeda 2001 : 83)

What is acceptable from a Chinese trader is not acceptable from a person who is part of the community and is expected to adopt local customs of "redistributing the gains to his fellows" (Maeda 2001: 83). The cultural difficulty for the Jakun to engage in trade seems to have diminished in the 1990s, according to Shanthi Thambiah's survey. She observes that

There are (...) three households in Kampung Peta which have grocery shops in the settlements. The shops are predominantly run by females in the household, a wife or a female child. The goods for sale are usually bought by men from the nearby town. (Thambiah 1999 : 279)

Photo 12. Rabiah in her shop. On the right, the price list on the fridge; on the left a sign indicates that the credit is limited to RM 50. Photo A. Vidal, March-April 2019.

During my stay there are five grocery stores in the village, all run by Jakun, and to my knowledge two that have recently closed (those of Iman and Hatiqah, which went bankrupt after a difficult year in 2018 for the whole village). It was impossible for me to access the people who ran these grocery stores, they refused to meet me for reasons I don't know: did they not want to let me know their income or did they associate me with the family that welcomed me, to whom they didn't want to do any favours? I was only able to interview Rabiah, whose business was very new at the time, but I could see that no grocery store was the only income for a *kelamin*. Some couples also have rubber plots or part-time jobs and a couple of shop owners are even both full-time employees. Rabiah, who has no other activity than her grocery store, receives an allowance from JAKIM (the department for the advancement of Islam) to compensate for her disability since she has neurological problems.

She opened this grocery store in November 2018 with the help of her brother, who gave her the use of a *pondok* on the side of the road, near his house which is quite far from the village and from her residence (see photo 12 on the previous page). She managed to be a beneficiary of RM 98 in February but lost between RM 200 and 400 the other months at the beginning of 2019. This

is partly due to the fact that she is still increasing her stock and partly to the low margins she practices, which I estimate at 10% of the purchase price based on a few examples she gives me. While other grocery stores are selling RM 5 a gallon of fuel, she is giving it away for 4.50 cents. She sells for less than others and buys the goods for more. Unlike other grocery stores that buy in Kahang or further away, she buys from Jeffrey, a Chinese-Malaysian itinerant trader who comes to the village twice a week in a yellow truck (*lori kuning*) and offers goods that are already more expensive, less varied and less fresh than in the city. So she offers no better choice than this one and, as well as the other grocers in the village, she does not benefit from wholesale prices.

Photo 13. The villagers get their supplies from Jeffrey's yellow truck.
Photo A. Vidal, March-April 2019.

Some villagers buy their supplies from the "yellow truck" (see photo 13 above), while others go to Kahang, where there are small, well-stocked and cheaper shops, or to Kluang or Mersing, where supermarkets offer even more competitive prices. The journey to Kahang is estimated at RM 50, that to Kluang at RM 100, but opportunities to go out of the village exist (Thursday afternoon market in Kahang, children returning from boarding school near Mersing every other weekend) and it is possible to take advantage of this to do some shopping. Fatimah and Nasrul say they spend RM 300 per month on food (*barang dapur*) when they manage to share a trip to the city or RM 400 when they are obliged to do their shopping in the village. Traders from outside the village, whether they are located elsewhere or are itinerant, benefit most of the Jakun's purchases, and local grocery stores are only used to meet one-off and immediate needs. So one will find there mainly snacks and cold drinks, a little bit of the essentials for cooking (dried anchovies, shallots and garlic, dried noodles, rice) and eggs, the freshness of which is

never guaranteed. These low sales figures make it an additional activity for the Jakun entrepreneurs, and in Tina's case, even an occupation. A final, more original business is run by Fatin, a woman of almost 40 years old, and her husband Suhail, a 50-year-old man who has a good income outside the village. Their shop only sells sodas, served in disposable plastic glasses with lots of ice cubes (see photo 14 below). At RM 1 per glass, they earn up to RM 500 per month when it is hot. Their *kedai oren* (orange soda shop) has perhaps the best return on investment in the village.

Photo 14. *Kedai oren*, the orange soda shop run by Suhail (inside in the foreground) and Fatin (behind him). Photo A. Vidal, March-April 2019.

6.1.2. Handicraft

Maeda notes in the 1960s that "handicrafts made by the Orang Hulu are of poor quality and have little market value, except in the village" (Maeda 2001: 51). The handicrafts then simply meet people's needs for useful objects, and if they are exchanged, it is within the village setting: "Pillows and pandanus mats are made at home" (Maeda 2001: 60). "Before, everyone made their own objects³⁸" explains Syazwani, a woman in her early 50s who produces handicrafts. Other forms of handicrafts, such as metal forging, had been observed in the late nineteenth century.

The natives manufacture spear-heads, and other iron articles. They obtain the iron from Malay or Chinese traders and work it up for themselves, and supply the other settlements on the Indau and its tributaries. The forge used by the Jakuns is very simple in its construction. (Lake et Kelsall 1894 : 3)

38 "Dulu semua orang buat sendiri."

This craft had already disappeared at the time of Maeda's investigation. Thambiah does not report the existence of any local production and in Colin Nicholas' report in 1999, handicrafts appeared as an activity likely to accompany the tourist development of Kampung Peta, given the number of tourists passing through the village. It concerns then objects that are more decorative than useful.

Photo 15. Basketry by Hatiqah. Photo A. Vidal, March-April 2019.

Twenty years later, there are no stalls where craft makers can sell their products, but tourists can buy them at home, according to the goodwill of the tourist guides. Ahmad, for example, is taking advantage of his inclusion in the village's tourist offer³⁹ to sell traditional puzzle games that he makes from bamboo, using machines for which JAKOA has granted him a subsidy. Hatiqah and her husband make the same puzzles, but out of wood, as well as baskets (*bakul*) and mats (*tikar*) (see photo 15 on previous page). She estimates that she sells RM 300 worth of handicrafts a year, which seems small in relation to the time she spends on them. Syazwani, who shares with Hatiqah the characteristic of having a husband employed in the national park (Taman Negara), earns up to RM 300 per month with a more diversified production. She also makes pandan pouches (*Pandanus sp.*) and miniature versions of traditional objects (a rice winnowing basket) for tourists. She learned the craft from her grandmother but now invents her own designs. Both use the raw material they find in the forest or village, *pandan* and various kinds of rattan. Hatiqah earns a better living from rubber trees, but "prefers handicrafts, which she finds more

39 Ahmad gives blowpipe demonstrations to tourists and shows the animal traps he makes on traditional models or invents.

enjoyable⁴⁰" (interview with Hatiqah). However, this activity is not well valued. The other villagers do not constitute a market since they now buy plastic objects (*tikar* and *tudung makanan* or dish covers) at a lower cost (interview with Syazwani). A small⁴¹ *tikar* costs RM 75. Before my visit to Syazwani, its last customer was a teacher from the village school who had bought three of them, perhaps to resell them or give them away outside the village.

Munirah, a 20-year-old woman, sister of Asma and Iman, studied handicrafts for three years in Kuala Lumpur with other Malay and indigenous students. She is specialized in making rattan furniture. Her family would like to see her stay in Kampung Peta, but she dreams instead of moving to the city and is not looking to start her own business or to find opportunities. Is it laziness (in her family it is suggested that she is lazy, *malas*), the refusal to settle in the village or a certain realism? Tourists are more interested in *pandan* pouches than rattan armchairs. Colin Nicholas, the anthropologist who runs the Centre for Orang Asli Concerns, and Reita Rahim, a Malaysian who is in charge of the NGO Gerai OA (Orang Asli), buy some of the local production to market it in the rest of the country. Gerai OA accompanies indigenous women to help them prize their knowledge and regain economic independence in a context where, as we shall see, their work is less remunerated than that of men. In 2018, this NGO enabled the women of Kampung Peta to discover the Tompoq Topoh Mah Meri Women's Initiative in Selangor, to visit the National Craft Expo in Kuala Lumpur or to learn how to dye the *pandan* leaf during a workshop in their village. But this commitment is limited: "[Kampung Peta is] part of our network but as they already have a reliable tourism network, we only give them support services" (interview with Reita Rahim). External support is limited and Syamsul village has plans to set up a craft shop for tourists, but this was already being discussed twenty years ago (Nicholas 1999: 24) and nothing has been done. We will return to this in the next chapter, about how the tourist windfall is captured.

Another handicraft activity is aimed (at least in part) at the inhabitants of the village, that of Fatin and a daughter of Ahmad and Zarina. They both have a sewing machine and do small sewing jobs for a fee. Fatin sews gaiters for the leeches that Saifuddin, whose child is self-employed in tourism, orders from her in exchange for fabric for RM 3 per pair. These gaiters are sold between RM 15 and 20 depending on the nationality of the tourists, who are the most solvent (and in this case captive) market in the village. However, even in this case, this market is

40 "Yang lebih suka, kraf tangan, senang dari noreh getah."

41 Tikars are nowadays used as a table at mealtimes, but they were also used as bedding and their size depends on the number of people likely to sleep on them. A small *tikar* is therefore 70 to 90 cm wide.

not exploited as it could be, and tourists sometimes go into the forest poorly equipped without having been offered such a purchase. We will try to understand why this manna is not as well exploited as it could be in terms of tourist employment, but we can already see that the villagers do not benefit as much as they could from the presence of tourists on the spot to sell the local production.

All these activities have the disadvantage for the villagers of being *makal*, fluctuating and not bringing a stable income. For many respondents, the prospect of having a permanent job that pays consistently is a more valuable prospect than their current situation.

6.2. Employment Except Tourism

The Jakun's interest in constant income jobs is not new and has been documented as far back as the 1960s.

Wage earners, especially those with monthly salaries, are envied, simply because they have regular cash incomes. This distribution among Orang Hulu between those with a fixed, predictable income and those whose finances are precarious and unstable seems to be important. But, paradoxically, there appears to be little special desire or competition for these contract jobs because (...) the Orang Hulu claim not to like working under another man's control. (Maeda 2001 : 48)

This lack of taste for the unequal relationship in the employment contract is quite marked and seems to have more to do with a well-established cultural trait than with circumstances such as the harshness of the exploitation or the low level of remuneration.

[Wage labor] is a work of *numpang* (to be a passenger) on another's enterprise, not one's own. Orang Hulu prefer to be collectors in the forest than wage laborers because they believe as collectors, as long as they stay out of debts, they will not be compelled to do regular or constant work. On the whole, they tend to think of themselves as free from bondage. (Maeda 2001 : 43)

Wage employment was almost non-existent in the 1960s in Kampung Peta. Thirty years later, Shanthi Thambiah notes that of the hundred or so adults living in the village at that time, five

men were employed by the Taman Negara, three men by a logging company, two men on a plantation, one woman by JHEOA at the nursery school, making a total of only eleven people. She does not report any refusal in principle and notes that the majority of these jobs are held by men, topic on which we will come back to later.

The traditionally expressed reluctance to be dependent on an employer never really appeared in the interviews I conducted in 2019, any moral reluctance disappearing behind assessments of job quality and its low appreciation by employees.

6.2.2. Public Sector Employment

Many people in the village dream of a stable job and income. A few have access to it. Most of them work in the public sector, especially in schools. Two men and two women are employed at SK Primary School for maintenance jobs. At the kindergarten (*tadika, tabika*) two Jakun women, a maintenance woman and a teacher are employed by the Ministry of Rural Affairs. The latter, Umairah, is the only teacher in the village who is not ill at ease. She earns RM 1,050 a month for 35 hours a week, or €220, which is not much for someone who has completed higher education like her. Nevertheless, she is pleased to have been able to return to the village because her position should regularly be opened to transfers. Two other people, a man and a woman, work for the public service in functions that I have not identified, and two others are employed in the public service but outside the village. The Jakun of Kampung Peta, especially if they are educated, do have some prospects for public employment but these are less rare if they accept to their place of residence. Even if civil servants, often Malay, come to work in the village (as commuters, leaving every night or every weekend), places are scarce for the Jakun.

The private sector offers fairly similar remuneration. Five men and one woman work for the oil palm plantations on the road to Kahang, beyond the forest reserve. Only one man is full-time, the others are part-time like Omar. He works six hours a day, six days a week, or 36 hours a week for RM 1,100, a working time and amount very close to full time and the Malaysian minimum wage. Three months earlier he was full-time but was forced to work fewer hours.

The Wildlife Conservation Society, a U.S. NGO, is also a significant employer. Two men from Kampung Peta are employed there but only intermittently reside in the village. Saiful, a 25-year-old man also employed by WCS, resides in Kahang and works throughout northern Johor state. Without a degree but knowing the forest very well, he does fieldwork and takes up cameras to

monitor the large fauna. He earns RM 50 per day and chooses his working hours, which makes his monthly salary vary between RM 1,150 (for 23 days) and 1,500 (for 30 days) according to his wishes. He likes his work and calls himself a diligent worker (*rajin*), so he takes few days off. Saiful does not have a work contract but has access to his employer's pension fund and is entitled to a three-day sickness insurance, which only covers incidents such as returning from the field with a fever. He notes that his employer practices some discrimination since the Orang Asli are the only employees in the field, with modest salaries, while in management positions there are only Malaysians, under contract and earning up to RM 2,000. "They have a good job,"⁴² he says (interview with Saiful). These jobs, which are of lesser quality in the Malaysian context, are nevertheless the best paid jobs in the village community.

Fatin's husband, Suhail, also resides in Kahang. A Chinese vegetable trader employs him to drive a truck between Kulai (Johor) and Kuala Rompin (Pahang). Suhail comes from another Jakun village far from the forest. He tells me that he had no choice but to live far from the village and come back on weekends. He is paid RM 2,000, which is the highest remuneration I have ever noted in Kampung Peta (excluding income from self-employment tourism), although he has to deduct the RM 300 rent he pays in town.

Whether in the public or private sector, employment opportunities are poor in Kampung Peta and leaving is the solution for some young people in the village, like Saiful and others I have not been able to meet. "There are also those who leave, they don't have land, they don't have a job, they will look for a job outside the village"⁴³ (interview with Kamaruddin). Many of the people I met who are in their twenties want to stay in the village or come back often, saying they are very attached to it, like Saiful, Syamsul or Asma. Zubaidah would like to leave for the only reason that she does not earn a good living, but her parents are the only ones left in Kampung Peta. To my knowledge, only Munirah is also attracted by the urban lifestyle and not just repelled by the village's poor economic opportunities.

6.3. Other Sources of Income

The village of Kampung Peta receives various private and public aid. The children of SK are offered school material or uniforms by the works of the firm Mitsubishi. Those of boarding age

42 "Dia kerja senang."

43 "Ada juga yang keluar, tak ada tanah, tak ada pekerjaan, cari kerja di luar."

near Mersing come back every two weeks at great expense and JAKOA contributes to the transport costs up to RM 100 per month, in addition to help with textbooks, uniforms and soap (interview with Qalesya). Gerai OA activities like those of the ICCA programme operate thanks to small scholarships, granted by UNDP or charitable organizations. These grants and programmes are specifically targeted at indigenous communities.

No one I know of receives the *Kebajikan Masyarakat*, an aid of about RM 300 granted without distinction of ethnicity to elderly people who have no family support. Neither Syazrina nor Hatiqah are eligible because they have many children and grandchildren to help them. Because of her disability, Rabiah receives a grant of RM 450 which, she says, only concerns Muslim Malaysians.

In the income of the Jakun of Kampung Peta should also be noted the importance of gambling, often expense, sometimes income.

The women play a game called *Jiki* which was first introduced into the community by Chinese tin miners at Sungai Kencim during the Japanese occupation. This game is played predominantly by the women while the men play *Mahjong*. (Thambiah 1999 : 288)

During my stay, while women played *ceki* often (transcribed by Maeda as *chiki*, 2001: 61), sometimes with men, men no longer played *mahjong* with each other or much less often. Money at stake in *ceki* can be as high as RM 50 on a Saturday afternoon (the second day of the weekend in some Malaysian states such as Johor), but since the money circulates within the community it is never won or lost. It is likely, however, that some of the money the Jakun play for the *nombor* is lost. It is a game of chance in which several times a week the villagers play four numbers and which Nobuta describes in his book on a Temuan village.

Most of the men set off for Pertang on the days (Wednesday, Saturday, Sunday) when you can purchase a ticket in the four-numbered lottery called “number” (*nombor*), which the villagers think of as gambling (*main judi*). (Nobuta 2009 : 104)

An emissary on a scooter comes to Kampung Peta, stopping at each house, to collect the bets and the four numbers played by each other, which he writes down on carbon paper or in a portable

machine that issues a ticket. Most often, the wager is lost to gambling entrepreneurs outside the village, but sometimes villagers win considerable sums of money. For example, Kamaruddin was able to make an investment when he made a large win, and his nephew Muhamad once bought a scooter after winning a comfortable sum (interview with Syazrina). His sister Iman invested a first gain in the construction of her house (RM 10,000) and after winning a second time was able to open a grocery store which later went bankrupt (interview with Iman). I was also told that it is customary for *nombor* winners to have a good party and to feed the whole village.

The most important support that helps people cope with difficulties is family support. Children of working age give RM 50, 100 or more to their families for the schooling of younger children or for old parents without income. Hatiqah receives RM 50 from her two sons when they can afford it, Iman gives RM 100 to her mother for her 11-year-old sister, Hatiqah receives RM 200 from her grandson for the maintenance of the rest of the family, including the two grandmothers. Zubaidah puts it this way: "When there is no food, we help each other in the village."⁴⁴

6.4. Moral Order and Technical Order

Maeda calls "moral order" and "technical order" the two registers in which the Jakun carry out the activities that enable them to earn a living. The first relates to subsistence activities in which the acquired goods must be shared to some extent. The second concerns goods of commercial value (even if they are the same goods, provided that they have a different circulation, as we have seen in the case of the wild boar) and money.

It is the shift between moral exchanges and technical ones that appears to be an indicator of the direction of change. As technical exchanges increase within the hamlet, and as Orang Hulu begin to take exchanges of this sort as a matter of course, the distinction between the "rich" and the "poor" in the hamlet, a distinction which is hardly noticed or even made at present, may become clarified. (Maeda 2001 : 62)

From rattan remuneration to salaried employment, the market economy is changing social structures, whether it is equality between women and men or solidarity in the village. In the 1960s, it was frowned upon to appropriate a margin on a commercial activity, but in the 1990s, Jakun are now commonly employed as grocers and this appropriation no longer seems

44 "Kalau tak ada makan, kampung tolong-tolong."

problematic, reflecting a major change in the circulation of wealth. The obligation to share no longer applies to all activities, it is reduced to the immediate family, to certain goods or certain income (such as the lottery, which owes nothing to work and everything to luck). Everyone's industry brings him or her an income that he or she is now free to keep for themselves or to share as they wish. To Zubaidah's irenic comment (see previous page), Asma says, "If you want something, you have to work because no one helps you, it's your responsibility⁴⁵" (interview with Zubaidah). These two visions of social relationships are clashing.

I chose to approach tourism activities separately for several reasons, the first being that it is the one that brings in the biggest income, hence contributing to the economic inequalities in the village. The employment at Taman Negara and at the structures that prefigured it also allow to compare two models of economic development. Finally, because it is about ecotourism, it is an issue that requires a certain cohesion of the village community and a common will to preserve the local environment as a common good even though the economic strategies have been strongly individualized.

45 "You must go to work if you want something because nobody helps you, you make the responsibility your home."

Chapter 7. Tourism Economy

The last economic activity that we study here is the most emblematic, the one that in Kampung Peta ensures the highest individual income. After describing the jobs that exist in tourism (and those that do not), we will look at the relationship between the village and Endau-Rompin National Park, its prefiguration with the Malaysian Nature Society and its current administration, as well as the Jakun's positive appreciation of the tourism industry and environmental conservation, two notions that their recent history has linked to each other.

7.1. Employment in Tourism

In the 1960s, guiding activities were unusual and did not concern mainly tourism.

Strangers – such as miners, timber searchers, and tourists – may sometimes hire an Orang Hulu as a guide. These casual and scanty earnings add little to the household income. (Maeda 2001 : 51)

The Jakun's knowledge of their environment is then valued by people who need to venture into the forest for utilitarian or recreational reasons, but tourism is still a marginal activity. In the 1960s, the federal government's first plan (1965-1970) did not provide any subsidies to develop tourism in Malaysia (Azizan 2010: 93) and the sector only gradually expanded: international tourist arrivals rose from 2.2 million in 1980 to 7.4 million in 1990 (Azizan 2010: 94) and in the 1990s they peaked at around 26 million. Per capita spending is growing and has doubled in the last twelve years, totalling RM 84 billion in 2018 (Malaysian Tourism Promotion Board 2019). In 2015, tourism was employing 2.5 million people in Malaysia, particularly in the retail trade, restaurants and hotels (Department of Statistics 2018a).

7.1.1. Employment in Taman Negara

In Kampung Peta tourist employment is distributed between permanent park employees, independent guides (*pribadi*) employed by the park on an intermittent basis and guides working for private agents or directly with the public.

Perbadanan Taman Negara (Johor) has employed 5 males from 5 households who are paid monthly. There are also 21 males and 3 females who are employed as guides and boat drivers for tourists who visit the park. They are paid daily and their services are only required when there are visits from tourists. (Thambiah 1999 : 278)

In 1999, out of 34 households in Kampung Peta, there are 29 people working in tourism. I counted 35 in 2019, spread over 29 households. So the proportion has decreased and in 2019 only half of the households in the village are involved in this activity. Seven people are full-time in Taman Negara and twelve part-time, employed in technical, logistical or administrative positions: cook, handyman, receptionist. Part-time employees such as Asma or her brother Muhamad are paid just over RM 700 for 23 working days per month at a rate of six hours per day, i.e. 138 h/month paid RM 5 each. Overtime is paid RM 3. Hatiqah's husband is employed full time in a job that his wife describes as "cleaning toilets" (*cuci tandas*). He earns RM 1,300 per month. With a maximum working week of 48 hours (Employment Act 1955, Part 12), his pay would be RM 6.5 per hour. Syazwani's husband earns RM 1,800 per month. The Orang Asli are the majority of the park's workforce, but in the most junior positions. The park's management justifies this lack of career development by their lack of qualifications but also their lack of experience: "Based on training and rules by government is same to Orang Asli and others staf. Education qualificate and experience is necessarily" (interview with the park management⁴⁶).

7.1.2. Different Statuses of Tourist Guides

The park also employs a contract labour force, mostly Jakun, to provide sightseeing tours and cooking for excursions (except in the case of Muslim excursionists, where the cooks are Malay). Contract workers are paid more for their work but their income is uncertain. Iman compares her income with that of her sister: "Asma earns 700 a month, I can earn 400 in three days. Her income is stable but low. 700 is too little, it's not enough."⁴⁷ The choice between the two is not easy and Iman later insists on the disadvantages of an unstable income.

If we work at the Taman Negara, we make money every month. If you are self-employed, sometimes you earn money every month but not during bad seasons like

46 The interview consisted in a series of short and poorly edited written answers to my questions. I had already addressed them during my stay to Encik Herman, director of the Taman Negara Endau Rompin Peta, who never found an occasion to meet me.

47 "Asma dapat 700 sahaja, saya 3 hari 400. Hers is stable but low. 700 terlalu sikit, tak cukup."

the rainy season. Many people in the village do this. If we are self-employed, sometimes we don't have any money. If there are a lot of tourists, we earn RM 1,000 per month, if there are no tourists we earn zero.⁴⁸ (interview with Iman)

Nine people are non-salaried guides (*pribadi*), some working for the park, others for private agents or on their own (two of them specialise in fishing tourism). For the same service (package, *pakej*) of three days and two nights on site ("3D2N"), the Taman Negara pays the guides for a single day at RM 130 (on days 1 and 3, visitors are left by themselves). He also pays RM 47 per person for three meals per day. In the private offer, that of a Chinese-Malaysian agent for whom Iman works, additional services (tubing down the river, demonstration of blowpipe and animal traps or cooking rice in bamboo) require the presence of a guide paid RM 100 for each of the three days. More meals are paid for. On a 3D2N package by person, Iman invests RM 100 in food and earns a RM 140 margin for her work, more than when she cooks for the park's clients. The workload is also different since the Taman Negara pays only one guide for groups of up to ten people and private agents work more with groups of Western tourists who are a couple, a family or a group of friends and rarely make more than four people.

The Taman Negara provides village guides with training courses in collaboration with the Johor Tourist Guide Association (Persatuan Pemandu Pelancong Bandar dan Alam Semulajadi Johor, JCNTGA) during which they learn as much about the environment as about transmitting this knowledge. The JCNTGA association has helped the villagers to enter the tourism business, notably through English courses. The president, a Muslim Indian-Malaysian man, believes that the result is a community of capable people. Even though many guides are not able to accompany an English-speaking public, the association's efforts have now been transferred to the other entrance to the park, that of Selai, whose inhabitants have even more skills to acquire (informal interview with the president of JCNTGA). Nevertheless, there are still many people in Kampung Peta in need of training, especially in English. Many guides work exclusively in Malay and would like to be called upon for tours with an international audience, which would allow them to work more often and earn more, but deplore their poor English or shyness (being *malu*). This is how Syamsul sums it up: "In Kampung Peta, they are smart but they don't have confidence in themselves, they are very shy⁴⁹" (don't dare to talk to people too different from

48 "Kerja Taman, kita akan dapat duit setiap bulan. Kerja sendiri, kadang kita dapat duit every month but if bad season like raining season, we can't get money. Lot of people in the village do that. If we kerja sendiri, sometimes no have money. If lots of tourists come here, we will get 1.000/month, if no tourist we get zero."

49 "In Kampung Peta, they very pandai but their level confidence, tak ada, they macam malu."

those around them).

7.1.3. Other Tourism Jobs

Others in the village would like to enter the tourism profession but the profession of guide seems inaccessible. Qalesya and her husband, on the day of the *tawkey rotan*, compare the hardship of their activity with the advantages of tourism, which are not within their reach: "It is difficult to obtain a tourist guide's licence⁵⁰" (Qalesya), "we are too stupid⁵¹" (Ismail). Zubaidah would like to work in tourism as a guide: "I can do it, I want to, but I don't know how to communicate, when [Aude] speaks I understand but I don't know how to speak well.⁵² "Places are expensive," she says, "especially since there are not enough tourists in the park.⁵³" In March 2019, Kampung Peta is coming out of a dead period in terms of tourism: two rainy seasons and, in between, a closure of the park for renovation work. Perhaps tourism support activities have not yet recovered, but during my stay the tourist employment is almost reduced to that of guide.

Photo 16. Building of a *perahu* by Sam. Photo A.Vidal, March-April 2019.

50 « Dapat kebenaran hantar pelancong susah. »

51 « Kita bodoh. »

52 « Saya boleh, saya nak, tapi tak berkomunikasi, dia cakap saya faham, tapi tak boleh cakap baik. »

53 « Pelancong Taman ada kurang. »

Nazim and his brothers Kamaruddin and Sam, who build their own *perahu* (monoxyyl bottom motor boat, see photo 16 on the previous page) operate a transport service on the river to Kuala Jasin, the starting point for excursions. The site is accessible by road into the park, but the passage by boat provides more economic benefits to the village and leaves visitors with beautiful memories. Apart from Fatin who sews gaiters against leeches and Ahmad who demonstrates his art of blowpipe making, there are few other jobs derived from tourism.

The income from tourism flows down very poorly and is concentrated on a few actors: a first circle of certified self-employed guides who are hired by the park, a second circle of English-speaking guides (and fishing guides, like Syazwan, who can earn up to RM 1,000 per month) who work for the park or for outside agents and earn a better living, and a third circle of two people, Syamsul and Fatah, who are the only ones to work directly with an international audience, without an agent. Syamsul estimates that his income can be as high as RM 3,000. Fatah earns, according to the president of the JCNTGA, RM 4 to 5,000 a month, which rewards his ability to make himself known on social networks, to the point where he has become one of the faces of Endau-Rompin National Park. Fatah and Syamsul are cousins and worked together for a long time until Syamsul decided to stop the collaboration, disappointed by Fatah's greed and his toughness in business (interview with Syamsul).

Hospitality is an industry associated with tourism that could benefit the village. A cottage was built by the inhabitants, probably with the help of a grant, and was to be managed for the benefit of the community. It is in disinheritance and the reason given to me is the inability of the *batin* to properly handle this mission. Rampuyan confirms that he does not know how to do it. While in the village there are young people who can handle bookings in English, with a very decent reaction time, it is a poorly connected and Malay-only-speaking sixty-year-old who has been entrusted with this mission. Lack of interest from people better placed to handle bookings has prevented this investment from benefiting the village.

Another grant led to the construction of buildings during the winter of 2018-2019: two large shelters, one with a basic kitchen, a structure of tables and benches and another for sleeping accommodation (photo 18 below), as well as four bungalows (photo 17), all using local techniques and materials, and sanitary facilities with English toilets and tiled floors. This facility, which Syamsul calls a camp site, was built by him, Asma, Nazim, Fatah and Sam, two uncles and their three nephews and niece. They are the ones who manage it in what seems to me to be a

certain confusion between village interest and self-interest, but I do not know the details of the grant that made it possible to undertake this work. It is too early to know if this development will be well maintained and used but for the moment it is.

Photo 17. Camp site, bungalows (and sanitary facilities). Photo 18. Shelter for camping. Photos A. Vidal, March-April 2019.

Tourist attendance at Endau-Rompin Park is not very high. The services are expensive (about RM 2,000 the 3D2N service for two people), partly because of the isolation of the village and the high price of 4 x 4 transport. There are far fewer tourists than people who can accommodate them and few guides are so busy that they have to share their activity with others. But rather than lowering their salaries, villagers working in tourism have increased their income by inflating prices, notes Lee Shin-Shin of UNDP.

They charge too high rates. (...) They asked us to stay in another room and charged RM 150, it's very expensive.⁵⁴ They charge 80+. They had a fan full of dust, I had to clean it myself! Sometimes they just want to charge higher but they have to have higher standards. (interview with Lee Shin-Shin)

Apart from the very different hygiene standards between the Jakun of the *kampung* and the wealthy urban visitors, another reason can be sought to explain the lack of cleanliness of the premises. The five people who run the camp site do not, to my knowledge, employ any of the unskilled people in the village to help them take care of the buildings. They do all the cooking or cleaning themselves. In doing so, they do not help to distribute the tourist manna and perhaps do

⁵⁴ In Kuala Tahan, the gateway to the Taman Negara of Pahang, a double room with all modern comfort (ensuite shower room, air conditioning and many amenities) costs between RM 120 and 150. Kampung Peta's accommodation offer is more basic.

not exploit as well as possible the skills, however modest, of the other people in the village.

"Not everyone can do ecotourism, only young people," says Shin-Shin about the limits she sees to tourism employment in the village. It is a service activity requiring skills that are uncommon in a village, and it pays high wages that are pulled up by the purchasing power of the wealthy classes in rich countries she is targeting. In addition to these structural causes of concentration, there is a collective dynamic that is not very effective, which for example does not exploit the possibility of creating less qualified jobs. Tourism, because of the high salaries it offers, arouses the envy of the inhabitants, who have a variety of skills but lack organisation, as can be seen at first glance.

What they want in Kampung Peta specifically is work on ecotourism. Quite a number of them are very capable but what is lacking is a more systematic way to put up the services that they can provide and to make it for tourists to understand, as agreed what kind of services they have, what they can bring people. (interview with Lee Shin-Shin)

7.1.4. Distribution of Income from Tourism

Shin-Shin praises the qualities of a group of young people from the village ("those young chaps") but believes that they "just have to be put in a more systematic way, not one here and there." She gives an example of what a collective dynamic would do.

Colin Nicholas has a vision that they must organize so well that when people look for Kampung Peta, immediately their organization would be there to make a booking. Currently this is not happening.

At present, an online search on the Endau-Rompin Park refers to a multiplicity of web pages including those of entrepreneurs outside the village who sell services with accommodation in the Taman Negara premises and in the village. During my stay, two French tourists who said they wanted to contribute to the village's economy and meet its inhabitants had booked their room in the park, finding it difficult to find their way in the offer proposed by a Chinese-Malaysian agent (with whom Asma and her sister are very satisfied). Direct communicating would enhance the visibility of a commercial offer that is more profitable to the local community and corresponds to

the ethical standards of certain Western visitors. The internal resources to replace external tourist agents exist: Fatah, Syamsul and Asma are quite capable of organising the stay of groups of tourists and their transport from Mersing or Kluang, as well as guiding them through the forest, cooking for them and building the bungalows where they will sleep – or employing people who can take care of all this. But since everyone has their own individual communication and offer, it's not always the best talents that are put forward. We have seen, for example, that infrastructures maintained by busy people are not very clean. As for Fatah, who is the best known guide in Kampung Peta, several sources tell me that many of the Western tourists he accompanies come back disappointed from excursions during which they learned nothing, whether about nature or culture, because he speaks very little to them. He seems to be a better entrepreneur than a guide. "If they do ecotourism on individual basis, it would not be beneficial as a whole" (interview with Lee Shin-Shin), or even the activity itself. The lack of collaboration between them reduces the quality of what they offer, and this inability to co-operate may be less a matter of disorganisation than a way of considering social life from the point of view of one's individual interest, without fear of harming one's cousin and degrading family ties. We shall have to return to the question of the individualisation of destinies and the role played by tourism, and more generally the economy in which the village is situated, in these changes.

The benefits of tourism are ambiguous ("mixed blessing", as the expression goes): in exchange for economic benefits that are sometimes disproportionned with the low local salaries, the inhabitants of a place that has become a tourist destination are subjected to cultural "standardisation" or "trivialisation" (Adams 2009) and see their environment degraded by massive use (Borchers 2009) or by an extravagant use of rare and fragile natural resources (Homewood and Rodgers 1991). In Kampung Peta, all the actors speak of ecotourism (*ekopelancongan*), an expression coined by Hector Ceballos-Lascurain in the late 1980s (Luquiau 2015: 130), at a time when the concept of sustainable development was being developed (Zaccai 2002). Ecotourism is along the same lines: it is nature tourism that must be conducted in a sustainable manner, that is, according to its most demanding definitions, have "low impact and little disruption of the ecosystem" while "a potential vehicle to provide environmental, socio-economic and cultural benefits at both local and national levels" (Brandon 1996: 1). These three pillars (environmental, socio-economic and cultural) are strongly reminiscent of the three pillars of sustainable development: environment, economy and democracy. This ecotourism, more than just nature tourism, has among its vocations that of sustaining disadvantaged rural communities, but the main regret in this regard is the lack of

redistribution in Kampung Peta of these economic benefits. It is expressed in these terms by outside observers such as the president of JCNTGA and Lee Shin-Shin, while the villagers who are kept away from this sector simply regret not being able to benefit as well from this economy. This has led to the change in strategy of the UNDP community conservation project.

In the current ICCA project for Kampung Peta livelihood is not the first thing, we started to look in ecotourism. (...) I understand the situation, I think during the consultation they push ecotourism but then I realized ecotourism is not for everyone. The group was quiet, especially the women. For the second project I will look more forward to this. (interview with Lee Shin-Shin)

The first project concerns tourist infrastructures and benefits to certain actors in the village, while others remain dependent on activities that are both painful and not very rewarding. The second, which began during my stay, is, as we have seen, about farming activities, to adapt the type of crops grown in the village to the constraints on land, agricultural prices and distance from the market. This is a turn initiated by Shin-Shin after the experience of the first project. How should we interpret the silence of the women she observed during the discussions she led on this subject? Were the villagers silenced by the group of tourism entrepreneurs? Or were they willing, hoping that the development of this sector would finally reach them, allowing them to benefit from high remuneration? I received very little general criticism of the place of tourism in Kampung Peta, only about the way this activity is carried out and in particular about the role of the Taman Negara.

7.2. Kampung Peta and the Taman Negara, a Momentous History

The Endau-Rompin National Park was established in 1993 as a joint initiative between the states of Johor and Pahang, named after the Endau and Rompin River watersheds, with the mouth of the Rompin River at Kuala Rompin 25km north of the Endau River. This river does not flow into the Taman Negara and about a quarter of the park which is located in Pahang is not visited since the two entrances, Selai and Kampung Peta, are in Johor.

7.2.1. Malaysian Nature Society in Kampung Peta

Endau-Rompin Park is administered by the Perbadanan Taman Negara Johor (Johor National Parks Corporation) but was foreshadowed by the Malaysian Nature Society (MNS), Malaysia's oldest environmentalist association, dating from the colonial era (Guerin 2017a) and still very active today. My main source on this is Ann Cheong, widow of Heah Hock Heng who led the MNS activity in Kampung Peta. In 1985-1986, she says, the State of Johor, which wanted to open a research centre in its northeastern forest, commissioned the MNS to organise a scientific expedition which was coordinated by Hock Heng and guided by the Jakun Nazim and Sangka Chuka (then *batin*). Later, after the establishment of the park, Hock Heng chose the site of the future Nature Education and Research Centre (NERC), a former Jakun settlement planted with durians, and hired people from Kampung Peta to construct the first buildings. Ann Cheong says that the villagers volunteered to dig the drains but her husband had the idea of using them to build the entire centre: "If you can build your own houses, you can jolly well build a research centre." The workers were recruited by the MNS, men and women, including very young men and women, all paid the same salaries and committed to opening bank accounts for the occasion. According to his widow, Hock Heng "gave everybody, including women, dignity" and she gives the example of the skills they acquired: driving, cooking.

We have on this period when Heah Hock Heng and the MNS appreciate the collaboration with the inhabitants of Kampung Peta the view of the villagers themselves collected by Colin Nicholas (who thanks "Heah of MNS-NERC [who] provided the useful first contacts with the community," Nicholas 1999: 3).

At any one time about 25-30 Jakun from Kampung Peta would be working on the project on a daily-rated wage of RM30 per day. There are however about 80 Jakun who are willing, and have registered, to work on the project, a third of whom are women. To provide a fairer distribution of employment opportunities, a rotation system has been put in place for the less-skilled jobs. Employment in the NERC project currently brings in an income of about RM17,000 to the Jakun in Kampung Peta. (Nicholas 1999 : 7)

Colin Nicholas reports a "general perception of the Jakun towards the Malaysian Nature Society (MNS) [being] that it has been a positive relationship" (Nicholas 1999: 7). This is not only

because of the economic benefit, but also because of the self-esteem that this collaboration brings. He quotes an elderly person from the village who did not work on the site.

The Taman Negara used to say that the Orang Asli can't do anything, can't carry loads or work with wood. That's why they wouldn't give us work. But the MNS was able to give us work. We, the Orang Asli, want this project to serve as an example, because they say that the Orang Asli have no experience, they don't know how to do this kind of work⁵⁵. (Nicholas 1999 : 7)

Nicholas also reports complaints about the delay in the work, but attributes this to the time it took to train villagers in techniques they did not know about and the difficulties in getting construction materials to the site due to the poor condition of the road. And these delays are not very severe compared to the value of working with the local community.

7.2.2. The Village Community and Environmental Protection Requirements

With the MNS, village residents are affected by conservation issues that previously appeared to be imposed from outside, with various prohibitions on hunting, fishing, logging or collecting. Sangka Chuka, then *batin*, recounts the change in perspective brought about by the relationship with the MNS: "I learned to love the forest with the MNS. I was also able to meet other people, people from outside. All this is thanks to the MNS. We became conscious thanks to the MNS" (Nicholas 1999: 6). Sangka is one of the architects of the collaboration between Kampung Peta and the MNS, and Ann Cheong describes it this way:

Sangka was a liberal, he welcomed new ideas so when the the *kampung* needed to elect a new *batin* they elected Sangka who was an outsider but the villagers accepted his leadership and that helped the *kampung* to change a lot. (interview with Ann Cheong)

The result, according to Colin Nicholas, is not "a change of heart towards the creatures of the forest but more a realisation that greater economic gain could be obtained if the natural

55 "Dulu Taman kata Orang Asli tak pandai buat, Orang Asli tak boleh pikul, tak pandai kerja kayu. Sebab itu tak bagi kerja. Tapi MNS boleh bagi kerja. Ini projek kita Orang Asli nak bagi contoh sebab dia kata Orang Asli tak ada pengalaman, tak boleh buat kerja macam ini."

attractions of the park were protected." (Nicholas 1999: 12). A change in attitude that Machang, a villager who we have seen "used to kill birds with slingshots⁵⁶", expresses it this way: "Now we know it is a loss to kill [the bird]. There is more profit in letting it live and taking people to watch the birds."⁵⁷ Machang then trained himself to know the names of birds in English in the hope of accompanying bird-watching tourists (Nicholas 1999: 13), but he no longer does this, he is now a farmer and fisherman. The lexical field he uses (*rugi, untung*) is that of economics and the comparison between two gains.

Conservation and tourism are partly linked in the Jakun's words: the latter is the condition of his existence. Even when tourism is not involved, the Jakun are able to set rules⁵⁸ to ensure the protection of their resources, whether rattan or fish. Colin Nicholas describes a change in community-regulated fishing practices. Aruana⁵⁹ fishing in particular is governed by a ritual described by Syamsul: "Before we harvest the fish aruana, the shaman will go up river and have a special place in the landscape to pray there, for the community here, when we harvest the aruana fish to ask the permission from the spirit of river." In 1999 Nicholas describes pragmatic rules adopted by the village to protect the resource, which is endangered in the downstream villages and which has diminished significantly in Kampung Peta. The villagers agreed among themselves, at the initiative of the *tawkey* who buys the fish from them, to adopt fishing techniques that are less likely to prevent the reproduction of adult fish. In an effort to ensure a sustainable resource, the village fishermen refuse techniques that can injure or kill adult fish, release them if caught, and settle for young fish, which already provide a good income. Fishermen from other villages can only fish in Kampung Peta if they follow these rules (Nicholas 1999: 14). Nazim expresses in 2019 how much the conservation requirements have been integrated by the Jakun, whether they are implemented by the park or whether they themselves have set the rules: "If we think 'Hey, we won in court, we can catch all the fish until there are no more,' in the end we are the ones who lose, not the park⁶⁰" (interview with Nazim). The Jakun are also the ones who are responsible for the conservation of Kampung Peta.

When other resources are accessible, or when attitudes to environmental protection make sense,

56 "Kita suka lastik itu burung."

57 "Sekarang kita sudah tahu bahawa rugi kita bunuh dia. Ada lebih untung kasi dia hidup, bawa orang tengok burung."

58 I do not have enough information on their actual implementation, but my informants did not express any complaints in this regard.

59 Aruana, a freshwater fish of the Osteoglossidae family, is sold as an ornamental fish at very high prices.

60 "Kita pikir Hey kita sudah menang mukamah kita boleh ambil ikan sampai habis tapi yang sebenarnya yang rugi kita sendiri, bukan yang Taman."

the Jakun know how to understand, obey and even make certain rules themselves. But it is more difficult when they are in need. Colin Nicholas gives the example of the rainy season, which is the season when their income is at its lowest: the park is closed, the rubber tree is not harvested. It is also the period when the animals are easiest to hunt. Seman, an informant of Nicholas' whom I have not met, justifies poaching in the park as follows: "When there is no other work, no other source of income, we are forced to disobey so that it is less difficult for us"⁶¹ (Nicholas 1999: 15). Coercive measures directed at the local population to ensure environmental protection often prove to be less effective than providing alternatives to predatory activities. This is the finding on which UNDP's ICCA programme builds by working with communities to seek viable economic strategies to increase their capacity to implement protection practices. In the words of Colin Nicholas, "a normal conservation project is just on conservation but this ICCA is focussing on people"

The situation described by Nicholas in 1999 regarding the relationship to environmental protection – a very instrumental relationship with very little of the animism that the villagers claim to have – still exists today. Asma has the same reasoning as Machang about the monkeys no longer being eaten in the village: "Better show [the monkey]." But this is now part of a relationship with the Taman Negara that has deteriorated considerably over the past 20 years.

7.2.3. Deterioration of Relations with the Taman Negara

After the construction of the NERC buildings, MNS recruited and trained education officers and then left the park, where it is no longer present today. "After all that was done [MNS] handed the project back to Johor government and little by little the staff was posted to other projects and left NERC (...). Since then it was not used as it was designed to be", says Ann Cheong, partly because the popular education dimension is less present and NERC welcomes instead an academic, student and research audience. It is now taken in charge by the Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia (UTHM) in Batu Pahat (Johor). Ann Cheong illustrates the deteriorating relationship between the park and the village community by the fact that when new buildings were built at NERC, an outside firm was chosen (because it could pay bribes, she believes) for a lower quality result. She cites local architects discovering and comparing the two buildings: "This one was built by Orang Asli, and the other by contractors, this one was built with love."

61 « Kalau benda lain tak ada, tak ada pendapatan lain, kita terpaksa-lah salah supaya tak susah. »

Taman Negara's policy towards the Jakun of Kampung Peta is ambiguous, and certainly not as well disposed towards them as Heah Hock Heng and the MNS have been. Although the park employs a majority of villagers, villagers complain that the Taman Negara employs in the best jobs outsiders who travel daily from Kahang and that opportunities for development are also scarce for the locals (Asma has been working in the park for more than ten years without ever climbing the ladder, while she is praised for her intelligence and leadership qualities by Lee Shin-Shin and Colin Nicholas who see her taking on many responsibilities). The conditions of remuneration or employment are often questioned and during my stay Iman rebelled against a new provision imposed by the administration: with the same remuneration she had to offer tourists an assortment of souvenirs sold by Ahmad. The "gift" from the park at her expense reduced her remuneration from RM 130 to RM 100. The employment of the Jakun in Taman Negara does not only meet the labour needs of the park, it is also a way of providing the village with an income to reduce the pressure on the environment of the park and the forest reserve.

While the park is much criticized as an employer, it is not criticized as a coercive force to enforce environmental protection laws. The Wildlife Conservation Act of 2010, section 51, grants Orang Asli non-commercial hunting rights to certain species. This is not the case under the 1980 National Parks Act, but the park authorities grant them similar rights: "Management still allowed them for going in and out the park for local purpose (food sources) and not for commercial using" (interview with the park authorities). On the other hand, even when the Jakun take liberties with these rules, for example by selling the property in question, they are not, to my knowledge, prosecuted. At worst they seem to get away with challenging the authorities to go up the trade routes: "If you have a problem with this, go and arrest the Chinese trader [who buys the meat]⁶²" (Nicholas 1999: 15).

The park and forest reserve authorities are also unable to take action against poachers who prey on the most strictly protected species: tiger, elephant, bear. Kamaruddin, Saiful and Syazwan report encounters in the forest with poaching teams from neighbouring countries and the reluctance of the police to intervene: "There are often poachers, always. Nothing is done. I've already made reports, I said there were Thai people, but [the police] took two weeks to come and see⁶³" (interview with Syazwan).

62 "Ada apa-apa, you tangkap dengan towkay Cina."

63 "Sering ada poachers, selalu ada. Nothing is done. Saya pernah buat report, saya cakap sana ada Thailand orang, dia perlu dua minggu mau masuk."

There aren't enough people to watch. (...) This area is a customary territory. (...) The Taman Negara is not guarded well enough. (...) Those who work [as forest rangers] are outsiders but not Orang Asli. They are Malays. They who keep watch. They can't do anything, they are afraid. (...) I came across a large group of poachers, from Thailand or Cambodia. (...) I just ran away. Next time, I'll take my blowpipe!⁶⁴
(interview with Syazwan)

Syazwan complains at the same time that the forest is not protected and that the Jakun are not employed in those missions for which they have the capacity and motivation – to protect their customary lands. The Taman Negara cannot employ the whole village, says Nazim, and I understood that the Jakun employees are overstaffed (as is often the case in Malaysia), with few tasks to keep them busy. But the monitoring missions are rather understaffed and would benefit from their expertise, as the Wildlife Conservation Society, which employs them, understands. The park management does not envisage recruiting more staff to these positions, but the relevant ministry announced in July 2019 the establishment of closer collaboration between rangers and police (Malaysiakini 2019).

The greatest tensions between Taman Negara and the village community are related to the land issue. In 1999, the park authorities have long had monthly meetings with the village committee (JKKK) and this is still the case today, on a regular basis or when the need arises (a meeting in April 2019 dealt with access to tombs on park land). This relationship is now marked by a serious dispute between them between 2012 and 2018. The Taman Negara attempted in 2012 to deny access to a less populated part of the village but understood as part of it since its establishment. There are various tombs and twenty houses, two of which are inhabited (interview with Nazim). The villagers filed a complaint, supported by pro bono lawyers and the expertise of Colin Nicholas. They won their lawsuit in 2016 (Mohd Nazlan 2016) but the Taman Negara appealed and postponed the appeal as much as possible before proposing an unfavourable settlement which they nevertheless accepted. In 2018, the Taman Negara closed for the whole year for minor renovations that apparently did not justify such a long closure (according to Zulkifli, a gardener at the park, and others). The villagers' income dropped considerably that year, and the inhabitants found themselves in great difficulty. This pressure explains, according

64 "Tak cukup orang [yang jaga]. (...) Itu area, itu wilayah tanah adat. (...) Taman Negara dijaga kurang baik. (...) Kalau pekerja, lain lain ada, tapi yang jaga hutan Orang Asli tak ada. Ada rangers tapi bukan Orang Asli. Orang Melayu. Yang jaga. Tak boleh enforce, dia takut. (...) Tiba tiba pemburuh haram sudah banyak, like Thailand, Kambodja. (...) Saya lari sahaja. For the next time, I will make the blowpipe!"

to Colin Nicholas, the choice of the inhabitants who agreed, in exchange for dropping the legal action, not to open any more farmland despite their need. Only a few months after this agreement, the villagers wanted to question it.

Now they want to change because they're ok economically but it's too late. It's the economics [who influenced their decision] which will affect their future economics.
(interview with Colin Nicholas)

7.2.4. Future of Tourism in Kampung Peta

While the loss of tourism revenues in 2018 has not dampened villagers' enthusiasm for tourism, they are less confident about the park. In order to reduce their dependence on the Taman Negara, villagers speak of opening alternative paths to those operated by the park, which were opened years ago by the Jakun. Located within the forest reserve and outside the park, these new roads would be accessible from Kampung Peta and could lead to the old village site across the river and to Bukit Peta. The two fishing guides, Syazwan and Kini, kept the same activity during the closure, proving that nature tourism in Kampung Peta is not limited to the park. Syamsul is also considering activities that could bring tourists in during the rainy season.

Nine months only, that's why with Asma we are building our own camp site. Even if the Taman closed, the *kampung* is not closed and the tourists can come directly to our place and we still have income from them. Even if they stay one night we are planning to the long term, a backup planning. In the rainy season, they can stay there, *makan-makan*, *tidur-tidur*, make games, listen stories if it's raining. Water tubing, lots of things we can do. Traditional food like cooking in the bamboo. (interview with Syamsul)

The village is difficult to access in case of heavy rains because of the track which constitutes the bulk of the journey, and it is likely that eating and sleeping are not very attractive activities for tourists who "do" Malaysia in three weeks, but people who depend on tourism are trying to make it a more stable activity and less dependent on the Taman Negara. They are not concerned that the arrival of international tourists is itself dependent on the economic health of the sending countries, oil prices or the international context: the Bali bombings in 2002, by explicitly threatening tourists, led to a decline in tourist arrivals across the region (Hitchcock *et al.* 2009)

and in 2003 Malaysia suffered a decline in arrivals of around 20%. Syamsul outlines some prospects for the future.

White people walk well, they pay well, they want to learn things, about our culture, what we eat, our way of life. Singaporeans also. Europeans are more interested in the forest. I think there will be more tourists in ten years and more people working in tourism, I'm not sure, I hope.⁶⁵ (interview with Syamsul)

The perception of tourism is very positive, and there is often talk of the exchanges it allows with the outside world. From Kampung Peta's point of view, the outside world is a Malaysia with institutions marked by a religion, Islam, which the Jakun do not appreciate. International tourism allows them to open up to a much wider world and to be valued more than what Malays do: they blame the Orang Asli for not being "advanced", their relationship with the forest is perceived as a wild way of life, animism is not considered a religion in Malaysia, and so on. All this, in the eyes of a Western tourist, is much more attractive than visiting these mosques which, according to the Malays, are the biggest attractions in the country (pink mosque of Putrajaya, blue mosque of Shah Alam, floating mosques of Kuala Terengganu and Malacca, etc.). Western tourists overthrow the hierarchies that prevail in Malaysia to the advantage of the Orang Asli.

The Jakun like to see that on their ground they are smarter (*pandai*) than the whites (*orang putih*). As a joke in the village says, the whites know how to enter the forest (*masuk hutan*) but not necessarily come back. The knowledge that enables the Jakun to guide tourists in the forest is passed on informally: "When I go to the jungle with oldest people, I asked them, I learned directly from them " (interview with Syamsul).

65 « Orang putih jalan jauh, bayar mahal, they want to learn something, our culture, what we eat, how is our life. Orang Singapura juga. Orang Eropa lebih motivated tentang rainforest. I think lebih banyak pelancong in ten years maybe, lebih banyak orang yang kerja pelancongan, I'm not sure, I hope so. »

Photo 19. The poster for the Kampung Peta Indigenous Festival on August 8, 2019, features a villager in traditional clothing made from the beaten bark of a terap tree (*Artocarpus odoratissimus*). Source : Syamsul.

Their appreciation of tourism is expressed in terms very similar to those used by Sangka Chuka to show his favourable feelings towards MNS (Nicholas 1999: 6). International tourism values indigenous cultures, in both senses of the term: it gives them interest and esteem, and this interest can lead to commercial exchanges. This is the case in the Cameron Highlands, where until a few years ago the tourism offer included visits to Semai villages,⁶⁶ and especially in the Taman Negara of Pahang where the Batek "play Batek for tourists" (Endicott *et al.* 2016). In Endau-Rompin, the park authorities did not have the idea to market the Jakun rituals and instead reduced the Bela Tanah ritual that was held in Kuala Jasin for the Lunar New Year from three days of festivities to a half day in 1999 (Nicholas 1999: 11). The people of the village are their own cultural entertainers and have for some years now been organizing a "traditional" festival

66 This attraction has been abandoned, according to tourism entrepreneurs in Tanah Rata, on the grounds that the villages are too poor and the tourists too uncomfortable with the spectacle of their misery.

staging their cultural identity every August 8: raft race, blowpipe contest, engagement ceremony (see photo 19, previous page). This is not an invention around a local rite, but to celebrate the International Day of the World's Indigenous People, which takes place the following day. With this date, they fit into a framework that is more militant than traditional.

To criticize the Taman Negara but to praise tourism is the most common position in the village. Asma is the only one, along with her sister Iman, who does not even want to depend on tourism, whether working for the park or independently: "When [my business] bears fruit, I will no longer need to be a guide, to work for the Taman Negara, I will work on my own."⁶⁷ In doing so, she is making the same choice as Lee Shin-Shin made for the second ICCA project, to turn to agriculture rather than depend on an unstable service activity. Nazim, although for him progress is about learning English and computer communication skills to support tourism activities, is actually quite close: "The most important thing is land. Life and land."⁶⁸ Colin Nicholas agrees.

[Asma] is smart, she knows she doesn't want to depend on tourism like they did. And for nine months they starve, they had nothing. Like in any society, you must balance your [sources of income]. It's an insurance scheme. (interview with Colin Nicholas)

Tourism has changed the village's economy so much that the loss of income from this activity alone in 2018 has pushed the inhabitants into great poverty. It has also exacerbated the tendency observed by Maeda in the 1960s to "distinguish between 'rich' and 'poor'" (Maeda 2001: 62). Tourism offers higher remuneration than other village activities, it has a structural tendency to concentrate them, but it only amplifies developments that are those of "technical exchanges". It is to these evolutions that the last chapter will be devoted by examining how this market economy disrupts relations between women and men and the non-commercial circulation of wealth within the family circle.

67 "Kalau berbuah sini, saya tak perlu antar lagi, antar orang, kerja Taman Negara, saya akan kerja sendiri."

68 "Isu paling penting tanah. Hidup pun penting tanah pun penting."

Chapter 8. Several Effects of Market Economy

8.1 Expenditure Trends and Growth of Wage Employment

8.1.1 First Gendered Division of Labour

The first texts that we have on the Jakun show a gendered division of labour. Women take care of domestic chores and are more involved in reproductive rather than productive activities, unlike men. Logan made this observation in 1847.

In the house (...) the husband appears more as an honored guest than as the lord. The wife has the entire management. A Binuá expressed their ideas on this score figuratively, by saying that the husband was the *nakhoda* of the *práúh*, and the wife *nakhoda* of the house. (Logan 1847 : 266)

Maeda resumed this analysis in 1965. "The division of labor between the sexes is clear. In a house the wife is said to be the skipper and is responsible for household matters, in which the husband hardly interferes" (Maeda 2001: 65). Women are also in charge of cultivation around the house, as opposed to the more distant rice fields.

Simple gardening may be carried on near the residence, where vegetables, sweet potatoes, banana, sugar cane, bamboo, rubber, and various fruit trees are planted. This work is done entirely by the women. (Maeda 2001 : 40)

Shanthi Thambiah qualifies this observation by noting a difference between tasks that are strictly reserved for one sex or the other and tasks that are more commonly performed by men or women.

In food preparation, carrying water and child care, women are more involved than men but these tasks are not exclusively done by women. Washing clothes, collecting

firewood and house cleaning are also predominantly done by women, while building and repairing the house is an exclusively male activity. (Thambiah 1999 : 280)

This is an important nuance as it reflects a gendered division of labour that is quite flexible and is found in other Orang Asli peoples. Even in the case of highly gendered activities, such as blowpipe hunting among the Batek, Endicott and Endicott observe a very low participation of women, at 2% of the trips (Endicott and Endicott 2012: 113-114), which is indicative of the fact that they are not prohibited from using the blowpipe and killing animals.

Other dimensions of the village economy also involve women and men: rattan collection and subsistence fishing are activities that Maeda, like Shanthi Thambiah in the late 1990s, sees couples carrying out together. The division between mixed and non-mixed activities is not between subsistence activities (hunting, fishing, agriculture) and commercial activities (rattan collection, wage labour) but within these activities: couples fish and cultivate hill rice together but only the men hunt; couples look for rattan and *kayu tije* (a tree whose pulp is sold for the production of adhesive) together but only the men are wage-earners. Thambiah nevertheless observes a shift within activities that are perceived as mixed and notes that rattan collection is becoming more specialized: groups of men organize more efficient collections or heavier rattans, without the women who are excluded. Since older couples were more likely to work together than younger couples, she wondered whether this was a development that had so far only affected younger couples or whether, having grown older in turn, they would once again enjoy working as a couple. For my part, I have seen couples of all ages (from 30 to 60) collecting rattan together and women more than men. Rattan is rather the activity of those who do not have any other choice, and it did not appear to me as specially gendered (except its cleaning which is done by women).

8.1.2 The Rise of Monetary Needs

The rise of commercial activities at the expense of livelihood activities, documented by Maeda, has been followed by a rise in wage employment. These movements are due to increased monetary needs and changes in spending and food.

The Jakun of Kampung Peta have traditionally practised slash-and-burn agriculture, hunting, fishing and collecting forest products for food, medicine or commercial purposes (Maeda 2001:

37-40), but as early as the 1960s, Maeda notes that "the harvest of dry rice provides subsistence only temporarily" and that "Orang Hulu like to eat the commercial rice from Padang Endau" (Maeda 2001: 40). Today, the share of subsistence farming is even lower and they buy rice, some vegetables (eggplant, tomato, cucumber, Chinese cabbage, *bok choy*, dried chilli, garlic and shallot), some fruits (watermelon, orange, banana), rare legumes, "city chicken" (*ayam bandar*), all their eggs, a few tins of canned food (sardines in particular), sea fish or beef on rare occasions, ingredients for cooking (coconut milk in bricks, dried anchovies, peanuts, spices and herbs, salt, sodium glutamate), tea, coffee, sugar and sweets, palm oil. The oil has considerably changed the villagers' diet and most dishes are now wok fried in a large amount of oil.

The current diet in the village consists of a mix of processed agro-industrial products, which are very high in calories and relatively low in nutrients, and local produce. Tea and coffee are very sweet and can be drunk at any time of the day, with or without unsweetened biscuits, and children buy many sweet snacks in grocery stores. It is likely that villagers, like the general Malaysian population, do not suffer from any major deficiencies, as is the case in poorer indigenous communities (The Star 2019), but have caloric intakes that are too high for their energy expenditure and a sugar intake that threatens them with type 2 diabetes and dental cavities. I do not have any statistics on the prevalence of this diabetes in Kampung Peta but it is part of the experience of the villagers who speak of it as a common condition. Type 2 diabetes affects about 20% of adults in Malaysia (Zanariah *et al.* 2015), perhaps less in the village where I found less overweight children than elsewhere in the country.

Another portion of the power is produced on site, either self-produced or purchased from neighbours. "Here everyone has enough to eat,⁶⁹" says Syazrina. Most of the *kelamin* I have met spend between RM 300 and 400 a month on food, which is one of their biggest expenses. Like other Malaysians, who enjoy a great abundance of food, the Jakun of Kampung Peta generally have a varied diet at their disposal, which plays an important role in social life. As their income is unstable and fluctuating, they are able to adapt their expenses and can bring them down to about RM 50 per month, rice (the 10kg packet costs RM 25-28) and basic food expenses (oil, anchovies, chili pepper, garlic, shallot) to embellish it. The *lauk*, the side dishes of the rice, are then reduced to the food available in the vicinity of the village: river fish and *pucuk*, the wild leaves that are harvested for pleasure as well as necessity. This is a strategy described to me by several people, including Asma: "If not money, you can go collect pucu paku, you can go fishing,

69 "Di sini semua makan cukup."

hunting, because have the forest. (...) If you're lazy, you don't eat, lah!" Similarly, when there is not enough money to buy gas for cooking, her sister Iman says it is always possible to use wood gathered in the forest.

The villagers' last resort food is rice, fish and vegetables. It is a balanced diet although not very varied. When *padi bukit* was still cultivated and rice was not available for purchase, the nutritional intake was more interesting since local rice from farmer selection has the advantage of being eaten whole and being richer in nutrients than rice from agronomic selection whose main objective is the productivity of the varieties. It was eaten alternatively with tubers and roots, among them cassava (*ubi kayu*) is the most important. Syazrina sometimes cooks her favourite dish, a simple cassava and wild leaf soup, which she notes is less fatty than wok cooking. Cassava was, when the Jakun depended on subsistence farming, "a much more abundant form of subsistence food" than rice (Maeda 2001: 40), and Syazrina confirms that in the past (*dulu*) rice was eaten only once a day, not two or three times as now. Food self-production still exists in Kampung Peta, but it is no longer an important part of productive activities, as we have seen.

In the 1960s, cash income was used to acquire rice and capital goods (machetes, sarongs, crockery) but in the 1990s Thambiah notes a wider range of goods consumed.

For most families wage employment is the only means for acquiring processed food and new prestige symbols such as motorcycle, modern houses, electrical appliances, etc. (Thambiah 1999 : 282)

Credit for a scooter or a car is as important an expense as food. Asma pays RM 380 in monthly installments (*bulanan*) for her scooter, while Zubaidah and her husband pay back their car credit RM 450 per month, plus fuel. To this expense must be added the smart phones that many people under the age of 40 are equipped with and the price of telecommunications. Salaries and service income make it easier to cover these expenses than independent activities in the primary sector, which are generally less remunerative. This contributes to making service and wage payments attractive, as Thambiah noted twenty years ago.

The desire for these new things has led to greater efforts on the part of men to find wage work and cash incomes, often with the result that the women became still more

alone at home. The direct effect of this on the women is that they play a less important role for the family standard of living while the men became much more so as wage earners. (Thambiah 1999 : 281)

In a village economy, with subsistence or commercial agriculture, women have their place in productive activities, but this is no longer the case in the context of wage employment.

8.2 Inequalities between Women and Men

8.2.1. Inequalities between Women and Men in the Labour Market

Today there are four women and fifteen men employed at Taman Negara in Kampung Peta, two men employed at the Wildlife Conservation Society, one woman and five men employed in the palm plantations. One man and one woman are civil servants. Only in the schools are there more women than men because employment is exclusively female in the kindergarten. A total of 10 women are employed in the village, which is the case of 26 men.

	Women	Men
Taman Negara full-time	2	10
Taman Negara part-time	2	5
Public employment (school not included)	1	1
School (SK + tadika)	4	2
<i>Total public employment</i>	<i>9</i>	<i>18</i>
Wildlife Conservation Society	0	2
Plantation full-time	0	1
Plantation part-time	1	4
Other wage employment	0	1
<i>Total private employment</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>8</i>
Total	10	26

Table 2. People employed in Kampung Peta.

Jakun women can breastfeed their children up to 5 or 6 years of age (Maeda 2001: 66), but the barriers to their employment are not related to their family obligations, since other members of the extended family, mostly women but also men, can care for their offspring during their

working hours, as I have observed. The most significant barrier to their employment is the discrimination they face from employers in hiring.

There is gender based work related discrimination in Malaysia. There is certainly a preference by most employers to hire men compared to women but women are preferred in certain professions. Women dominate in the public sector compared to the private sector. (interview with Shanthi Thambiah)

Even in the public sector, women in Kampung Peta are half as likely as men to be employed and inequalities explode in the private sector. There is no gender gap in the earnings of men and women in the public sector, but there is in the private sector (Shanthi Thambiah). In their study on employment in Kampung Chang Lama (Perak) in the early 2000s, Colin Nicholas, Tjah Yok Chopil and Tiah Sabak observed different pay according to ethnicity and gender. Between 1970 and 1998, Orang Asli men are still paid half as much as non-Orang Asli men. The same gap is observed between Orang Asli and non-Orang Asli women (it was even greater in previous decades) and women are paid about a third less than men of the same ethnicity. In 1998, Orang Asli women are therefore paid RM 12 per day while Orang Asli men negotiate their work at RM 18 and non-native men are paid RM 35. The lower economic interest of women in working may also explain a priority within the *kelamin* for male employment, in a context where jobs are scarce and many people who are available for employment do not have them.

	Remuneration in 1970 (in RM)	Remuneration in 1998 (in RM)
Man non-OA	10	35
Man OA	5	18
Woman non-OA	8	25
Woman OA	2	12

Table 3. Wage trends of non-indigenous and indigenous workers in Kampung Chang Lama (Perak). Source : Colin Nicholas, Tjah Yok Chopil and Tiah Sabak 2003 : 101.

Village women who are neither salaried nor self-employed in service activities may fall back, as men do, on self-entrepreneurship in the primary sector, which is akin to what Eric C. Thompson calls *kerja kampung* following a survey in a Malaysian village in the 1990s. They may also be *suri rumah*, or "queens of the house", i.e. housewives. "A *suri rumah* implies a woman whose husband is sufficiently affluent that she need not concern herself with matter outside the domestic sphere" (Thompson 2012: 99). The concept of *suri rumah* implies that women are not

engaged in subsistence activities (gardening, collecting, fishing) nor do they share in the activities of their husbands, such as Zarina and Ahmad, Fatimah and Nasrul, couples who together collect rattan and work on the rubber tree farm. Or that their work is not valued. Thompson insists in his survey to know if his respondents are *suri rumah* or have a *kerja kampung* activity because the two options are exclusive of each other. In theory, the rural economy only leaves inactive people who are not able to work, dependent elderly people, or pregnant women like Normah, a young married woman who is nearing term during my stay and has stopped all productive activity.

Suri rumah is therefore a very urban concept and moreover closer to the vision of the couple promoted by Islam (a man who rules at home and earns the household money) than to the more egalitarian gender relations of the Orang Asli. In Kampung Peta nine women are *suri rumah*, qualified as such by their husbands or by my informants whose first reflex was to tell me that they were "not working" (*tak kerja*). Syazwan is proud to tell me that his wife is "suri rumah sahaja" and that her work as a fishing guide is enough for the whole family. Most of these nine women have husbands who are employed, which is consistent with Thompson's analysis that this model corresponds to the organization of couples in which the man is a wage earner. But some of these husbands, such as Muhamad, work part-time and the household is struggling to make ends meet (according to Syazrina, his mother). Two older women, like Saifuddin's wife, are also supposed to be *suri rumah* while their husbands *kerja kampung* and they are likely to help them. So it seems to me that the concept, which is "not indigenous to the Orang Asli" (interview with Shanthi Thambiah), was imported before the generalization of the breadwinner husband as the sole full-time wage earner or earning equal amounts in self-employment. This confusion means that that model exists in representations before it exists in reality and this reflects a profound change in the way Orang Asli couples function.

This merging of indigenous social structures with those of the Malaysian majority is documented by other authors, whose work is cited by Nicholas *et al.* in their book on Semai women facing the degradation of the natural environment and the development of the market economy (Nicolas *et al.* 2003: 26-27). Signe Howell, referring to the Chewong, points to outside employment opportunities that are open to men and closed to women, economic changes combined with dominant unequal representations to disrupt gender relations (Howell 1983: 46-47). Karen Endicott on Batek (1981) and Barbara Nowak on Mah Meri (1986) observe couples working together and a gendered specialization of tasks that is not strict. A somewhat more recent survey

conducted by Endicott and Endicott in 1990 documents a significant change in women's lifestyles in a community now engaged in agricultural activities.

One difference was that most women's activities took place in or near the camp. Women made few of the expeditions that had been so common before, in which large groups of women and children would go in the forest looking for food. With the increase of rice and flour in the diet, people sought wild tubers only as supplements or for special reasons. (Endicott et Endicott 2012 : 210)

At the time of the first study "men in the farming group alternated between working on their fields and collecting forest produce for trade. (...) In 1990 hunting of all kinds had become almost exclusively a male occupation" (Endicott et Endicott 2012 : 212).

According to the groups in question, the exclusion of women from productive work is due to the disappearance of mixed tasks, which is caused by the degradation or loss of the environment in which they were carried out. It is also caused by the attraction of another lifestyle and other activities, in addition to discrimination against women in the labour market and the assimilation of dominant representations, particularly Malay and Muslim ones, of gender roles in society. Even the Jakun of Kampung Peta, who are animist and far more resistant to conversion to Islam than other groups, have endorsed the *suri rumah* model. This exclusion has important implications for women's autonomy.

8.2.2. Implications for Gender Inequality

The first gendered specialisation of tasks among the Jakun was not accompanied by any power of coercion: "The wife and husband are equal, and neither seems to exercise authority over the other in any formal manner" (Maeda 2001: 65). Is this equality between spouses still on the agenda since the changes in the *kelamin* economy? Increased specialisation, where activities are allocated more strictly, with reproductive activities being allocated to women and productive activities to men only, has immediate repercussions on women's economic independence.

While some men have been compensated for the loss of their traditional livelihood, women have not been directly compensated in any way. In relinquishing their role in subsistence farming, the women have lost their economic independence to a certain

degree. (Thambiah 1999 : 282)

I have observed these differences in income between men and women (see my respondents' incomes in table 5 in the appendix): income from self-employment in the primary sector is due to the combined efforts of women and men, but almost always, when the couple benefits from additional income in wages and salaries or in services, it is the man's (wage earners in Taman Negara, tourist income of Kamaruddin, wage employment of Suhail in Kahang). When both spouses have this type of income, it is rare for the woman's income to be higher, but it does happen, as in the case of Umairah and Zulkifli. This difference in treatment in the labour market "may eventually lead to sexual inequalities, especially when the incomes earned by women are way below those earned by men" (Thambiah 1999: 284).

What Iman calls "sitting at home" (*duduk di rumah sahaja*), a fate she considers unenviable, has consequences for women's well-being. Since there is ultimately little work in a Jakun house in the absence of wood chores and subsistence activities, "women who have no children or only older children have little to do and are bored and restless" (Thambiah 1999: 281). The loss of economic independence of one of the spouses is also problematic in the couple: "Cash income increases the occasions for conflicts over how wages will be used" (*ibid.*). Men, who are under increased pressure to provide for the needs of the household, may fail and be left by their wives, sink into alcoholism or abandon their families (*ibid.*).

It is ironic that at a time when women are entering men's sphere and are breaking out of the home and participating on a wider scale in areas previously considered men's domains, the reverse is happening among the Orang Asli where men and women are beginning to experience segregation along sexual lines. (Thambiah 1999 : 268)

Thambiah's disturbing finding is mitigated by the fact that the Jakun maintain a "bilateral inheritance system" that does not deprive women of the means of production as is the case among the Malaysians, who give less inheritance to women. And we have seen that the trends she identified at the end of the 1990s are still not accomplished twenty years later, even though women have lower incomes overall than men and even though the existence in the village of women who "do not work" shows a devaluation of their contribution to household wealth. This concern is quite similar to another about socio-economic inequalities in the village.

With the spread of the notions of private property as belonging to only one family or one individual, either male or female, has denied access to resources they once had, especially where resources are becoming scarce. Variations in the status and position of women and men within the community accentuate the formation of economic classes. (Thambiah 1999 : 287)

We will try to understand the extent to which these income inequalities break away from traditional uses and whether they are increasing in the long term.

8.3 Other Inequalities

8.3.1 Exchanges in the Family Sphere

Among the Jakun, as in many Orang Asli communities, many resources are traditionally shared within the community. The land does not belong to anyone, its usufruct is offered in equal parts to each *kelamin* and the rice from the harvest is symbolically shared. This is no longer the case today for many reasons. The land, which could be enjoyed by those who worked it, has become property and the object of trade ("commodification", see Nonini 1992: 33-36) and the land that can be cultivated by the Orang Asli has been reduced to a minimum. The village community of Kampung Peta has grown significantly and the increased importance of the market economy has undermined what Maeda calls the "exchange of moral order" between people.

Within families, however, there is still some circulation of goods and services. The village is too big a family now and these exchanges take place in the closest branches. Children who have an income contribute to sustaining their parents, whether they are elderly or caring for school-going children, so much so that few elderly people among my respondents receive the *Kebajikan Masyarakat*, an allowance of RM 300 or so allocated to older people without other resources. The children move from house to house, spending their free time with their cousins. Women, who are often responsible for children because fathers are busy with other tasks, can always leave the care of their offspring to a sister or cousin.

Adults move around less easily, especially when they are parents. Asma practices the art of *berhendeng*, going to eat at each other's home, which is governed by certain rules: it is reserved

for close family, involves offering food to compensate for the food one eats and it is better accepted from unmarried people. Nevertheless, this expression implies a suspicion of abuse. Groups of people who eat together remain fairly flexible and there are many invitations between people from the same family. It is common to borrow (*tumpang, numpang*) various objects in this context: scooters are the ones that circulate in the most obvious way. The *kelamin* is therefore not the only area in which goods circulate, but the continuous exchange of gifts ("constant give and take") no longer takes place at the village level but only at the level of the close family.

8.3.2 Individualisation of Destinies

The social organisation of the village and the reduction of "moral exchanges" do not smooth out the inequalities that increase in wages, hence Maeda's concern that the generalization of "technical exchanges" will lead to the formation of economic classes (Maeda 2001: 62). The village land is too small and not all *kelamins* have enough to live on. There are disparities among all of them, which Colin Nicholas explains in a general history of land allocation to indigenous villages.

In the past, you work the land, the land is yours. Green paddy and so on. Once your activity ceases, the land goes back to the forest and to the community. But when the government came in with this policy of preservation and all this kind of things, they gave houses and lots. Specially rubber, each family a rubber lot, usually 6 acres per family (...). These lots became fixed. No more scope for expanding, no more new land. The first person gets 6 acres, but after that you have five children, you give all to one person or you divide by 5. It becomes smaller and smaller. After many generations, there's nothing to give up. (interview with Colin Nicholas)

The collection of rattan makes it possible to cope with the lack of land, as well as the wage labour does. The income that everyone gets from one occupation or another is disparate: there are "rich" and "poor" people in the village and no redistribution mechanism can reduce the gap between them. The villagers' discourses commenting on this situation often involve individual merit: those who earn enough are "smart" (*pandai*) or "hard-working" (*rajin*), the others are "stupid" (*bodoh*) or "lazy" (*malas*). In the event of failure, villagers are more likely to blame themselves than they blame the economic situation: Hatiqah, whose grocery store went bankrupt

during the closure of the Taman Negara at a time when much less money was circulating in Kampung Peta, says she suffered this failure because she was "lazy". Syazrina and her daughter Asma have very harsh words for Qalesya and her husband Ismail, a cousin of Syazrina's who inherited two small plots of land and sold one to his sister. They say he is a lazy man who does not take responsibility for his large family. "[Qalesya], she is nothing," says Asma during our survey of the village. Land is limited, but she says there are plenty of opportunities to get by. There is school, there is self-employment in agriculture or tourism, and at worst there is rattan and *pucuk*. She mentions to me several times the expression of Western tourists who have given her a life lesson: everyone is responsible for their own success or failure⁷⁰ and it is this lesson that she delivers to a classmate whose husband has just lost his job on the plantation and who only has to collect rattan with him.

Zubaidah : When there's no food, we help each other in the village⁷¹.

Asma : You must go to work if you want something because nobody helps you, you make the responsibility your home.

Zubaidah : Not everyday people help you.

Asma : For everything have the forest for sale. (interview with Zubaidah)

We saw that the options were limited for the villagers of Kampung Peta. Those who succeed in school have opportunities but elsewhere, provided they integrate into Malaysian urban society and do not stay in the village. Because in the village public jobs are not for them. Only Umairah, the *tadika* teacher, has a qualified job that matches her level of education. She says she takes advantage of the fact that her colleagues are not interested in the location of the job. The other graduates have had to leave the village or remain in the village without opportunity (Syamsul has a background in accountancy and Hainil, Kamaruddin's wife, has a bachelor's degree in political science from Universiti Sains Malaysia). They are all under 40 years old, for those I met, which suggests that these school and university opportunities are recent. Despite these constraints, Asma relies on individual merit and is very pessimistic about the possibility of having a collective destiny.

I have a principle. If you want to succeed in life, don't wait for anyone. I think we're

70 The fact that the lesson is delivered by Westerners who earn their income in a part of the world where salaries are structurally so high compared to those of indigenous Malaysians may be enough to call into question the weight of individual merit in someone's destiny.

71 "Kalau tak ada makan, kampung tolong-tolong."

alone in life. One day we won't be together with Mother, we won't always live with our friends, sometimes we need to make our own life.⁷² (interview with Asma)

Paradoxically, Asma is one of the people most involved in the life of the village and particularly in projects outside: she participates in the ICCA project and is the village referent for Gerai OA (even if she does not produce any handicrafts). She therefore navigates between the two registers that are the responsibility of the individual and the apprehension of the village as a body capable of carrying out together the collective initiatives proposed from the outside – because it is always in a collective register that these initiatives are formulated. Colin Nicholas proposes to carry out these projects without any illusion on the motivation (according to him very mixed) for the common good: "Nobody works for free," he says, but he does not despair of the village's capacity to organise itself collectively. The lack of effectiveness of the initiatives that have been carried out so far (such as the construction of the first bungalows) is due only to epiphenomena. "The community is united but it's not organised. Wrong people were given responsibility" (interview with Colin Nicholas). He therefore proposes structures that are partly community-based and partly private, from which the people who maintain them and the community that remains in control benefit. Individual self-interest could, in his view, contribute to the effectiveness of these structures better than volunteering.

Jakun society remains structurally egalitarian, with equal participation of everyone in collective decisions, but it is evolving into an unequal society in which individualism and individual choices and actions are becoming the norm. The Kampung Peta community is unique in that environmental degradation has little or no impact on it, and unlike other Orang Asli communities, it is only deprived of the use of the forest (including opening it up) through legal provisions. But similar changes can be observed in other Orang Asli villages and peoples: the Temiar (Nobuta 2009), the Semai (Gomes 2004 and Nicholas *et al.* 2003), the Batek (Endicott and Endicott 2012), to name but a few studies focused on economy. These developments have been driven by structural economic changes and the extension of the market economy into rural communities, changes that have also disrupted Malay village communities (Scott 2008). These changes, sometimes disruptions, may be experienced positively (access to consumer goods, richer food) or as a loss, especially when it comes to cultural transformations. Development too is an "ambiguous blessing".

72 "Saya ada prinsip. Kalau mau berjaya, jangan tunggu orang. Saya percaya kita ada life sendiri. One day kita not always together dengan Mak, kita tak selalu hidup dengan kawan, sometimes kita perlu ada kehidupan sendiri."

Conclusion

In the 1960s, the village of Kampung Peta was almost entirely occupied with subsistence agriculture and the collection of rattan and forest products. The following decades introduced a greater variety of economic activities: sedentary commercial agriculture on reserve lands (rubber trees in particular), wage employment (in the public and private sectors), and independent service activities (trade, tourism). All these forms of activity coexist today and offer a plurality of destinies, some miserable and others more enviable.

Villagers express strong preferences between these different opportunities, which are based on several criteria. Those that bring the highest and most stable income are the most appreciated... but sometimes the two are antinomic and one has to choose between a risky independence and the assurance of earning a modest salary every month. The bond of wage subordination, which was so despised in the 1960s, is now scorned only by people who are very self-confident and know they can rely on their own skills. Others dream of a job that protects them from material hardship. The drudgery of some jobs makes them unattractive, from collecting rubber amidst mosquitoes to carrying heavy loads of rattan. We have seen the difference in appreciation between the latter occupation and hands-free walks in the forest and how much the arduousness of the load devalues the whole experience. Both tour guides and Wildlife Conservation Society staff appreciate the forest setting in which they work, while rattan collectors dream of a more sedentary activity. Being home for lunch, being able to take a nap... keeping time for oneself is also part of the criteria according to which the rattan is an unenviable occupation, which villagers only resolve when they are confronted with a lack of cultivable land. Even if the repetitive or low-value nature of the activities was the subject of few judgements in the interviews I conducted, the inhabitants of Kampung Peta do not fail to note when a task is rewarding, especially when it allows them to demonstrate their skills (in construction or life in the forest). This appreciation, in contrast to the contempt in which the Orang Asli are often held in Malaysia, is an important element in the villagers' attraction to tourism jobs. Having contacts with the outside world that are not the administration and its Malay face makes it possible to get away from the paternalistic logic that usually prevails between Malays and Orang Asli, some perceived as modern and others as backward.

Tourism is a service activity different from those that can be found in the neighbouring villages: it leads to a remote village wealthy urbanites and foreigners who earn a higher salary and value in every sense of the word those who are in contact with them. The remuneration from tourism is out of all proportion to what most of the inhabitants of Kampung Peta are entitled to and no initiative has so far found a way to avoid its concentration. Tourism opens up the village to the outside world, a contact that is unanimously appreciated and which does not arouse any mistrust. However, the values of the wealthy urban classes or Western tourists are very different from those who have long organised Jakun social life. Without appreciating the values of the host society or understanding the difference with their own, these outsiders sometimes advocate a straight forward individualism and claim that everyone should be held responsible for their own fate.

In this context, the action of external actors such as the Malaysian Nature Society, which foreshadowed the national park, the current administration of the Taman Negara and the United Nations Development Programme has yielded a wide range of results. The Taman Negara, arguably the largest provider of direct income in the village with its nineteen employees, is nevertheless the least appreciated institution, accused even of not properly protecting the customary lands it has appropriated. The Taman Negara, an employer deemed indelicate and an opposing party in a lawsuit, clearly does not have the community's interests at heart and just pays some of the people in the village while others have no choice but to engage in prohibited commercial collections. The MNS and UNDP have each in their own way tried to share out the tourism windfall, and the latter, which runs an indigenous community conservation programme (ICCA), is imagining alternatives to tourism and more accessible and inclusive economic activities. UNDP's change of strategy, in a village where almost everyone dreams of working in tourism, commits it to follow the next developments. Is it necessary to despair of tourism in order to sustain local communities and not only its most dynamic entrepreneurs? What agricultural choices are capable of compensating for the unequal distribution of land in a context of scarcity? In the current system of values, which hesitates between a practice of solidarity and sending back each person to their individual responsibilities, what economy is capable of providing the Jakun with a certain material ease without further undermining the structures that regulate their social life?

Appendices

Glossary

adat : custom

ayam bandar : industrial chicken

ayam hutan : wild gallinacea

ayam kampung : farm chicken

babi hutan : wild boar

batin : indigenous village leader

belukar : secondary forest

berhendeng (*jakun*) : eating at other people's

bomoh : shaman, traditional healer (Malay or indigeous)

dulu : before, long time ago

dusun : orchard

gotong-royong : productive activity carried out together by villagers or neighbours

hutan : forest

ikat : bundle (rattan stems)

jin : spirit (Jin Bumi : spirit of the land)

kampung : village

kebun : garden, orchard

kelamin : couple, nuclear family (Jakun)

keluarga : extended family (Jakun)

kenduri : feast, reception

keramat : sacred place

kongsi : association, co-operation

ladang : field, meadow

malu : shy, shameful

Orang Asli : natural human beings, post-Independance term for indigenous people in peninsular Malaysia

Orang Asal : original human beings, post-Independance term for indigenous people in eastern Malaysia, now reclaimed by indigenous people in peninsular Malaysia

padi bukit : hill rice, cultivated without water input

pawang : shaman, master of the rites (Malay or indigenous)

petai : legume of high commercial value

pondok : hut
rotan : rattan
saudara : sister or brother, cousin
sendiri : bachelor, independent, someone living by herself
Taman Negara : national parc
tikar : mat
tumpang/numpang : borrow
ubi : roots and tubers (cassava, sweet potato, taro)
ulu : upriver
pucuk : edible leave
tawkey : trader

Acronyms

COAC : Centre for Orang Asli Concerns, advocacy ressource centre
FELDA : Federal Land Development Authority, a state-owned company, now listed on the stock exchange, responsible for establishing rubber and oil palm farmers on pioneering agricultural fronts
ICCA : Indigenous Community Conservation Area, UNDP programme
JHEOA (until 2011) : Jabatan Hal Ehwal Orang Asli, bureau of Orang Asli affairs
JAKIM : Jabatan Kemajuan Islam Malaysia, bureau for the development of Malaysian Islam
JAKOA (since 2011) : Jabatan Kemajuan Orang Asli, bureau for the development of Orang Asli
JKKK : Jawatankuasa Kemajuan dan Keselamatan Kampung, village development and safety committee (used to be **JKK** : Jawatan Kuasa Kampung, village committee)
JOASM : Jaringan Orang Asal SeMalaysia, majority organization of the indigenous people in Malaysia
MNS : Malaysian Nature Society, oldest nature association in Malaysia funded in 1940
PH : Pakatan Harapan, coalition ruling Malaysia since 2018
POASM : Persatuan Orang Asli Semenanjung Malaysia, majority organization of the indigenous people of peninsular Malaysia
PNUD/UNDP : Programme of United Nations for development
RM : Ringgit Malaysia, Malaysian currency
UMNO : United Malays National Organisation, party ruling coalition Barisan Nasional from Independence since 2018
WCS : Wildlife Conservation Society, US environmental NGO operating in Malaysia

Interviews

<i>Name (most names were changed)</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Location</i>
Ahmad and Zarina	13 March	Kampung Peta
Munirah	16 March	Kampung Peta
Asma	17 March, 19 April et 20 April	Kampung Peta
Iman	17 March et 7 April	Kampung Peta
Syazrina	20 March	Kampung Peta
Hatiqah	23 March	Kampung Peta
Machang	24 March	Kampung Peta
Farah	25 March	Kampung Peta
Kamaruddin and Hainil	26 March	Kampung Peta
Qalesya <i>with Asma</i>	27 March	Kampung Peta
Hatiqah <i>with Asma</i>	27 March	Kampung Peta
Umairah and Zulkifli	28 March	Kampung Peta
Saiful	30 March	Kampung Peta
Syazwani <i>with Asma</i>	1 st April	Kampung Peta
Zubaidah <i>with Asma</i>	1 st April	Kampung Peta
Syamsul	2 April, 8 April et 14 April	Kampung Peta
Saifuddin and his wife	9 April	Kampung Peta
Rampuyan (<i>batin</i>)	10 April	Kampung Peta
Rabiah	13 April	Kampung Peta
Fatimah and Nasrul	13 April	Kampung Peta
Syazwan and his wife	15 April	Kampung Peta
Nazim	18 April	Kampung Peta
Fatin et Suhail	19 April	Kampung Peta
Jef	22 April	Ulu Beranang Jeramkedah
Lee Shin-Shin	24 April	Putrajaya
Colin Nicholas	26 April	Subang Jaya
Ann Cheong	27 April	Petaling Jaya
Shanthy Thambiah	2 May	Kuala Lumpur
Endau Rompin Peta Management	11 June	By e-mail
Reita Rahim	3 July	By e-mail
Shanthy Thambiah	16 August	By e-mail

Table 4. List of interviews taken between March and August 2019.

Households Sources of Income

<i>Name (every name was changed)</i>	<i>Activity(s)</i>	<i>Other</i>
Iman and Omar	Tourism (<i>pribadi</i>) Plantation wage	Less gifts to the family
Hatiqah and Saiful	Rubber Wage Taman Negara	Handicraft
Machang (married, number of children unknown)	Fishing Rottan Rubber	Rents the plot and the boat he uses
Kamaruddin and Hainil	Rubber Tourism (<i>pribadi</i>)	Sometimes rottan
Qalesya and Ismail	Rottan	7 children including one in boarding school
Hatiqah	Gifts from the children	
Zulkifli Umairah	Wage Taman Negara Wage tadika	
Saiful (single)	Wage Wildlife Conservation Society	
Syazwani and her husband	Handicraft Wage Taman Negara	4 children in school, including university, schooling aids
Zubaidah et Luqman	Rottan Rubber	
Syamsul (single)	Tourism (<i>pribadi</i>)	
Syamsul and his wife	Rubber	Durians
Rabiah (single)	Pension JAKIM	Shop: more expenses than income
Fatimah Nasrul	Rottan Rubber	Durians
Syazwan and Sardila	Fish tourisme	Fruits
Suhail and Fatin	Wage in Kahang Sewing	Selling soft drinks less the rent in Kahang

Table 5. Main income sources of households interviews in March-April 2019 in Kampung Peta.

Maps, Diagrams and Photos

Map 1. Fédération de Malaysia (Malaisie), physical map.
Uwe Dederling, Malaysia_relief_location_map.jpg, Wikimedia.org, accessed 18 July 2019.

Map 2. Districts of Johor state, peninsular Malaysia.
Goran tek-en, Districts_and_PBT_of_Johor.svg, Wikimedia Commons, accessed 8 July 2019.

Map 3. Settlement on Endau River by Orang Hulu in the 1960.
 MAEDA TACHIMOTO, Narifumi, 2001, *The Orang Hulu: A Report on Malaysian Orang Asli in the 1960s*, Subang Jaya: COAC : 15.

Map 4. Current settlement on Endau River.
 From Open Street Map, screenshot 16 July 2019.

Map 5. Kampung Peta and national parc Endau-Rompin, entrance Peta. Some settlements in grey. From Open Street Map, screenshot 8 July 2019.

Map 6. Relief map of Kampung Peta.
Date and screenshot from <http://elevation.maplogs.com/> accessed 8 July 2019 (rights reserved Google).

Photo 20. Satellite photo of Kampung Peta.
 Google Maps, screenshot 1st August 2019.

Map 7. Extract from the map produced by the villagers of Kampung Peta with the Centre for Orang Asli Concerns to support their claims in the case of Sangka Chuka & Anor vs. Pentadbir Tanah Daerah Mersing, Johor & Ors (2012-2018). Photograph A. Vidal, taken in April 2019.

The map above shows the indigenous reserve in blue (221 hectares), the disputed lands in beige, and an area of 100 hectares in brown, of which the eastern part, the right bank of the river, was the subject of the dispute.

Map 8. Map produced by the villagers of Kampung Peta with the Centre for Orang Asli Concerns to support their claims in the case of Sangka Chuka & Anor vs. Pentadbir Tanah Daerah Mersing, Johor & Ors (2012-2018). Photograph A. Vidal, taken in April 2019.

Diagram 1. Annual rainfall in Kampung Peta.
<https://fr.climate-data.org/asia/malaysia/johor/kampung-peta-972308/>
 Accessed 8 July 2019.

Diagram 2. Annual temperature in Kampung Peta.
<https://fr.climate-data.org/asia/malaysia/johor/kampung-peta-972308/>
 Accessed 8 July 2019.

Map 9. Map of deforested areas in the extended environment of Kampung Peta. Deforested areas in 2017 in red and in 2018 in turquoise blue.

From screenshot 8 July 2019, <http://earthenginepartners.appspot.com/science-2013-global-forest>.

HANSEN, M. C. *et al.*, 2013, "High-Resolution Global Maps of 21st-Century Forest Cover Change", *Science*, 342 (6160).

Diagram 3. House plan in Kampung Peta: Iman and Omar's house. Realisation: A. Vidal.

List of Photographs, Tables, Maps and Diagrams

Photo 1: Prayer room (*surau*).

Photo 2. Health centre (*pusat rawatan kesihatan*).

Photo 3. SK, Sekolah Kebangsaan Kampung Peta.

Photo 4. Marriage of Adam and Farah, 25 March 2019.

Photo 5. Tomb of Zulkarnain and rite performed by his widow Syazrina.

Photo 6. Meeting between Colin Nicholas (COAC) and the inhabitants of Kampung Peta under the *balai budaya*.

Photo 7. Syazrina clearing a plot of land.

Photo 8. Rattan *manau*.

Photo 9. The *tawkey rotan* is loading the goods he buys.

Photo 10. Zarina cleaning the rattan.

Photo 11. Balqis and her husband clearing a plot of land.

Photo 12. Rabiah in her shop.

Photo 13. Villagers get supplies from Jeffrey's yellow truck.

Photo 14. *Kedai oren*, the orange soda shop run by Suhail and Fatin.

Photo 15. Basketry by Hatiqah.

Photo 16. Building a perahu by Sam.

Photo 17. Camp site, bungalows (and sanitary facilities).

Photo 18. Courtyard for camping.

Photo 19. Poster for the Kampung Peta indigenous festival on August 8, 2019, featuring a villager.

Photo 20. Satellite photo of Kampung Peta.

Table 1. Comparison of key human development indicators between Orang Asli and the general Malaysian population.

Table 2. Employed persons in Kampung Peta.

Table 3. Wage trends of non-indigenous and indigenous workers in Kampung Chang Lama

(Perak).

Table 4. List of interviews conducted between March and August 2019.

Table 5. Main income of households interviewed in March-April 2019 in Kampung Peta.

Map 1. Federation of Malaysia (Malaysia), physical map.

Map 2. Districts of Johor State, Peninsular Malaysia.

Map 3. Orang Hulu settlement of the Endau River in the 1960s.

Map 4. Current settlement of the Endau River.

Map 5. Kampung Peta and Endau-Rompin National Park, Peta Entrance.

Map 6. Relief map of Kampung Peta.

Map 7. Excerpt from the map produced by the villagers of Kampung Peta.

Map 8. Map produced by the villagers of Kampung Peta.

Map 9. Map of deforested areas in the extended environment of Kampung Peta.

Diagram 1. Annual rainfall in Kampung Peta.

Diagram 2. Annual temperatures at Kampung Peta.

Diagram 3. Plan of a house in Kampung Peta.

Bibliography

ABDUL Rahman, 1989, in BENJAMIN 2015 : 4, note 12

ABORIGINAL PEOPLES ACT 1954, 2006 (rééd.), Laws of Malaysia (Act 134), 18 pages

ADAMS, Kathleen, 2009, "Indonesian souvenirs as micro-monuments to globalization and modernity: Hybridization, deterritorialization and commodification", in HITCHCOCK, Michael, KING, Victor T. et PARNWELL, Michael (ed.), *Tourism in Southeast Asia: Challenges and New Directions*, Copenhagen: NIAS Press, 69-82.

ANDAYA, Leonard Y., 2002, "Orang Asli and the Melayu in the History of the Malay Peninsula", *Journal of the Malaysian Branch of the Royal Asiatic Society*, 75 (1) (282): 23-48

ANDAYA, Leonard, 2008, *Leaves of the Same Tree*, Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press

ASSISTANT PROTECTOR OF ABORIGINES, 1954, letter dated 22 May 1954 from Assistant Protector of Aborigines, Mersing, to Protector of Aborigines of the Federation of Malaya, Kuala Lumpur

AZIZAN Marzuki, 2010, "Tourism development in Malaysia. A review on federal government policies", *Theoretical and Empirical Researches in Urban Management*, 5 (8) (17): 85-97

BAER, Adela, 2006, "The Health of Orang Asli Women", in BAER, A., ENDICOTT, Karen, GIANNO, Rosemary, HOWELL, Sign, NOWAK, Barbara S. et van der SLUYS, Cornelia, *Orang Asli Women of Malaysia*, Subang Jaya: COAC, 107-130

BAER, Adela, 2010, "Orang Asli (Indigenous Malaysian) Biomedical Bibliography", <https://ir.library.oregonstate.edu/downloads/6q182m326>, consulté le 16 juillet 2019

BEAUD, Stéphane et WEBER, Florence, 1998, *Guide de l'enquête de terrain* (1997), Paris : La Découverte

BENJAMIN, Geoffrey, 2002, "On being tribal in the Malay world", in BENJAMIN, Geoffrey et CHOU, Cynthia (ed.), *Tribal Communities in the Malay World: Historical, Cultural and Social Perspectives*, Leiden: International Institute for Asian Studies, Singapore: Institute of Southeast Asian Studies, 7-76

BENJAMIN, Geoffrey, 2015, "Who gets to be called 'Indigenous', and why?", text of the lecture given on 10 April 2015 international conference on access to justice for indigenous peoples, Centre for Malaysian Indigenous Studies (CMIS) and Faculty of Law, University of Malaya, Kuala Lumpur, 15 pages

BORCHERS, Henning, 2009, "Dragon Tourism Revisited: The Sustainability of Tourism Development in Komodo National Park", in HITCHCOCK, Michael, KING, Victor T. et PARNWELL, Michael (ed.), *Tourism in Southeast Asia: Challenges and New Directions*, Copenhagen: NIAS Press, 270-285

CARSTEN, Janet, 1996, "Cooking money: Gender and the symbolic transformations of means of exchange in a Malay fishing community" in PARRY, Jonathan, BLOCH, Maurice (ed.), *Money and the Morality of Exchange* (1989), Cambridge (US): Cambridge University Press, 117-141

CHO, George, 1982, "Rubber smallholders in Peninsular Malaysia: problems and prospects", *Australian Geographical Studies*, 20 (2): 197-209

CONSTITUTION of the Federation of Malaysia, 1957 (revised in 2007), accessed on constituteproject.org (Comparative Constitutions Project, University of Texas at Austin) on 15 July 2019

CRABTREE-PARKER, Isabel, Jonathan *et al.*, 2016, *Death of the Dragon God Lake: Voices from Tasik Chini, Malaysia*, Petaling Jaya: SIRD

DENTAN, Robert Knox, ENDICOTT, Kirk, GOMES, Alberto G. et HOOKER, M. B., 1996, *Malaysia and the "Original People": A Case Study of the Impact of Development on Indigenous Peoples*, Boston: Allyn and Bacon

DENTAN, Robert Knox, 2008, *Overwhelming Terror: Love, Fear, Peace, and Violence among the Semai of Malaysia*, Lanham, MD: Rowman and Littlefield

DEPARTMENT OF STATISTICS (DoS), 2018a, "Economic Census 2016: Tourism Statistics", Putrajaya, 3 pages

DEPARTMENT OF STATISTICS (DoS), 2018b, "Selected Demographic Indicators Malaysia", Putrajaya, 3 pages

DOVE, Michael R., 1996, "Rice-Eating Rubber and People-Eating Governments: Peasant versus State Critiques of Rubber Development in Colonial Borneo", *Ethnohistory*, Vol. 43, No. 1, 33-63

DOVE, Michael R., 2002, "Hybrid histories and indigenous knowledge among Asian rubber smallholders", *International Social Science Journal*, 54 (173) : 349-359

ECONOMIC PLANNING UNIT (EPU), 2010, "10th Malaysian Plan 2011-2015", Putrajaya, 451 pages

EMPLOYMENT ACT 1955, 2012 (reissue), Laws of Malaysia (Act 265), 120 pages

ENDICOTT, Karen L., 1981, "The conditions of egalitarian male-female relationships in foraging societies", *Canberra Anthropology*, 4 (2): 1-10

ENDICOTT, Kirk, 1984, "The economy of the Batek of Malaysia: Annual and historical perspectives", *Research in Economic Anthropology*, 6: 29-52

ENDICOTT, Kirk, 2016, "Introduction", 1-38, in ENDICOTT, Kirk (ed.) *Malaysia's Original People: Past, Present and Future of the Orang Asli*, Singapour: NUS Press

ENDICOTT, Kirk et DENTAN, Robert, 2004, *Into the Mainstream or Into the Backwater? Malaysian Assimilation of Orang Asli In Civilizing the Margins: Southeast Asian Government Policies for the Development of Minorities*, Singapour: NUS Press, p. 24-55

ENDICOTT, Kirk, LYE Tuck-Po, NURUL Fatanah Zahari, RUDGE, Alice, 2016, "Batek Playing Batek for Tourists at Peninsular Malaysia's National Park", *Hunter Gatherer Research*, 2 (1): 97-121

ENDICOTT, Kirk M. et Karen L., 2012, *The Headman Was a Woman: The Gender Egalitarian Batek of Malaysia* (2008), Subang Jaya: Center for Orang Asli Concerns

EVANS, I. H. N., 1923, *Studies in Religion, Folk-lore, & Custom in British North Borneo and the Malay Peninsula*, Cambridge: The University Press

FOOD AND AGRICULTURE ORGANIZATION, 1997, "Asia-Pacific Forestry Sector Outlook Study: Country Report – Malaysia", working paper No APFSOS/WP/07, 10. "Non-Wood Forest Produce - Status And Trends", Kuala Lumpur (non-paginated, accessed on 28 July 2019, <http://www.fao.org/3/W7701E/W7701E00.htm>)

FAVRE, P. É. L., 1865, *An Account of the Wild Tribes Inhabiting the Malayan Peninsula, Sumatra and a Few Neighbouring Islands, With a Journey in Johore and a Journey in the Menangkabaw States of the Malayan Peninsula*, Paris: Imperial Printing Office

GHEE, Lim Teck, 1974, "Malayan Peasant Smallholders and The Stevenson Restriction Scheme, 1922-28", *Journal of the Malaysian Branch of the Royal Asiatic Society*, 47 (2): 105-122

GIANNO, Rosemary, 2006, "What Happened to the Female Midwives? Gender, Childbirth, and Change in Semelai Society", in BAER, A., ENDICOTT, Karen, GIANNO, Rosemary, HOWELL, Sign, NOWAK, Barbara S. et Van der SLUYS, Cornelia, 2006, *Orang Asli Women of Malaysia*, Subang Jaya: COAC, 91-106

GIANNO, Rosemary, BAYR, Klaus J., 2009, "Semelai agricultural patterns: Toward an understanding of variation among indigenous cultures in southern peninsular Malaysia", *Journal of Southeast Asian Studies*, 40 (1): 153-185

GOMES, Alberto G., 2004, *Looking for Money: Capitalism and Modernity in an Orang Asli Village*, Subang Jaya: Center for Orang Asli Concerns et Melbourne: Trans Pacific Press

GUÉRIN, Mathieu, 2017a, « Conserver la faune sauvage de la péninsule malaise, de la Malaya britannique à la Malaisie indépendante », *VertigO*, vol. 17, n° 1 (non paginé, mis en ligne le 25 mai 2017, consulté le 29 décembre 2018, <http://journals.openedition.org/vertigo/18503>)

GUÉRIN, Mathieu, 2017b, « Protéger la forêt et sa faune contre les indigènes en Malaya Britannique », *Péninsule*, 75 : 37-71

HANSEN, M. C., POTAPOV, P. V., MOORE, R., HANCHER, M., TURUBANOVA, S. A., TYUKAVINA, A., THAU, D., STEHMAN, S. V., GOETZ, S. J., LOVELAND, T. R., KOMMAREDDY, A., EGOROV, A., CHINI, L., JUSTICE, C. O., TOWNSHEND, J. R. G., 2013, « High-Resolution Global Maps of 21st-Century Forest Cover Change », *Science*, 342 (6160): pp.?

HARPER, T. N., 1997, "The Politics of the Forest in Colonial Malaya", *Modern Asian Studies*, 31 (1): 1-29

HARPER, T. N., 2001, *The End of Empire and the Making of Malaya*, Cambridge (UK): Cambridge University Press

HERVEY, D. F. A., 1879, "A Trip To Gunong Blumut", *Journal of the Straits Branch of the Royal Asiatic Society*, 3: 85-115

HERVEY, D. F. A., 1881, "The Ęndau and its Tributaries", *Journal of the Straits Branch of the Royal Asiatic Society*, 8: 93-132

HITCHCOCK, Michael et I. NYOMAN Darma Putra, 2009, "Terrorism and tourism in Bali and Southeast Asia", in HITCHCOCK, Michael, KING, Victor T. et PARNWELL, Michael (ed.), *Tourism in Southeast Asia: Challenges and New Directions*, Copenhagen: NIAS Press, 83-98

HOMEWOOD, Katherine M. et RODGERS, W. A., 1991, *Maasailand Ecology. Pastoralist Development and Wildlife Conservation in Ngorongoro, Tanzania*, Cambridge (UK): Cambridge University Press

HOWELL, Signe, 1983, "Chewong women in transition: The effect of monetisation on a hunter-gatherer society of Malaysia", *Women and Development in South East Asia*, Canterbury: Centre for South-East Asian Studies, University of Kent

JHEOA, 1983, "Strategi Perkembangan Ugama Islam di Kalangan Masyarakat Orang Asli", in NICHOLAS 2000 : 255

KRATOSKA, Paul H., 1985, "The peripatetic peasant and land tenure in British Malaya", *Journal of Southeast Asian Studies*, 1985, 16 (1), 16-45

LAFAYE DE MICHEAUX, Elsa, 2012, *La Malaisie, un modèle de développement souverain ?*, Lyon : ENS Éditions

LAKE, H. W., KELSALL, H. J., 1894, "A Journey On The Sembrong River. From Kuala Indau To Batu Pahat", *Journal of the Straits Branch of the Royal Asiatic Society*, 26: 1-33

LEMBAGA GETAH MALAYSIA, 2018, "Natural Rubber Statistics 2018", (26 pages, accessed on 31 July 2019, <http://www.lgm.gov.my/nrstat/nrstats.pdf>)

LOGAN, J. R., 1847, "The Orang Binua of Johore", *Journal of the Indian Archipelago and Eastern Asia*, 1:242-293

LUQUIAU, Clotilde, 2013, « Les animaux sauvages au village. Entre sources de conflits et attractions touristiques (Bornéo, Sabah, Malaysia) », *Carnets de géographes*, n° 5, 1-19 (mis en ligne le 1er janvier 2013, consulté le 30 juin 2019, <http://journals.openedition.org/cdg/1068>)

LUQUIAU, Clotilde, 2015, « La nature écartelée : tourisme, environnement et développement dans la Kinabatangan à Bornéo (Sabah, Malaisie) », thèse de doctorat en géographie humaine, Université de Paris Ouest-Nanterre-La Défense, non publiée

LYE, Tuck-Po, 2018, *Changing Pathways: Forest Degradation and the Batek of Pahang, Malaysia* (2004), Petaling Jaya: SIRD

MAEDA TACHIMOTO, Narifumi, 2001, *The Orang Hulu: A Report on Malaysian Orang Asli in the 1960s*, Subang Jaya: COAC

MAHATHIR Mohamad, 1970, *The Malay Dilemma*, in BENJAMIN 2015 : 4, note 12

MALAYSIAKINI, 2019, "Cops, rangers to conduct joint anti-poaching patrols", 6 juillet 2019

MALAYSIAN TOURISM PROMOTION BOARD, 2019, "Tourist arrivals", accessed on 12 August 2019 sur <http://mytourismdata.tourism.gov.my>

MANICKAM, Sandra Khor, 2015, *Taming the Wild: Aborigines and Racial Knowledge in Colonial Malaya*, Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press

MILNER, Anthony, 2008, *The Malays*, Hoboken: Wiley-Blackwell

MILNER, Anthony, 2016, *Kerajaan: Malay Political Culture on the Eve of Colonial Rule* (1982), Petaling Jaya: SIRD

MINISTRY OF EDUCATION (MoE), 2013, "Malaysia Education Blueprint 2013-2025 (Preschool to Post-Secondary Education)", Putrajaya in UNDP 2013 : 149

MOHD NAPI Daud, PUSHPARAJAH, E. et SUBRAMANIAM, T., 1987, "Development of a Statistical Model for Optimum Density in *Hevea*", *Journal of Rubber Research*, 2 (3) : 142-151

MOHD NAZLAN Mohd Ghazali JC, 2016, High Court Malaya, judgment of Sangka Chuka & Anor vs. Pentadbir Tanah Daerah Mersing, Johor & Ors, Johor Bahru: Judicial Review No: 25-27-02-2012, 11 January 2016

NATIONAL FORESTRY ACT 1984, 2006 (reissue), Laws of Malaysia (Act 313), 92 pages

NATIONAL PARKS ACT 1980, 2013 (reissue), Laws of Malaysia (Act 226), 14 pages

- NICHOLAS, Colin, 1999, "Providing for Beneficially Active Socio-Economic Involvement of the Jakun of Kampung Peta in the Endau-Rompin National Park", non published, 28 pages
- NICHOLAS, Colin, 2000, *The Orang Asli and the Contest for Ressources*, Copenhagen: IWGIA and Subang Jaya: COAC
- NICHOLAS, Colin, 2013, "Expert Report on the History, Presence and Occupation of the Jakun-Orang Asli in the Kampung Peta-Ulu Endau Customary Territory", non publié, 19 pages
- NICHOLAS, Colin, TIJAH Yok Chopil, TIAH Sabak, 2003, *Orang Asli Women and the Forest: The Impact of Resource Depletion on Gender Relations among the Semai*, Subang Jaya: COAC
- NICHOLAS, Colin, JENITA Engi, TEH, Yen Ping, 2010, *The Orang Asli and the Undrip: From Rhetoric to Recognition*, Subang Jaya: Center for Orang Asli Concerns et Jaringan Orang Asal SeMalaysia
- NOBUTA, Toshihiro, 2009, *Living on the Periphery: Development and Islamization Among the Orang Asli in Malaysia (2008)*, Subang Jaya: COAC
- NONINI, Donald M., 1992, *British Colonial Rule and the Resistance of the Malay Peasantry, 1900-1957*, New Haven: Yale University Southeast Asia Studies
- NOWAK, Barbara S., 1986, *Marriage and Household: Btsisi? Response to a Changing World*, thèse de doctorat, State University of New York at Buffalo
- ROSNIZA Aznie, C. R., LYNDON, N., YAAKOB, M. J., MOHD AZLAN, A., SYAHIRAN, M. D., et BESAR, J. A., LAM, K.C., MOKHTAR, J., MAZRIN Rohizaq, C.R., 2018, "Independent Oil Palm Smallholder's Challenges in Malaysia", *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 8 (13): 68-75
- RUSASLINA Idrus, 2010, "From Wards to Citizens: Indigenous Rights and Citizenship in Malaysia", *PoLAR: Political and Legal Anthropology Review*, 33 (1): 89-108

SCHEBESTA, Paul, 1973, *Among the Forest Dwarfs of Malaya* (1928), Kuala Lumpur: Oxford University Press

SCOTT, James C., 2008, *Weapons of the Weak: Everyday Forms of Peasant Resistance*, New Haven: Yale University Press

SELANGOR, 1895, "Minutes on Sel.Sec/2852/1895", in HARPER 1997 : 8

SELLATO, Bernard, 2006, « Systèmes juridiques traditionnels et gestion des ressources naturelles à Bornéo », cours non publié

SHEEMA Abdul Aziz, CLEMENTS, Gopalasamy Reuben, RAYAN, Darmaraj, SANKAR, Preetha 2013, "Why conservationists should be concerned about natural resource legislation affecting indigenous peoples' rights: Lessons from Peninsular Malaysia", *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 22 (3): 639-655

SKEAT, Walter William, BLAGDEN, Charles Otto, 1906, *Pagan Races of the Malay Peninsula*, London: MacMillan and Co

THE STAR, 2019, "'We feel we may go extinct': Orang Asli are starving in Perak's jungles", 5 mai 2019

SUHAKAM (Human Rights Commission of Malaysia), 2013, "Report of the National Inquiry Into the Land Rights of Indigenous Peoples", 192 pages

THAMBIAH, Shanthi, 1999, "Orang Asli Women and Men in Transition" in JOMO K. S. (ed.), *Rethinking Malaysia*, Hong-Kong: Asia 2000 et Kuala Lumpur: Malaysian Social Science Association, 267-292

THOMPSON, Eric, 2012, *Unsettling Absences: Urbanism in Rural Malaysia* (2007), Singapour: NUS Press

UMNO, 1948, letter dated 6 April 1948 from UMNO secretary general to Deputy Chief Secretary of the Federation of Malaya

UNDP, 2013, *Malaysia Human Development Report*, Kuala Lumpur, 362 pages

UNDP, n.d., "Malaysia Country Profile Sheet for ICCA-GSI", accessed on <https://www.sgp.undp.org/about-us-157/partnerships/icca-gsi.html> 12 August 2019

WILDLIFE CONSERVATION ACT 2010, 2014 (reissue), Laws of Malaysia (Act 716), 192 pages

WOLLENBERG, Eva et ANI Septiani Nawir, 1998, "Estimating the Incomes of People who Depend on Forests", in WOLLENBERG, Eva et INGLES, Andrew (ed.), *Incomes from the Forest: Methods for the Development and Conservation of Forest Products for Local Communities*, Bogor: Center for International Forestry Research, 157-188

ZACCAÏ, Edwin, 2002, *Le Développement durable. Dynamique et constitution d'un projet*, Berne-Bruxelles : PIE-Peter Lang

ZANARIAH Hussein *et al.*, 2015, "Diabetes Care in Malaysia: Problems, New Models, and Solutions", *Annals of Global Health*, 81 (6): 851-862

Table of Contents

Terima kasih.....	2
Introduction.....	5
Chapter 1. Orang Asli in Malaysia	
1.1. Orang Asli in Malaysia, a Complex of Peoples.....	7
1.2. Political and Economic Situation of the Orang Asli.....	9
1.3. Jakun in the Orang Asli Complex of Peoples.....	12
Chapter 2. Kampung Peta	
2.1. Situation and History.....	15
2.2. Description of the village.....	17
2.2.1. Access.....	17
2.2.2. Natural Environment.....	17
2.2.3. Houses and Settlements.....	18
2.3. Equipment.....	19
2.3.1. Water and Electricity.....	19
2.3.2. Public Services.....	20
2.3.3. Means of Communication and Transportation.....	21
Chapter 3. Rituals and Society	
3.1. Rites of Passage.....	23
3.1.1. Being Born and Being Named.....	23
3.1.2. Marriage and Matrimonial Strategies.....	25
3.1.3. Funeral Rituals.....	28
3.1.4. Other Rituals.....	30
3.2. Social Organisation and Family.....	34
3.2.1. The Batin and the Village Committee.....	34
3.2.2. Gotong-royong.....	36
3.2.3. Land.....	37
3.2.4. The Kelamin Family Group.....	38
Chapter 4. Subsistence Activities	
4.1. Food Self-production.....	41
4.1.1. Fishing, Hunting, Gathering.....	42
4.1.2. Subsistence Agriculture.....	43
4.2. Decline in Subsistence Activities.....	45
4.2.1. Animal Intrusions and Crop Damages.....	45
4.2.2. Preferences for Commercial Activities.....	47
Chapter 5. Primary Sector Commercial Activities	
5.1. Collecting and Trading Rattan.....	53
5.1.1. A Long-Standing Commercial Activity.....	53
5.1.2. Economic, Environmental, and Social Issues.....	54
5.1.3. Trading Rattan Today.....	56
5.2. Rubber Agriculture.....	60
5.2.1. Introduction of Rubber Tree Cultivation in Malaysia.....	60

5.2.2. Rubber Agriculture in Kampung Peta.....	62
5.3. Other Cash Crops.....	65
5.3.1. Cultivation and Trade in Durian and Other Seasonal Fruits.....	65
5.3.2. Oil Palm and Agricultural Prospects.....	67
 Chapter 6. Self-Employment (Except Primary Sector) and Wage Employment	
6.1. Retail Trade and Handicraft.....	69
6.1.1. Retail Trade.....	69
6.1.2. Handicraft.....	72
6.2. Employment Except Tourism.....	75
6.2.2. Public Sector Employment.....	76
6.3. Other Sources of Income.....	77
6.4. Moral Order and Technical Order.....	79
 Chapter 7. Tourism Economy	
7.1. Employment in Tourism.....	81
7.1.1. Employment in Taman Negara.....	81
7.1.2. Different Statuses of Tourist Guides.....	82
7.1.3. Other Tourism Jobs.....	84
Photo 16. Building of a perahu by Sam. Photo A.Vidal, March-April 2019.....	84
7.1.4. Distribution of Income from Tourism.....	87
7.2. Kampung Peta and the Taman Negara, a Momentous History.....	89
7.2.1. Malaysian Nature Society in Kampung Peta.....	90
7.2.2. The Village Community and Environmental Protection Requirements.....	91
7.2.3. Deterioration of Relations with the Taman Negara.....	93
7.2.4. Future of Tourism in Kampung Peta.....	96
 Chapter 8. Several Effects of Market Economy	
8.1 Expenditure Trends and Growth of Wage Employment.....	101
8.1.1 First Gendered Division of Labour.....	101
8.1.2 The Rise of Monetary Needs.....	102
8.2 Inequalities between Women and Men.....	105
8.2.1. Inequalities between Women and Men in the Labour Market.....	105
8.2.2. Implications for Gender Inequality.....	108
8.3 Other Inequalities.....	110
8.3.1 Exchanges in the Family Sphere.....	110
8.3.2 Individualisation of Destinies.....	111
Conclusion.....	115
Appendices.....	117
Glossary.....	118
Interviews.....	120
Households Sources of Income.....	121
Maps, Diagrams and Photos.....	122
List of Photographs, Tables, Maps and Diagrams.....	129
Bibliography.....	131